

Scheme S1. Structure of product **S1** obtained from the condensation of compounds **7** and **9**.

Figure S1. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, 298K, CDCl₃) of monocondensed product S1.

Figure S2. Different packings observed in the crystal structures of 1-5.

Figure S3. Normalized absorption (solid line) and fluorescence (dotted line) spectra of model benzothiadiazoles substituted with either two TIPS-acetylenes or two TPS-acetylenes on the 4,7 positions in CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S4. Concentration-dependent emission spectra of compounds **1-5** ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 400$ nm). Inset: Fitting curves of the emission intensity as a function of solution concentration.

Figure S5. Normalised solution (solid line) and solid state (dashed line) emission spectra of compounds **1-5**.

TIPS

TPS

Figure S6. Normalized cyclic voltammograms of model benzothiadiazoles substituted with either two TIPS-acetylenes or two TPS-acetylenes on the 4,7 positions in $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NPF}_6$ (0.1 M) in CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure S7. Orbitals from top to bottom, **1-5** computed at the B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)-Dichloromethane.

Table S1. Selected conditions used for the condensation of compounds **7** and **9**.

Entry	Reaction conditions	Result
1	AcOH, reflux	S1 (84%)
2	CHCl ₃ /AcOH 2:1, reflux	S1 (78%)
3	1,2-dichlorethane/AcOH 3:1, reflux	S1 (75%)
4	<i>m</i> -cresol, 180 °C	no reaction
5	TiCl ₄ , pyridine, DCM, r.t.	S1 (20%)
6	S1 + 9 , CCl ₄ /AcOH 3:1, reflux	degradation

Table S2. Orbital energies for **1-5** computed at the B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)-Dichloromethane

	B3LYP-6-31G(d,p)-Dichloromethane				
	S_0-S_1 / nm	Osc. Strenght	LUMO / eV	HOMO / eV	GAP /eV
1	453	0.49	-2.61	-5.75	3.15
2	449	0.39	-2.68	-5.87	3.19
3	443	0.49	-2.64	-5.79	3.15
4	456	0.52	-2.69	-5.91	3.22
5	443	0.37	-2.71	-5.93	3.22

General Experimental Methods

All reagents and solvents were purchased from Fisher Scientific, ABCR, Alfa Aesar, Sigma Aldrich or VWR, and were used without further purification unless specified otherwise. Preparation of air moisture sensitive materials was carried out in dried flasks under nitrogen atmosphere employing standard Schlenk techniques. Anhydrous THF was dried using an Innovative Pure Solve solvent purification system.

Column chromatography was performed on Silica gel 60 (40-60 μm) from Scharlab. Analytical thin layer chromatography (TLC) was carried out using aluminum sheets (20x20 cm) pre-coated with silica gel RP-18W 60 F254 from Merck). UV-active compounds were detected using a UV-lamp from CAMAG at wavelength $\lambda = 254$ or 366 nm.

NMR spectra in solution were recorded on a Bruker Avance 400 MHz or 500 MHz spectrometer at 298K using partially deuterated solvents as internal standards.

High Resolution Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization (coupled to a Time-Of-Flight analyzer) Mass Spectrometry experiments were recorded in CIBiomaGUNE in a Ultraflex III (Bruker Daltonics) MALDI-ToF (frequency-tripled (355 nm) Nd:YAG laser) by Dr. Javier Calvo.

X-ray data collections were performed in an Agilent Supernova diffractometer equipped with an Atlas CCD area detector, and a $\text{CuK}\alpha$ micro-focus source with multilayer optics ($\lambda = 1.54184\text{\AA}$, 250 μm FWHM beam size) by Dr. Leire Sanfelices (SGiker, University of the Basque Country). The quality of the crystals was checked under a polarizing microscope, and a suitable crystal or fragment was mounted on a Mitegen Micromount TM using Paratone-N inert oil and transferred to the diffractometer. The samples were kept at 150(10)K with an Oxford Cryosystems Cryostream 700 cooler.

Absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 950 spectrometer.

Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a LS55 Perkin-Elmer Fluorescence spectrometer. The photoluminescence quantum yield (PQLY) was measured following equation 1:

$$\Phi_f^i = \Phi_f^s \cdot \frac{F^i f_s \eta_i^2}{F^s f_i \eta_s^2} \quad (1)$$

where Φ_f^s stands for the quantum yield of the reference standard; F^i for the measured fluorescence (area) of a solution at known concentration at the selected excitation wavelength; F^s is the measured fluorescence (area) of a solution at known concentration of reference standard at the selected excitation wavelength; $f_s = 1 - 10^{-A_s(\lambda_{exc})}$ stands for the absorption factor of a solution at a known concentration of the reference standard at the excitation wavelength; $f_i = 1 - 10^{-A_i(\lambda_{exc})}$ stands for the absorption factor of a solution at known concentration of

given products at the excitation wavelength. Finally, η_i is the refraction index of the solvent of the solution of the given compounds; η_s refers to the refraction index of the solvent of the solution of the reference standard. 9,10-Diphenylanthracene (DPA) was selected as reference standard ($\Phi_f^{DPA} = 0.93$)^[35] at the concentration of $7.57 \cdot 10^{-7}$ M in cyclohexane ($\eta_{CHex} = 1.45$). The excitation wavelength was set at 357 nm. Three different solutions at different concentration of each hexacene were analyzed and quantum yields were expressed as the average of the three measurements with its associated error (Table S2). The solid-state emission spectra were recorded using the drop-casting technique with a compound concentration of 1 mg/1 mL in dichloromethane. The excitation wavelength was set to 400 nm, and the optical fluorescence spectra were measured in the wavelength range spanning from 400 to 700 nm. A 3 nm slit width was employed for this measurement.

Table S2. Quantum yields.

	Φ_f^i		Φ_f^i		Φ_f^i
1	28.83 (± 1.57)	%	3	78.18 (± 0.41)	%
2	66.33 (± 0.55)	%	4	38.04 (± 1.19)	%
			5	75.48 (± 0.79)	%

Electrochemical measurements were carried out on a Princeton Applied Research Parstat 2273 in a 3-electrode single compartment cell with glassy carbon disc working electrode, a platinum wire counter electrode and a silver wire pseudoreference electrode. All the potential values are reported versus the redox potential of the ferrocene/ferrocenium couple.

Compound 1

In a flame-dried Schlenk flask, 14 mg of tetraketone **6** (374.15 g/mol, 38 μmol) and 40 mg of diamine **9** (468.88 g/mol, 85 μmol , 2.2 eq.) were suspended in 2 mL of AcOH. The resultant suspension was heated at 55 °C under inert atmosphere. Reaction was monitored by TLC until consumption of starting material. When reaction was completed, the resultant mixture was cooled down to room temperature, cold methanol was added and the suspension was filtered, affording 40 mg of **1** (32 μmol) as yellow solid in 86% yield.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{CDCl}_3\text{-}d^1$): δ = 9.90 (4H, s, H_a), 8.03 (4H, s, H_b), 1.70 (18H, s, H_e) and 1.28 (42H, m, $\text{H}_{c,d}$).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{CDCl}_3\text{-}d^1$): δ = 151.05, 143.43, 142.03, 135.12, 129.36, 125.82, 124.32, 104.51, 99.98, 35.81, 31.90, 19.12 and 11.73.

HRMS (MALDI-ToF): (m/z) [M] $+\text{H}^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{80}\text{H}_{111}\text{N}_4\text{Si}_4$: 1239.7885; found: 1239.7866.

UV [$\lambda(\epsilon)$] [$\text{nm}(M^{-1})$]: 338(116463), 413 (49256), 435(54417).

Compound 2

In a flame-dried Schlenk flask, 25 mg of tetraketone **6** (374.15 g/mol, 67 μ mol) and 135 mg of diamine **10** (672.24 g/mol, 200 μ mol, 3 eq.) were suspended in 3 mL of AcOH. The resultant suspension was refluxed under inert atmosphere. Reaction was monitored by TLC until consumption of starting material. When reaction was completed, the resultant mixture was cooled down to room temperature, cold methanol was added and the suspension was filtered, affording 103 mg of **2** (62 μ mol) as yellow solid in 93% yield.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{CDCl}_3\text{-d}^1$): δ = 9.73 (4H, s, H_a), 8.15 (4H, s, H_b), 7.88 (24H, J = 7.7 Hz, d, H_c), 7.43 (36H, m, $\text{H}_{d,e}$) and 0.93 (18H, s, H_f).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{CDCl}_3\text{-d}^1$): δ = 151.85, 144.06, 142.62, 136.15, 134.67, 133.88, 130.42, 129.39, 128.48, 126.82, 126.32, 124.48, 106.70, 98.69 and 31.34.

HRMS (MALDI-ToF): (m/z) [M] $+\text{H}^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{116}\text{H}_{87}\text{N}_4\text{Si}_4$: 1647.5974; found: 1647.6042.

UV [$\lambda(\epsilon)$] [$\text{nm}(M^{-1})$]: 338(279291), 413(126033), 435(118390).

Compound 3

In a flame-dried Schlenk flask, 25 mg of tetraketone **7** (574.91 g/mol, 43 μ mol) and 87 mg of diamine **10** (672.98 g/mol, 130 μ mol, 3 eq.) were suspended in 3 mL of AcOH. The resultant suspension was heated at 80 °C under inert atmosphere. Reaction was monitored by TLC until consumption of starting material. When reaction was completed, the resultant mixture was cooled down to room temperature, cold ethanol was added and the suspension was filtered. Crude solids were loaded into a flash chromatography column (eluent hexane/dichloromethane 3:2) and the desired fraction was precipitated on ethanol affording 28 mg of **3** (15 μ mol) as yellow solid in 40% yield.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃-d₁): δ = 9.94 (4H, s, H_a), 8.16 (4H, s, H_b), 7.83 (24H, J= 7.56 Hz, d, H_c), 7.43 (36H, m, H_{d,e}), 1.24 (6H, m, H_f) and 0.74 (36H, d, H_g).

¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃-d₁): δ = 143.68, 142.09, 136.90, 135.81, 135.56, 133.77, 130.12, 128.70, 128.3, 128.25, 124.42, 107.12, 98.14, 18.60 and 11.03.

HRMS (MALDI-ToF) (*m/z*) [M+Ag]⁺ calcd. for C₁₂₆H₁₁₀AgN₄Si₆: 1953.6397; found: 1953.6483.

UV [$\lambda(\epsilon)$] [*nm*(*M*⁻¹): 335(10843), 418(50470), 443(58092).

Compound 4

In a flame-dried Schlenk flask, 25 mg of tetraketone **8** (779.01 g/mol, 32 μ mol) and 45 mg of diamine **9** (468.88 g/mol, 96 μ mol, 3 eq.) were suspended in 5 mL of MeOH/AcOH 2:3. The resultant suspension was heated at 80 °C under inert atmosphere. Reaction was monitored by TLC until consumption of starting material. When reaction was completed, the resultant mixture was cooled down to room temperature, cold methanol was added and the suspension was filtered. Crude solids were loaded into a flash chromatography column (eluent hexane/dichloromethane 7:3) and the desired fraction was precipitated on ethanol affording 48 mg of **4** (29 μ mol) as dark yellow solid in 90% yield.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃-d¹): δ = 10.06 (4H, s, H_a), 7.92 (4H, s, H_b), 7.73 (12H, dd, H_g), 7.40 (18H, m, H_{e,i}), 1.26 (6H, m, H_c) and 0.99 (36H, d, H_d).

¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃-d¹): δ = 142.81, 142.08, 136.73, 136.68, 134.82, 134.56, 134.35, 129.79, 129.34, 129.02, 128.15, 124.26, 104.45, 100.54, 18.90, 11.47.

HRMS (MALDI-ToF): (*m/z*) [M+Ag]⁺ calcd. for C₁₀₆H₁₂₂AgN₄Si₆: 1749.7336; found: 1749.7434.

UV [$\lambda(\epsilon)$] [*nm(M⁻¹)*]: 332(70769), 412(37011), 436(46660).

Compound 5

In a flame-dried Schlenk flask, 33 mg of tetraketone **8** (779.01 g/mol, 42 μmol) and 86 mg of diamine **10** (672.98, 127 μmol , 3 eq.) were suspended in 3 mL of AcOH. The resultant suspension was refluxed under inert atmosphere. Reaction was monitored by TLC until consumption of starting material. When reaction was completed, the resultant mixture was cooled down to room temperature, cold methanol was added and the suspension was filtered. Crude solids were loaded into a flash chromatography column (eluent hexane/dichloromethane 3:1) and the desired fraction was precipitated on methanol affording 38 mg of **5** (19 μmol) as dark yellow solid in 46% yield.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, $\text{CD}_2\text{Cl}_4-d^2$): δ = 10.06 (4H, s, H_a), 8.15 (4H, s, H_b), 7.71 (24H, d, J = 6.8 Hz, H_c), 7.48 (12H, d, J = 6.55 Hz, H_f), 7.34 (12H, m, J = 7.45 Hz H_g), 7.25 (24H, m, J = 7.35 Hz, H_d) and 6.98 ppm (18H, m, $\text{H}_{h,e}$).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (500 MHz, $\text{CD}_2\text{Cl}_4-d^2$): δ = 142.94, 141.50, 136.19, 135.46, 133.28, 133.14, 129.82, 129.42, 128.78, 127.89, 127.79, 123.93, 120.18, 107.24, 98.41.

HRMS (MALDI-ToF): (m/z) [M] $+\text{H}^+$ calcd. for $\text{C}_{144}\text{H}_{99}\text{N}_4\text{Si}_6$: 2051.6468; found: 2051.6502.

UV [$\lambda(\epsilon)$] [$\text{nm}(M^{-1})$]: 336(70367), 417(30565), 437(29729).

Figure S7. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR in CDCl_3 for compound **1**.

Figure S8. ¹H and ¹³C NMR in CDCl₃ for compound 2.

Figure S9. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR in CDCl_3 for compound **3**.

Figure S10. ¹H and ¹³C NMR in CDCl₃ for compound 4.

Figure S11. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR in $\text{C}_2\text{D}_2\text{Cl}_4$ for compound 5.

X-Ray Data Compound 1

a20190140_JMM226B

Table 1 Crystal data and structure refinement for a20190140_JMM226B.

Identification code	a20190140_JMM226B
Empirical formula	C ₈₀ H ₁₁₀ N ₄ Si ₄
Formula weight	1240.07
Temperature/K	150.01(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	10.8876(9)
b/Å	12.8440(8)
c/Å	16.6397(9)
α/°	72.981(5)
β/°	75.573(6)
γ/°	66.521(7)
Volume/Å ³	2017.3(3)
Z	1
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.021
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.983
F(000)	674.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.317 × 0.281 × 0.129
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	7.69 to 137.998
Index ranges	-13 ≤ h ≤ 13, -11 ≤ k ≤ 15, -18 ≤ l ≤ 20
Reflections collected	15195
Independent reflections	7483 [R _{int} = 0.0512, R _{sigma} = 0.0752]
Data/restraints/parameters	7483/61/476
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.125
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.1018, wR ₂ = 0.2885
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1264, wR ₂ = 0.3181
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	1.25/-0.44

Table 2 Fractional Atomic Coordinates (×10⁴) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters (Å²×10³) for a20190140_JMM226B. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} tensor.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
Si1	8795.7 (13)	-2242.5 (8)	9590.7 (7)	37.5 (3)
Si2	7123.7 (12)	6277.9 (8)	4304.2 (6)	33.3 (3)
N1	6870 (3)	2354 (2)	8937.4 (18)	26.8 (6)
N2	6426 (3)	4460 (2)	7716.9 (18)	26.0 (6)
C1	7261 (4)	2360 (3)	8105 (2)	28.6 (8)

C2	7892 (4)	1273 (3)	7844 (2)	32.6 (8)
C3	8257 (5)	1289 (3)	6988 (3)	39.3 (9)
C4	8031 (5)	2335 (3)	6370 (2)	37.8 (9)
C5	7429 (4)	3402 (3)	6601 (2)	29.9 (8)
C6	7031 (4)	3431 (3)	7479 (2)	26.1 (7)
C7	6038 (4)	4447 (3)	8538 (2)	26.4 (7)
C8	5363 (4)	5551 (3)	8813 (2)	27.2 (7)
C9	5158 (4)	6608 (3)	8222 (2)	31.8 (8)
C10	4488 (5)	7676 (3)	8463 (2)	35.0 (9)
C11	4010 (4)	7663 (3)	9329 (2)	31.9 (8)
C12	4204 (4)	6620 (3)	9933 (2)	27.7 (8)
C13	4892 (4)	5541 (3)	9684 (2)	25.4 (7)
C14	6264 (4)	3370 (3)	9164 (2)	26.4 (7)
C15	8134 (4)	194 (3)	8451 (2)	34.7 (9)
C16	8386 (5)	-758 (3)	8922 (3)	40.2 (10)
C17	9476 (10)	-2328 (6)	10542 (5)	37 (2)
C17B	10140 (20)	-2395 (13)	10296 (10)	52 (5)
C18	10072 (10)	-1380 (7)	10405 (7)	52 (2)
C18B	9450 (30)	-1461 (12)	10829 (12)	69 (6)
C19	10533 (5)	-3552 (4)	10855 (3)	49.8 (11)
C20	7136 (5)	-2507 (4)	9973 (3)	50.2 (11)
C21	6096 (6)	-1597 (4)	10454 (4)	62.2 (14)
C22	7340 (5)	-3738 (4)	10509 (3)	49.4 (11)
C23	9921 (5)	-3258 (3)	8888 (3)	47.4 (11)
C24	11248 (7)	-3031 (6)	8492 (4)	72.6 (17)
C25	9204 (8)	-3225 (5)	8201 (4)	70.4 (17)
C26	7226 (4)	4445 (3)	5946 (2)	31.7 (8)
C27	7125 (5)	5247 (3)	5329 (2)	36.2 (9)
C28	6174 (5)	5966 (4)	3656 (3)	43.9 (10)
C29	6671 (7)	4683 (5)	3602 (5)	67.7 (16)
C30	6079 (7)	6769 (7)	2781 (4)	78 (2)
C31	8946 (5)	6106 (4)	3864 (3)	51.0 (11)
C32	9835 (11)	4929 (7)	3627 (5)	66 (2)
C32B	9700 (40)	4765 (9)	3909 (17)	66 (2)
C33	9058 (9)	7173 (7)	3140 (5)	58.4 (19)
C33B	9300 (30)	6707 (19)	2932 (9)	58 (6)
C34	6187 (6)	7801 (4)	4495 (3)	53.5 (12)
C35	6906 (9)	8061 (5)	5044 (5)	87 (2)
C36	4705 (6)	8022 (5)	4841 (4)	68.8 (16)
C37	4312 (5)	8823 (3)	7800 (3)	43.3 (10)
C38	3624 (9)	8846 (5)	7101 (4)	62.0 (19)
C38B	2780 (30)	9440 (20)	7757 (19)	78 (7)
C39	3450 (11)	9886 (5)	8171 (4)	75 (3)
C39B	4780 (30)	9597 (19)	8108 (15)	62 (5)
C40	5725 (10)	8896 (7)	7399 (6)	78 (3)

C40B

5030 (30)

8658 (19)

6920 (14)

63 (5)

Table 3 Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for a20190140_JMM226B.
The Anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: -
 $2\pi^2[h^2a^2U_{11}+2hka^*b^*U_{12}+\dots]$.

Atom	U ₁₁	U ₂₂	U ₃₃	U ₂₃	U ₁₃	U ₁₂
Si1	58.6 (7)	11.1 (5)	31.0 (6)	1.1 (4)	-8.7 (5)	-3.0 (4)
Si2	47.6 (6)	23.3 (5)	22.3 (5)	4.1 (4)	-6.3 (4)	-11.5 (4)
N1	40.5 (17)	11.5 (12)	22.2 (14)	0.6 (10)	-6.4 (12)	-4.8 (11)
N2	38.4 (16)	13.8 (13)	22.1 (14)	2.0 (10)	-9.3 (12)	-6.9 (11)
C1	42 (2)	12.5 (15)	25.3 (17)	2.0 (13)	-10.0 (15)	-5.2 (13)
C2	48 (2)	16.5 (16)	26.2 (18)	0.8 (13)	-7.6 (15)	-6.3 (15)
C3	60 (3)	16.9 (16)	31 (2)	-5.9 (14)	-4.0 (17)	-4.3 (16)
C4	60 (3)	22.6 (18)	23.7 (18)	-1.4 (14)	-7.5 (16)	-8.7 (17)
C5	39 (2)	18.0 (16)	26.1 (17)	-1.2 (13)	-5.6 (14)	-5.7 (14)
C6	33.9 (18)	14.3 (15)	23.7 (17)	1.4 (13)	-8.4 (14)	-3.6 (13)
C7	34.3 (18)	16.7 (16)	23.8 (17)	2.3 (13)	-8.7 (14)	-6.6 (13)
C8	40 (2)	14.1 (15)	23.6 (17)	1.3 (13)	-8.3 (14)	-7.4 (13)
C9	55 (2)	13.5 (15)	19.9 (16)	2.0 (12)	-6.7 (15)	-7.6 (15)
C10	58 (2)	17.1 (17)	24.6 (18)	1.7 (13)	-9.5 (16)	-9.4 (16)
C11	47 (2)	12.1 (15)	29.3 (18)	2.1 (13)	-9.1 (15)	-6.2 (14)
C12	42 (2)	12.4 (15)	22.3 (17)	2.2 (12)	-9.0 (14)	-5.1 (14)
C13	34.2 (18)	15.3 (16)	24.1 (17)	1.3 (14)	-7.6 (14)	-8.1 (13)
C14	36.9 (19)	13.8 (15)	24.4 (17)	-0.1 (12)	-7.6 (14)	-5.7 (13)
C15	54 (2)	14.1 (16)	27.8 (18)	-4.3 (14)	-4.9 (16)	-4.2 (15)
C16	63 (3)	16.3 (17)	30.7 (19)	-2.7 (14)	-5.7 (18)	-6.2 (16)
C17	47 (5)	26 (3)	31 (4)	-7 (3)	-13 (3)	-1 (3)
C17B	65 (12)	41 (8)	43 (9)	-5 (6)	-1 (8)	-22 (9)
C18	66 (6)	32 (4)	62 (6)	-11 (4)	-21 (4)	-14 (4)
C18B	114 (19)	17 (6)	73 (13)	6 (7)	-38 (12)	-17 (8)
C19	61 (3)	29 (2)	53 (3)	2.9 (18)	-22 (2)	-9.4 (19)
C20	55 (3)	28 (2)	56 (3)	-4.6 (19)	-9 (2)	-4.9 (18)
C21	62 (3)	32 (2)	77 (4)	-9 (2)	0 (3)	-9 (2)
C22	53 (3)	26 (2)	60 (3)	6.5 (18)	-17 (2)	-11.0 (18)
C23	71 (3)	14.3 (16)	40 (2)	-1.5 (15)	-5 (2)	-1.7 (17)
C24	65 (4)	63 (4)	66 (4)	-7 (3)	6 (3)	-12 (3)
C25	111 (5)	49 (3)	47 (3)	-18 (2)	-10 (3)	-20 (3)
C26	44 (2)	19.6 (17)	25.3 (18)	-5.1 (14)	-4.4 (15)	-5.2 (14)
C27	53 (2)	21.2 (17)	27.4 (18)	1.7 (14)	-8.0 (16)	-9.1 (16)
C28	53 (3)	46 (2)	31 (2)	-0.7 (17)	-5.4 (18)	-22 (2)
C29	69 (4)	67 (4)	80 (4)	-35 (3)	-11 (3)	-25 (3)
C30	93 (5)	117 (5)	40 (3)	22 (3)	-28 (3)	-71 (4)
C31	51 (3)	66 (3)	34 (2)	0 (2)	-12.1 (19)	-24 (2)
C32	51 (4)	89 (4)	58 (5)	-43 (4)	4 (4)	-11 (3)

C32B	51 (4)	89 (4)	58 (5)	-43 (4)	4 (4)	-11 (3)
C33	57 (5)	80 (5)	38 (3)	-3 (4)	1 (3)	-34 (4)
C33B	49 (9)	69 (10)	53 (10)	-9 (7)	-1 (7)	-25 (8)
C34	78 (4)	25 (2)	47 (3)	8.3 (17)	-12 (2)	-17 (2)
C35	120 (6)	43 (3)	112 (6)	-34 (3)	-36 (5)	-19 (3)
C36	70 (4)	43 (3)	78 (4)	-22 (3)	-9 (3)	2 (2)
C37	73 (3)	19.3 (17)	29.4 (18)	1.9 (14)	-11.1 (18)	-10.9 (17)
C38	99 (5)	31 (3)	46 (3)	20 (2)	-34 (3)	-20 (3)
C38B	75 (10)	63 (9)	74 (10)	15 (8)	-16 (8)	-22 (8)
C39	130 (7)	20 (3)	39 (3)	6 (2)	-2 (4)	-7 (3)
C39B	91 (10)	44 (8)	58 (9)	0 (6)	-19 (7)	-35 (7)
C40	99 (7)	47 (4)	75 (5)	27 (4)	-19 (5)	-38 (4)
C40B	82 (10)	43 (8)	50 (8)	3 (6)	-5 (7)	-18 (7)

Table 4 Bond Lengths for a20190140_JMM226B.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å	Atom	Atom	Length/Å
Si1	C16	1.844 (4)	C11	C12	1.393 (5)
Si1	C17	1.866 (7)	C12	C13	1.418 (5)
Si1	C17B	2.01 (2)	C12	C14 ¹	1.463 (5)
Si1	C20	1.891 (6)	C13	C13 ¹	1.449 (6)
Si1	C23	1.863 (4)	C15	C16	1.210 (6)
Si2	C27	1.827 (4)	C17	C18	1.532 (8)
Si2	C28	1.879 (5)	C17	C19	1.563 (8)
Si2	C31	1.882 (5)	C17B	C18B	1.538 (10)
Si2	C34	1.892 (5)	C17B	C19	1.462 (17)
N1	C1	1.343 (5)	C20	C21	1.527 (7)
N1	C14	1.327 (5)	C20	C22	1.529 (6)
N2	C6	1.348 (4)	C23	C24	1.535 (8)
N2	C7	1.323 (5)	C23	C25	1.520 (8)
C1	C2	1.433 (5)	C26	C27	1.214 (6)
C1	C6	1.435 (4)	C28	C29	1.539 (7)
C2	C3	1.376 (6)	C28	C30	1.518 (7)
C2	C15	1.425 (5)	C31	C32	1.539 (7)
C3	C4	1.405 (5)	C31	C32B	1.572 (10)
C4	C5	1.387 (5)	C31	C33	1.562 (7)
C5	C6	1.424 (5)	C31	C33B	1.546 (9)
C5	C26	1.435 (5)	C34	C35	1.518 (9)
C7	C8	1.464 (5)	C34	C36	1.511 (9)
C7	C14	1.440 (4)	C37	C38	1.520 (8)
C8	C9	1.395 (5)	C37	C38B	1.54 (3)
C8	C13	1.409 (5)	C37	C39	1.520 (8)
C9	C10	1.397 (5)	C37	C39B	1.53 (2)
C10	C11	1.403 (6)	C37	C40	1.545 (11)

C10 C37 1.535(5) C37 C40B 1.51(2)

¹1-X,1-Y,2-Z

Table 5 Bond Angles for a20190140_JMM226B.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C16	Si1	C17	110.1(3)	C8	C13	C13 ¹	121.4(4)
C16	Si1	C17B	105.6(5)	C12	C13	C13 ¹	120.2(4)
C16	Si1	C20	106.1(2)	N1	C14	C7	121.1(3)
C16	Si1	C23	107.07(19)	N1	C14	C12 ¹	118.7(3)
C17	Si1	C20	108.0(4)	C7	C14	C12 ¹	120.2(3)
C20	Si1	C17B	128.0(6)	C16	C15	C2	175.7(4)
C23	Si1	C17	116.2(3)	C15	C16	Si1	176.9(3)
C23	Si1	C17B	99.6(5)	C18	C17	Si1	112.7(6)
C23	Si1	C20	109.0(2)	C18	C17	C19	110.1(7)
C27	Si2	C28	106.7(2)	C19	C17	Si1	113.0(5)
C27	Si2	C31	106.6(2)	C18B	C17B	Si1	107.3(15)
C27	Si2	C34	108.4(2)	C19	C17B	Si1	110.0(11)
C28	Si2	C31	116.7(2)	C19	C17B	C18B	110.0(12)
C28	Si2	C34	109.3(2)	C21	C20	Si1	111.7(4)
C31	Si2	C34	108.8(2)	C21	C20	C22	111.1(4)
C14	N1	C1	118.0(3)	C22	C20	Si1	111.5(3)
C7	N2	C6	118.1(3)	C24	C23	Si1	112.2(4)
N1	C1	C2	119.0(3)	C25	C23	Si1	111.8(4)
N1	C1	C6	121.1(3)	C25	C23	C24	110.5(5)
C2	C1	C6	119.9(3)	C27	C26	C5	172.7(4)
C3	C2	C1	118.5(3)	C26	C27	Si2	171.0(3)
C3	C2	C15	120.3(3)	C29	C28	Si2	114.5(4)
C15	C2	C1	121.2(3)	C30	C28	Si2	112.8(4)
C2	C3	C4	122.0(3)	C30	C28	C29	111.4(5)
C5	C4	C3	121.1(4)	C32	C31	Si2	115.4(6)
C4	C5	C6	119.1(3)	C32	C31	C33	113.3(6)
C4	C5	C26	119.0(3)	C32B	C31	Si2	105.0(15)
C6	C5	C26	122.0(3)	C33	C31	Si2	111.2(4)
N2	C6	C1	120.4(3)	C33B	C31	Si2	118.9(10)
N2	C6	C5	120.1(3)	C33B	C31	C32B	105.6(8)
C5	C6	C1	119.5(3)	C35	C34	Si2	110.4(4)
N2	C7	C8	119.2(3)	C36	C34	Si2	112.4(4)
N2	C7	C14	121.3(3)	C36	C34	C35	112.9(5)
C14	C7	C8	119.5(3)	C10	C37	C38B	107.1(10)
C9	C8	C7	120.7(3)	C10	C37	C40	108.9(4)
C9	C8	C13	119.9(3)	C38	C37	C10	109.5(4)
C13	C8	C7	119.3(3)	C38	C37	C40	108.4(6)
C8	C9	C10	122.1(3)	C39	C37	C10	112.9(4)

C9	C10	C11	117.9 (3)	C39	C37	C38	107.6 (6)
C9	C10	C37	120.8 (3)	C39	C37	C40	109.5 (6)
C11	C10	C37	121.3 (3)	C39B	C37	C10	108.9 (9)
C12	C11	C10	121.2 (3)	C39B	C37	C38B	108.0 (16)
C11	C12	C13	120.5 (3)	C40B	C37	C10	113.4 (9)
C11	C12	C14 ¹	120.2 (3)	C40B	C37	C38B	107.8 (16)
C13	C12	C14 ¹	119.3 (3)	C40B	C37	C39B	111.4 (14)
C8	C13	C12	118.4 (3)				

¹1-X,1-Y,2-Z

Table 6 Torsion Angles for a20190140_JMM226B.

A	B	C	D	Angle/°	A	B	C	D	Angle/°
N1	C1	C2	C3	178.4 (4)	C14	C7	C8	C13	-2.9 (5)
N1	C1	C2	C15	-1.2 (6)	C14 ¹	C12	C13	C8	-178.5 (3)
N1	C1	C6	N2	0.7 (6)	C14 ¹	C12	C13	C13 ¹	0.9 (6)
N1	C1	C6	C5	-178.4 (4)	C15	C2	C3	C4	179.8 (4)
N2	C7	C8	C9	-1.5 (6)	C16	Si1	C17	C18	-22.8 (8)
N2	C7	C8	C13	177.0 (3)	C16	Si1	C17	C19	-148.5 (5)
N2	C7	C14	N1	0.0 (6)	C16	Si1	C20	C21	-57.4 (4)
N2	C7	C14	C12 ¹	-178.5 (3)	C16	Si1	C20	C22	177.6 (3)
C1	N1	C14	C7	-0.4 (6)	C16	Si1	C23	C24	61.0 (4)
C1	N1	C14	C12 ¹	178.2 (3)	C16	Si1	C23	C25	-63.8 (4)
C1	C2	C3	C4	0.2 (7)	C17	Si1	C20	C21	60.6 (5)
C2	C1	C6	N2	179.4 (4)	C17	Si1	C20	C22	-64.5 (4)
C2	C1	C6	C5	0.3 (6)	C17	Si1	C23	C24	-62.4 (5)
C2	C3	C4	C5	0.1 (7)	C17	Si1	C23	C25	172.7 (4)
C3	C4	C5	C6	-0.3 (7)	C17B	Si1	C20	C21	68.2 (7)
C3	C4	C5	C26	179.7 (4)	C17B	Si1	C20	C22	-56.9 (7)
C4	C5	C6	N2	-179.1 (4)	C17B	Si1	C23	C24	-48.7 (6)
C4	C5	C6	C1	0.0 (6)	C17B	Si1	C23	C25	-173.6 (6)
C6	N2	C7	C8	-179.2 (3)	C20	Si1	C17	C18	-138.2 (7)
C6	N2	C7	C14	0.7 (5)	C20	Si1	C17	C19	96.2 (6)
C6	C1	C2	C3	-0.4 (6)	C20	Si1	C23	C24	175.4 (4)
C6	C1	C2	C15	-180.0 (4)	C20	Si1	C23	C25	50.5 (4)
C7	N2	C6	C1	-1.0 (5)	C23	Si1	C17	C18	99.0 (7)
C7	N2	C6	C5	178.1 (3)	C23	Si1	C17	C19	-26.6 (7)
C7	C8	C9	C10	178.4 (4)	C23	Si1	C20	C21	-172.3 (4)
C7	C8	C13	C12	-178.1 (3)	C23	Si1	C20	C22	62.6 (4)
C7	C8	C13	C13 ¹	2.5 (6)	C26	C5	C6	N2	0.9 (6)
C8	C7	C14	N1	179.9 (3)	C26	C5	C6	C1	-179.9 (4)
C8	C7	C14	C12 ¹	1.4 (5)	C27	Si2	C28	C29	-51.6 (4)
C8	C9	C10	C11	-0.3 (7)	C27	Si2	C28	C30	179.6 (4)
C8	C9	C10	C37	178.3 (4)	C27	Si2	C31	C32	66.4 (5)

C9 C8 C13C12	0.5 (6)	C27 Si2 C31 C32B	51.7 (13)
C9 C8 C13C13 ¹	-178.9 (4)	C27 Si2 C31 C33	-162.8 (4)
C9 C10C11C12	0.4 (6)	C27 Si2 C31 C33B	169.5 (11)
C9 C10C37C38	55.0 (7)	C27 Si2 C34 C35	62.0 (5)
C9 C10C37C38B	113.8 (14)	C27 Si2 C34 C36	-65.0 (4)
C9 C10C37C39	174.8 (6)	C28 Si2 C31 C32	-52.6 (5)
C9 C10C37C39B	-129.7 (12)	C28 Si2 C31 C32B	-67.4 (14)
C9 C10C37C40	-63.4 (7)	C28 Si2 C31 C33	78.2 (5)
C9 C10C37C40B	-5.0 (14)	C28 Si2 C31 C33B	50.4 (11)
C10C11C12C13	-0.1 (6)	C28 Si2 C34 C35	178.0 (5)
C10C11C12C14 ¹	178.0 (4)	C28 Si2 C34 C36	51.0 (4)
C11C10C37C38	-126.4 (5)	C31 Si2 C28 C29	67.4 (4)
C11C10C37C38B	-67.6 (14)	C31 Si2 C28 C30	-61.4 (5)
C11C10C37C39	-6.6 (8)	C31 Si2 C34 C35	-53.6 (5)
C11C10C37C39B	48.9 (13)	C31 Si2 C34 C36	179.4 (4)
C11C10C37C40	115.2 (6)	C34 Si2 C28 C29	-168.7 (4)
C11C10C37C40B	173.5 (13)	C34 Si2 C28 C30	62.5 (5)
C11C12C13C8	-0.4 (6)	C34 Si2 C31 C32	-176.8 (5)
C11C12C13C13 ¹	179.0 (4)	C34 Si2 C31 C32B	168.4 (13)
C13C8 C9 C10	-0.2 (6)	C34 Si2 C31 C33	-46.0 (5)
C14N1 C1 C2	-178.7 (4)	C34 Si2 C31 C33B	-73.8 (11)
C14N1 C1 C6	0.0 (6)	C37 C10C11C12	-178.2 (4)
C14C7 C8 C9	178.6 (4)		

¹1-X,1-Y,2-Z

Table 7 Hydrogen Atom Coordinates ($\text{\AA}\times 10^4$) and Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2\times 10^3$) for a20190140_JMM226B.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
H3	8673.93	572.46	6808.97	47
H4	8295.86	2309.97	5785.41	45
H9	5483.68	6601.69	7637.88	38
H11	3546.41	8378.93	9507.33	38
H17	8692.72	-2192.05	11012.33	45
H17B	10961.43	-2265.03	9915.04	62
H18A	10847.51	-1484.12	9947.38	78
H18B	10369.05	-1437.06	10930.85	78
H18C	9379.84	-614.12	10249.87	78
H18D	8937.33	-729.18	10475.8	104
H18E	10136.46	-1341.35	11038.92	104
H18F	8828.48	-1715.77	11311.97	104
H19A	10094.34	-4134.44	11034.98	75
H19B	10888.46	-3534.94	11335.27	75
H19C	11278.9	-3752.71	10390.29	75

H19D	9749.93	-3805.69	11047.73	75
H19E	10848.38	-3522.98	11347.77	75
H19F	11262.91	-4101.57	10543.46	75
H20	6764.02	-2433.16	9458.43	60
H21A	6409.34	-1673.04	10978.67	93
H21B	5225.21	-1716.06	10594.76	93
H21C	5984.99	-817.69	10097.35	93
H22A	7850.43	-4302.63	10148.96	74
H22B	6456.03	-3815.94	10754.5	74
H22C	7845.06	-3884.82	10966.82	74
H23	10163.15	-4062.82	9251.08	57
H24A	11826.55	-3606.89	8152.26	109
H24B	11718.79	-3092.75	8945.03	109
H24C	11047.55	-2248.55	8127.44	109
H25A	8368.34	-3385.78	8464.35	106
H25B	9798.47	-3814.68	7875.17	106
H25C	8982.74	-2453.9	7818.88	106
H28	5223.55	6147.11	3962.08	53
H29A	7588.19	4465.25	3281.4	102
H29B	6060.51	4575.53	3314.22	102
H29C	6679.05	4190.87	4177.2	102
H30A	5648.78	7578.69	2840.31	117
H30B	5536.8	6596.61	2481.81	117
H30C	6990.71	6648.67	2456.15	117
H31	9332.55	6137.28	4338.45	61
H31A	9316.18	6349.71	4242.55	61
H32A	9647.54	4299.04	4078.61	100
H32B	10792.86	4830.32	3561.13	100
H32C	9632.21	4909.08	3091.68	100
H32D	9570.16	4337.54	4498.45	100
H32E	10666.17	4607.69	3706	100
H32F	9323.49	4515.65	3550.95	100
H33A	8582.32	7256.94	2683.92	88
H33B	10014.73	7053.28	2914.03	88
H33C	8648.67	7879.47	3368.23	88
H33D	8607.61	6818.68	2604.42	87
H33E	10184.94	6219.55	2685.34	87
H33F	9335.23	7464.24	2915.21	87
H34	6229.26	8349.02	3928.78	64
H35A	6970.1	7488.18	5585.66	131
H35B	6394.48	8842.43	5151.89	131
H35C	7818.58	8019.37	4749.4	131
H36A	4255.36	7977.28	4416.5	103
H36B	4279.93	8796.62	4970.62	103
H36C	4619.4	7433.73	5360.79	103

H38A	4162.16	8172.98	6844.71	93
H38B	3549.87	9563.41	6664.18	93
H38C	2717.31	8818.1	7342.47	93
H38D	2640.09	10106.14	7274.71	117
H38E	2316.76	9701.83	8285.35	117
H38F	2415.42	8890.5	7685.25	117
H39A	2556.66	9836.51	8429.41	112
H39B	3346.23	10589.87	7718.32	112
H39C	3892.87	9916.23	8605.32	112
H39D	5771.91	9282.55	8061.46	93
H39E	4380.1	9615.79	8702.06	93
H39F	4495.19	10387.05	7756.44	93
H40A	6150.41	8951.38	7831.94	117
H40B	5630.14	9585.16	6933.4	117
H40C	6291.86	8197.09	7177.99	117
H40D	4536.64	8356.02	6676.73	95
H40E	5952.72	8103.83	6952.88	95
H40F	5051.34	9405.56	6557.98	95

Table 8 Atomic Occupancy for a20190140_JMM226B.

Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy
C17	0.645 (18)	H17	0.645 (18)	C17B	0.355 (18)
H17B	0.355 (18)	C18	0.645 (18)	H18A	0.645 (18)
H18B	0.645 (18)	H18C	0.645 (18)	C18B	0.355 (18)
H18D	0.355 (18)	H18E	0.355 (18)	H18F	0.355 (18)
H19A	0.645 (18)	H19B	0.645 (18)	H19C	0.645 (18)
H19D	0.355 (18)	H19E	0.355 (18)	H19F	0.355 (18)
H31	0.75	H31A	0.25	C32	0.75
H32A	0.75	H32B	0.75	H32C	0.75
C32B	0.25	H32D	0.25	H32E	0.25
H32F	0.25	C33	0.75	H33A	0.75
H33B	0.75	H33C	0.75	C33B	0.25
H33D	0.25	H33E	0.25	H33F	0.25
C38	0.75	H38A	0.75	H38B	0.75
H38C	0.75	C38B	0.25	H38D	0.25
H38E	0.25	H38F	0.25	C39	0.75
H39A	0.75	H39B	0.75	H39C	0.75
C39B	0.25	H39D	0.25	H39E	0.25
H39F	0.25	C40	0.75	H40A	0.75
H40B	0.75	H40C	0.75	C40B	0.25
H40D	0.25	H40E	0.25	H40F	0.25

Table 9 Solvent masks information for a20190140_JMM226B.

Number	X	Y	Z	Volume	Electron count	Content
1	0.000	0.000	0.500	223.4	34.1 ?	

Experimental

Single crystals of C₈₀H₁₁₀N₄Si₄ [a20190140_JMM226B]. A suitable crystal was selected and mounted on a SuperNova, Single source at offset/far, Atlas diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 150.01(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the ShelXS [2] structure solution program using Direct Methods and refined with the ShelXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

1. Dolomanov, O.V., Bourhis, L.J., Gildea, R.J., Howard, J.A.K. & Puschmann, H. (2009), J. Appl. Cryst. 42, 339-341.
2. Sheldrick, G.M. (2008). Acta Cryst. A64, 112-122.
3. Sheldrick, G.M. (2015). Acta Cryst. C71, 3-8.

Crystal structure determination of [a20190140_JMM226B]

Crystal Data for C₈₀H₁₁₀N₄Si₄ (*M*=1240.07 g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), *a* = 10.8876(9) Å, *b* = 12.8440(8) Å, *c* = 16.6397(9) Å, α = 72.981(5)°, β = 75.573(6)°, γ = 66.521(7)°, *V* = 2017.3(3) Å³, *Z* = 1, *T* = 150.01(10) K, μ (CuK α) = 0.983 mm⁻¹, *D*_{calc} = 1.021 g/cm³, 15195 reflections measured (7.69° ≤ 2 θ ≤ 137.998°), 7483 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0512, *R*_{sigma} = 0.0752) which were used in all calculations. The final *R*₁ was 0.1018 (*I* > 2 σ (*I*)) and *wR*₂ was 0.3181 (all data).

Refinement model description

Number of restraints - 61, number of constraints - unknown.

Details:

1. Fixed Uiso
At 1.2 times of:
All C(H) groups, All C(H,H) groups
At 1.5 times of:
All C(H,H,H) groups, All C(H,H,H,H,H,H) groups
2. Restrained distances
C32B-C31 = C32-C31 = C33B-C31 = C33-C31 = C18B-C17B = C18-C17
1.54 with sigma of 0.01
C32B-C33B
2.5 with sigma of 0.01
3. Uiso/Uanis restraints and constraints
Uanis(C38B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C39B) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
Uanis(C37) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C38) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
Uanis(C32B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C32) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
Uanis(C33B) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
Uanis(C40B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C39) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.002 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.004
Uiso(H18D) = Uiso(H18E)
Uanis(C32) = Uanis(C32B)
4. Others
Sof(C17B)=Sof(H17B)=Sof(C18B)=Sof(H18D)=Sof(H18E)=Sof(H18F)=Sof(H19D)=
Sof(H19E)=Sof(H19F)=1-FVAR(1)
Sof(C17)=Sof(H17)=Sof(C18)=Sof(H18A)=Sof(H18B)=Sof(H18C)=Sof(H19A)=Sof(H19B)=
Sof(H19C)=FVAR(1)
Fixed Sof: H31(0.75) H31A(0.25) C32(0.75) H32A(0.75) H32B(0.75) H32C(0.75)
C32B(0.25) H32D(0.25) H32E(0.25) H32F(0.25) C33(0.75) H33A(0.75) H33B(0.75)
H33C(0.75) C33B(0.25) H33D(0.25) H33E(0.25) H33F(0.25) C38(0.75) H38A(0.75)
H38B(0.75) H38C(0.75) C38B(0.25) H38D(0.25) H38E(0.25) H38F(0.25) C39B(0.25)
H39D(0.25) H39E(0.25) H39F(0.25) C40(0.75) H40A(0.75) H40B(0.75) H40C(0.75)
C40B(0.25) H40D(0.25) H40E(0.25) H40F(0.25) C39(0.75) H39A(0.75) H39B(0.75)
H39C(0.75)
- 5.a Ternary CH refined with riding coordinates:
C17(H17), C17B(H17B), C20(H20), C23(H23), C28(H28), C31(H31), C31(H31A),

C34(H34)
5.b Aromatic/amide H refined with riding coordinates:
C3(H3), C4(H4), C9(H9), C11(H11)
5.c Idealised Me refined as rotating group:
C18(H18A,H18B,H18C), C18B(H18D,H18E,H18F), C19(H19A,H19B,H19C),
C19(H19D,H19E,
H19F), C21(H21A,H21B,H21C), C22(H22A,H22B,H22C), C24(H24A,H24B,H24C),
C25(H25A,
H25B,H25C), C29(H29A,H29B,H29C), C30(H30A,H30B,H30C), C32(H32A,H32B,H32C),
C32B(H32D,H32E,H32F), C33(H33A,H33B,H33C), C33B(H33D,H33E,H33F),
C35(H35A,H35B,
H35C), C36(H36A,H36B,H36C), C38(H38A,H38B,H38C), C38B(H38D,H38E,H38F),
C39B(H39D,H39E,H39F), C40(H40A,H40B,H40C), C40B(H40D,H40E,H40F),
C39(H39A,H39B,
H39C)

This report has been created with Olex2, compiled on 2018.05.29 svn.r3508 for OlexSys. Please [let us know](#) if there are any errors or if you would like to have additional features.

X-Ray Data Compound 2

a20180181_jmm181

Table 1 Crystal data and structure refinement for a20180181_jmm181.

Identification code	a20180181_jmm181
Empirical formula	C ₁₃₀ H ₁₀₂ N ₄ Si ₄
Formula weight	1832.51
Temperature/K	149.99(10)
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁
a/Å	8.7139(4)
b/Å	36.754(2)
c/Å	17.7432(6)
α/°	90.0
β/°	99.394(4)
γ/°	90.0
Volume/Å ³	5606.5(5)
Z	2
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.086
μ/mm ⁻¹	0.868
F(000)	1932.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.451 × 0.336 × 0.11
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	6.974 to 136
Index ranges	-8 ≤ h ≤ 10, -44 ≤ k ≤ 44, -21 ≤ l ≤ 21
Reflections collected	43779
Independent reflections	19917 [R _{int} = 0.1275, R _{sigma} = 0.1535]
Data/restraints/parameters	19917/781/1192
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.195
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.1375, wR ₂ = 0.3564
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1769, wR ₂ = 0.3943
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	1.28/-0.94
Flack parameter	0.39(9)

Table 2 Fractional Atomic Coordinates (×10⁴) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters (Å²×10³) for a20180181_jmm181. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} tensor.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
Si1	6283 (4)	6725.7 (10)	3027.4 (17)	26.1 (7)
Si2	-1177 (3)	3810.7 (11)	3475.0 (16)	28.5 (8)
Si3	5055 (4)	3799.2 (10)	9846.8 (18)	27.6 (7)
Si4	12515 (3)	6721.3 (10)	9388.0 (16)	25.1 (7)
N1	7341 (11)	6104 (3)	5517 (5)	20.3 (19)
N2	2915 (12)	4461 (3)	5737 (6)	25 (2)
N3	4073 (12)	4417 (3)	7328 (6)	28 (2)
N4	8474 (12)	6073 (3)	7106 (6)	25 (2)
C1	8761 (14)	6650 (3)	5425 (7)	25 (2)

C2	8339 (14)	6355 (4)	5892 (7)	27 (3)
C3	6952 (12)	5828 (3)	5953 (6)	20 (2)
C4	5952 (13)	5544 (3)	5574 (6)	21 (2)
C5	5453 (14)	5555 (3)	4808 (7)	24 (2)
C6	4453 (14)	5297 (3)	4424 (7)	24 (2)
C7	3903 (14)	5022 (4)	4877 (7)	27 (2)
C8	4421 (13)	4996 (3)	5650 (6)	20 (2)
C9	3921 (13)	4699 (3)	6115 (6)	19 (2)
C10	2510 (13)	4179 (3)	6197 (6)	22 (2)
C11	1426 (14)	3911 (4)	5845 (7)	28 (3)
C12	952 (17)	3644 (4)	6298 (8)	36 (3)
C13	1576 (17)	3615 (4)	7085 (8)	34 (3)
C14	2663 (14)	3867 (4)	7429 (7)	26 (2)
C15	3050 (14)	4160 (3)	6982 (7)	24 (2)
C16	4470 (14)	4694 (3)	6904 (7)	23 (2)
C17	5475 (14)	4974 (3)	7286 (7)	24 (2)
C18	5953 (15)	4967 (4)	8063 (7)	27 (2)
C19	6989 (14)	5227 (4)	8453 (7)	27 (3)
C20	7464 (15)	5507 (4)	8005 (7)	28 (3)
C21	7005 (14)	5518 (4)	7217 (7)	25 (2)
C22	7546 (13)	5812 (3)	6759 (6)	20 (2)
C23	8952 (13)	6340 (3)	6670 (6)	21 (2)
C24	10030 (12)	6614 (3)	7005 (6)	18 (2)
C25	10453 (13)	6891 (4)	6533 (6)	23 (2)
C26	9857 (15)	6905 (4)	5776 (8)	31 (3)
C27	5437 (13)	5261 (3)	6026 (7)	22 (2)
C28	5967 (13)	5257 (3)	6825 (7)	22 (2)
C29	8050 (13)	6689 (4)	4649 (7)	25 (2)
C30	7422 (13)	6722 (4)	3994 (7)	24 (2)
C31	6760 (18)	7116 (4)	2451 (9)	39 (3)
C32	6295 (14)	7469 (5)	2627 (8)	45 (4)
C33	6690 (17)	7757 (5)	2148 (9)	46 (4)
C34	7460 (20)	7696 (6)	1549 (11)	58 (4)
C35	7860 (20)	7361 (6)	1375 (12)	62 (5)
C36	7486 (19)	7059 (5)	1797 (8)	45 (4)
C37	6756 (15)	6296 (4)	2532 (7)	26 (2)
C38	5757 (18)	6166 (4)	1905 (8)	38 (3)
C39	6184 (18)	5858 (4)	1523 (9)	39 (3)
C40	7584 (17)	5688 (4)	1763 (9)	39 (3)
C41	8551 (17)	5808 (4)	2413 (8)	37 (3)
C42	8177 (18)	6110 (4)	2808 (9)	39 (3)
C43	4191 (15)	6762 (4)	3111 (8)	32 (3)
C44	3111 (17)	6916 (4)	2504 (9)	37 (3)
C45	1585 (19)	6950 (6)	2564 (10)	53 (4)
C46	1060 (20)	6866 (5)	3239 (11)	54 (4)
C47	2065 (18)	6721 (5)	3871 (10)	45 (3)
C48	3602 (18)	6676 (5)	3795 (9)	45 (4)
C49	3967 (16)	5317 (4)	3566 (8)	34 (3)
C50	5360 (20)	5262 (6)	3180 (11)	61 (5)
C51	3410 (30)	5703 (6)	3326 (12)	63 (5)

C52	2770 (20)	5045 (6)	3248 (11)	58 (4)
C53	683 (13)	3909 (3)	5056 (7)	24 (2)
C54	-16 (14)	3867 (4)	4395 (7)	30 (3)
C55	-712 (17)	4167 (4)	2806 (8)	36 (3)
C56	-1103 (15)	4531 (4)	2923 (8)	31 (3)
C57	-901 (18)	4803 (4)	2388 (9)	41 (3)
C58	-210 (20)	4721 (5)	1779 (10)	50 (4)
C59	256 (19)	4361 (5)	1647 (9)	43 (3)
C60	-53 (16)	4088 (4)	2160 (8)	35 (3)
C61	-804 (16)	3352 (4)	3056 (7)	31 (3)
C62	-1829 (19)	3234 (4)	2403 (9)	41 (3)
C63	-1600 (20)	2911 (5)	2028 (11)	55 (4)
C64	-260 (20)	2700 (5)	2346 (10)	52 (4)
C65	720 (20)	2807 (5)	2999 (10)	50 (4)
C66	436 (19)	3146 (5)	3366 (10)	49 (4)
C67	-3261 (16)	3871 (4)	3581 (8)	33 (3)
C68	-4411 (17)	3959 (4)	2968 (9)	37 (3)
C69	-5890 (20)	4036 (5)	3037 (11)	54 (4)
C70	-6360 (20)	4011 (5)	3725 (11)	55 (4)
C71	-5250 (20)	3927 (5)	4361 (11)	54 (4)
C72	-3778 (18)	3849 (4)	4284 (9)	42 (3)
C73	3310 (14)	3835 (3)	8213 (7)	25 (2)
C74	3915 (14)	3793 (4)	8864 (6)	29 (3)
C75	4513 (13)	3413 (3)	10429 (6)	21 (2)
C76	4650 (18)	3052 (4)	10270 (9)	41 (3)
C77	4250 (18)	2756 (5)	10683 (10)	49 (4)
C78	3700 (20)	2831 (5)	11353 (11)	53 (4)
C79	3472 (17)	3196 (4)	11566 (8)	38 (3)
C80	3855 (16)	3471 (4)	11109 (8)	33 (3)
C81	4599 (15)	4233 (4)	10286 (7)	27.6 (7)
C82	3236 (14)	4422 (4)	10065 (7)	27.6 (7)
C83	2782 (14)	4717 (4)	10468 (8)	32 (3)
C84	3828 (17)	4839 (4)	11130 (9)	38 (3)
C85	5172 (18)	4658 (4)	11337 (9)	40 (3)
C86	5581 (17)	4366 (4)	10946 (8)	34 (3)
C87	7173 (15)	3757 (4)	9760 (8)	31 (3)
C88	8217 (16)	3625 (4)	10363 (7)	29 (3)
C89	9794 (17)	3590 (5)	10337 (9)	41 (3)
C90	10315 (18)	3687 (5)	9676 (9)	44 (3)
C91	9300 (19)	3823 (5)	9065 (9)	46 (3)
C92	7662 (17)	3853 (5)	9096 (9)	47 (4)
C93	7472 (17)	5205 (4)	9313 (8)	36 (3)
C94	8080 (30)	4827 (6)	9537 (12)	64 (5)
C95	5960 (20)	5259 (6)	9665 (11)	64 (5)
C96	8710 (20)	5470 (6)	9603 (11)	60 (5)
C97	10639 (15)	6628 (4)	7811 (8)	31 (3)
C98	11302 (15)	6663 (4)	8430 (7)	28 (3)
C99	12116 (14)	6352 (4)	10057 (7)	25 (2)
C100	12640 (19)	5989 (4)	9945 (9)	42 (3)
C101	12320 (20)	5707 (6)	10398 (10)	53 (4)

C102	11667 (19)	5791 (5)	11064 (10)	47 (4)
C103	11230 (20)	6132 (5)	11205 (10)	46 (4)
C104	11485 (15)	6417 (4)	10722 (7)	29 (3)
C105	14605 (15)	6675 (4)	9251 (7)	34 (3)
C106	15700 (20)	6558 (5)	9900 (10)	49 (4)
C107	17250 (20)	6521 (5)	9838 (11)	56 (4)
C108	17760 (20)	6582 (6)	9160 (12)	61 (5)
C109	16760 (20)	6718 (7)	8527 (12)	66 (5)
C110	15094 (19)	6746 (5)	8606 (9)	46 (3)
C111	12075 (15)	7158 (4)	9822 (7)	29.2 (18)
C112	13042 (18)	7284 (4)	10440 (8)	39 (3)
C113	12635 (18)	7612 (4)	10838 (9)	42 (3)
C114	11252 (17)	7778 (4)	10597 (8)	39 (3)
C115	10295 (18)	7647 (4)	9962 (9)	42 (3)
C116	10712 (15)	7345 (4)	9585 (7)	29.2 (18)
C1D	9110 (20)	4781 (5)	5812 (10)	99 (5)
C2D	7920 (20)	4527 (6)	5647 (8)	117 (11)
C3D	7510 (20)	4311 (5)	6225 (11)	92 (8)
C4D	8290 (20)	4348 (5)	6969 (9)	73 (6)
C5D	9490 (20)	4602 (5)	7135 (8)	90 (8)
C6D	9900 (20)	4818 (5)	6556 (12)	99 (5)
C7D	9560 (40)	4981 (9)	5137 (18)	99 (5)
C8D	2442 (17)	5804 (4)	7070 (8)	68 (4)
C13D	3693 (17)	6041 (4)	7239 (7)	68 (4)
C12D	4153 (16)	6251 (4)	6663 (9)	87 (7)
C11D	3360 (20)	6224 (4)	5919 (8)	81 (7)
C10D	2109 (19)	5987 (5)	5751 (7)	84 (7)
C9D	1649 (16)	5777 (4)	6326 (9)	86 (7)
C14D	2050 (50)	5603 (11)	7740 (20)	128 (13)

Table 3 Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for a20180181_jmm181. The Anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: $-2\pi^2[h^2a^{*2}U_{11}+2hka^*b^*U_{12}+\dots]$.

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
Si1	25.2 (11)	35.5 (12)	17.0 (10)	1.9 (10)	1.7 (9)	-0.8 (10)
Si2	13.2 (13)	65 (2)	5.6 (12)	1.3 (13)	-3.0 (10)	-1.5 (14)
Si3	25.3 (10)	37.0 (11)	19.8 (10)	0.7 (9)	2.1 (8)	-0.4 (9)
Si4	15.9 (12)	48.7 (17)	9.4 (11)	-1.7 (12)	-2.0 (9)	-2.8 (12)
N1	16 (3)	33 (4)	10 (3)	0 (3)	-4 (3)	0 (3)
N2	21 (3)	31 (3)	22 (3)	0 (2)	1 (2)	-3 (2)
N3	27 (3)	32 (3)	25 (3)	0 (2)	3 (2)	-1 (2)
N4	21 (3)	35 (4)	17 (3)	1 (3)	1 (3)	-1 (3)
C1	22 (4)	32 (4)	20 (4)	3 (3)	2 (3)	0 (3)
C2	26 (4)	33 (4)	22 (4)	0 (3)	4 (3)	-3 (3)
C3	14 (3)	28 (4)	18 (4)	-3 (3)	3 (3)	-3 (3)
C4	20 (4)	29 (4)	14 (3)	0 (3)	-1 (3)	-3 (3)
C5	22 (3)	29 (3)	21 (3)	0 (2)	4 (2)	-2 (2)
C6	22 (3)	28 (3)	21 (3)	1 (2)	1 (2)	-2 (2)
C7	24 (4)	32 (4)	22 (4)	-1 (3)	2 (3)	-6 (3)

C8	19 (3)	25 (3)	17 (3)	-1 (2)	2 (2)	-2 (2)
C9	15 (3)	28 (4)	14 (3)	-2 (3)	1 (3)	-4 (3)
C10	20 (3)	26 (3)	18 (3)	0 (2)	3 (2)	0 (2)
C11	25 (3)	31 (3)	26 (3)	-2 (2)	3 (2)	-2 (2)
C12	35 (4)	38 (4)	33 (4)	1 (3)	4 (3)	-1 (3)
C13	34 (4)	37 (4)	31 (4)	0 (3)	5 (3)	-2 (3)
C14	25 (3)	29 (3)	24 (3)	1 (2)	5 (2)	-1 (2)
C15	23 (3)	27 (3)	21 (3)	0 (2)	3 (2)	-2 (2)
C16	21 (4)	30 (4)	18 (4)	0 (3)	1 (3)	-4 (3)
C17	24 (3)	28 (3)	20 (3)	0 (2)	3 (2)	-2 (2)
C18	25 (3)	30 (3)	23 (3)	0 (2)	3 (2)	-1 (2)
C19	21 (4)	35 (4)	24 (4)	0 (3)	1 (3)	-5 (3)
C20	27 (3)	32 (3)	25 (3)	-1 (2)	4 (2)	-2 (3)
C21	25 (4)	31 (4)	19 (4)	-3 (3)	2 (3)	-5 (3)
C22	16 (3)	30 (4)	14 (3)	-2 (3)	4 (3)	-2 (3)
C23	16 (3)	30 (4)	17 (4)	-1 (3)	1 (3)	-4 (3)
C24	10 (3)	27 (4)	16 (3)	-1 (3)	0 (3)	-4 (3)
C25	20 (4)	34 (4)	15 (4)	1 (3)	1 (3)	-6 (3)
C26	28 (4)	37 (4)	28 (4)	-1 (3)	4 (3)	-5 (3)
C27	19 (4)	30 (4)	17 (4)	-2 (3)	3 (3)	-2 (3)
C28	20 (3)	26 (3)	19 (3)	0 (2)	3 (2)	1 (2)
C29	21 (4)	33 (4)	21 (4)	-2 (3)	6 (3)	-3 (3)
C30	22 (3)	28 (3)	22 (3)	0 (3)	5 (2)	0 (3)
C31	41 (5)	42 (5)	34 (4)	2 (4)	4 (4)	0 (4)
C32	11 (5)	97 (13)	27 (6)	4 (7)	0 (5)	-9 (6)
C33	32 (7)	70 (11)	31 (7)	13 (7)	-9 (6)	-10 (7)
C34	61 (7)	61 (7)	52 (7)	17 (5)	10 (5)	-6 (6)
C35	63 (7)	72 (7)	50 (7)	14 (6)	11 (6)	-6 (6)
C36	44 (8)	72 (11)	22 (6)	12 (6)	7 (6)	-3 (7)
C37	27 (4)	32 (4)	19 (4)	-1 (3)	6 (3)	-4 (3)
C38	38 (4)	42 (5)	32 (4)	-1 (3)	0 (3)	2 (4)
C39	38 (4)	45 (5)	32 (4)	-3 (4)	0 (3)	0 (4)
C40	37 (4)	44 (5)	34 (4)	0 (4)	3 (3)	0 (4)
C41	35 (4)	41 (5)	36 (4)	1 (4)	6 (3)	1 (3)
C42	39 (4)	41 (4)	36 (4)	-2 (3)	2 (3)	-4 (4)
C43	27 (4)	39 (4)	31 (4)	4 (3)	4 (3)	-2 (3)
C44	33 (4)	43 (5)	34 (4)	0 (4)	5 (3)	-2 (4)
C45	29 (7)	90 (13)	35 (8)	-3 (8)	-9 (6)	6 (8)
C46	49 (5)	59 (6)	56 (5)	0 (4)	11 (4)	0 (4)
C47	39 (5)	55 (5)	45 (5)	2 (4)	17 (4)	-2 (4)
C48	33 (7)	77 (12)	31 (7)	-2 (7)	20 (6)	-7 (7)
C49	32 (4)	38 (4)	31 (4)	0 (3)	5 (3)	-4 (3)
C50	63 (8)	78 (8)	44 (7)	-4 (6)	15 (6)	-6 (6)
C51	74 (8)	65 (8)	46 (7)	7 (6)	0 (6)	6 (7)
C52	58 (6)	65 (6)	49 (6)	1 (5)	3 (5)	-10 (5)
C53	21 (4)	32 (4)	21 (4)	-2 (3)	7 (3)	4 (3)
C54	18 (5)	60 (9)	12 (5)	-3 (5)	3 (4)	-7 (5)
C55	34 (4)	44 (5)	31 (4)	4 (3)	6 (3)	-4 (3)
C56	30 (4)	37 (4)	27 (4)	3 (3)	6 (3)	-2 (3)
C57	40 (4)	42 (4)	39 (4)	1 (3)	4 (3)	0 (3)

C58	50 (5)	55 (5)	46 (5)	3 (4)	4 (4)	-6 (4)
C59	45 (5)	48 (5)	36 (5)	3 (4)	7 (4)	-3 (4)
C60	34 (4)	39 (4)	32 (4)	2 (3)	6 (3)	0 (3)
C61	31 (4)	40 (4)	25 (4)	-3 (3)	9 (3)	0 (3)
C62	42 (5)	46 (5)	33 (4)	-3 (4)	4 (4)	-3 (4)
C63	53 (7)	62 (7)	49 (6)	-7 (5)	5 (5)	-1 (5)
C64	58 (6)	53 (6)	47 (6)	-4 (5)	16 (5)	3 (5)
C65	48 (5)	51 (5)	49 (5)	-1 (4)	6 (4)	1 (4)
C66	44 (6)	55 (6)	44 (6)	1 (5)	-2 (5)	0 (5)
C67	30 (4)	37 (4)	30 (4)	-1 (3)	5 (3)	-2 (3)
C68	33 (4)	42 (4)	36 (4)	-2 (3)	3 (3)	0 (3)
C69	50 (5)	59 (6)	54 (5)	-1 (4)	5 (4)	-1 (4)
C70	50 (5)	60 (6)	55 (5)	-2 (4)	10 (4)	-2 (4)
C71	52 (5)	61 (6)	51 (5)	-1 (4)	12 (4)	2 (4)
C72	39 (4)	46 (4)	42 (4)	1 (3)	9 (3)	0 (3)
C73	22 (3)	28 (3)	25 (3)	1 (2)	3 (2)	-3 (2)
C74	27 (5)	45 (5)	12 (4)	2 (4)	-4 (4)	0 (4)
C75	15 (4)	34 (4)	15 (3)	4 (3)	3 (3)	-3 (3)
C76	41 (5)	44 (5)	38 (4)	2 (4)	8 (4)	-2 (4)
C77	36 (6)	59 (7)	51 (6)	4 (5)	7 (5)	4 (5)
C78	50 (5)	56 (5)	51 (5)	7 (4)	7 (4)	-3 (4)
C79	36 (4)	44 (5)	33 (4)	4 (3)	8 (3)	-5 (4)
C80	31 (4)	37 (4)	30 (4)	3 (3)	5 (3)	0 (3)
C81	25.3 (10)	37.0 (11)	19.8 (10)	0.7 (9)	2.1 (8)	-0.4 (9)
C82	25.3 (10)	37.0 (11)	19.8 (10)	0.7 (9)	2.1 (8)	-0.4 (9)
C83	16 (5)	46 (6)	32 (5)	1 (4)	-2 (4)	0 (4)
C84	38 (4)	43 (5)	34 (4)	1 (3)	6 (3)	-1 (4)
C85	41 (5)	46 (5)	32 (4)	-5 (4)	0 (3)	-1 (4)
C86	34 (4)	40 (4)	28 (4)	0 (3)	4 (3)	2 (3)
C87	30 (3)	35 (4)	30 (3)	0 (3)	7 (3)	-1 (3)
C88	30 (5)	44 (5)	12 (4)	4 (4)	0 (4)	1 (4)
C89	27 (5)	53 (6)	44 (6)	-3 (5)	11 (5)	-5 (5)
C90	33 (5)	55 (6)	45 (6)	3 (5)	10 (5)	0 (5)
C91	43 (5)	54 (5)	45 (5)	4 (4)	19 (4)	-1 (4)
C92	25 (7)	79 (12)	36 (8)	24 (8)	4 (6)	-2 (7)
C93	36 (4)	40 (4)	32 (4)	1 (3)	5 (3)	-4 (3)
C94	65 (7)	68 (7)	57 (6)	4 (5)	5 (5)	0 (5)
C95	68 (8)	84 (9)	44 (7)	-7 (6)	23 (6)	-2 (7)
C96	59 (6)	68 (7)	50 (6)	-1 (5)	0 (5)	-10 (5)
C97	19 (5)	44 (6)	25 (5)	3 (4)	-6 (4)	-2 (4)
C98	27 (3)	31 (4)	25 (3)	0 (3)	2 (3)	-1 (3)
C99	21 (4)	34 (4)	19 (4)	4 (3)	-3 (3)	-3 (3)
C100	43 (5)	43 (5)	39 (5)	1 (4)	4 (4)	1 (4)
C101	45 (9)	70 (12)	38 (8)	11 (7)	-11 (7)	0 (8)
C102	43 (6)	53 (6)	42 (6)	13 (5)	2 (5)	-8 (5)
C103	47 (5)	51 (5)	41 (5)	3 (4)	7 (4)	-2 (4)
C104	25 (4)	38 (4)	24 (4)	2 (3)	7 (3)	-3 (3)
C105	28 (5)	51 (6)	24 (5)	0 (4)	5 (4)	-4 (4)
C106	46 (6)	59 (7)	42 (6)	-4 (5)	7 (5)	-1 (5)
C107	53 (6)	60 (6)	54 (6)	-2 (4)	7 (4)	-5 (4)

C108	56 (6)	66 (6)	62 (6)	-2 (4)	11 (4)	-1 (4)
C109	66 (7)	76 (7)	59 (7)	2 (6)	22 (6)	-7 (6)
C110	45 (6)	57 (6)	34 (5)	-2 (5)	3 (5)	-1 (5)
C111	26 (2)	33 (3)	27 (3)	0 (2)	2.4 (19)	-2 (2)
C112	39 (4)	44 (5)	34 (4)	-2 (4)	1 (3)	4 (4)
C113	40 (5)	47 (5)	37 (4)	-6 (4)	3 (4)	-2 (4)
C114	37 (4)	43 (5)	36 (4)	0 (3)	3 (3)	2 (4)
C115	39 (5)	44 (5)	43 (5)	1 (4)	5 (4)	1 (4)
C116	26 (2)	33 (3)	27 (3)	0 (2)	2.4 (19)	-2 (2)
C1D	97 (6)	104 (6)	96 (6)	-4 (4)	19 (4)	5 (4)
C2D	115 (12)	117 (12)	118 (12)	0 (7)	21 (7)	3 (7)
C3D	91 (10)	97 (10)	91 (10)	1 (7)	19 (7)	3 (7)
C4D	69 (8)	78 (8)	74 (8)	-1 (6)	17 (6)	3 (6)
C5D	87 (9)	98 (10)	88 (9)	-3 (7)	20 (7)	8 (7)
C6D	97 (6)	104 (6)	96 (6)	-4 (4)	19 (4)	5 (4)
C7D	97 (6)	104 (6)	96 (6)	-4 (4)	19 (4)	5 (4)
C8D	65 (5)	76 (5)	61 (5)	-7 (4)	7 (4)	4 (4)
C13D	65 (5)	76 (5)	61 (5)	-7 (4)	7 (4)	4 (4)
C12D	86 (9)	88 (9)	87 (9)	1 (6)	16 (6)	11 (6)
C11D	80 (9)	83 (9)	81 (9)	-6 (6)	17 (6)	5 (6)
C10D	78 (9)	91 (9)	81 (9)	-4 (6)	8 (6)	8 (6)
C9D	86 (9)	86 (9)	87 (9)	-9 (6)	14 (6)	1 (6)
C14D	135 (17)	131 (17)	118 (17)	-3 (12)	20 (13)	9 (13)

Table 4 Bond Lengths for a20180181_jmm181.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å	Atom	Atom	Length/Å
Si1	C30	1.835 (12)	C47	C48	1.38 (2)
Si1	C31	1.849 (16)	C49	C50	1.50 (2)
Si1	C37	1.885 (14)	C49	C51	1.54 (2)
Si1	C43	1.858 (14)	C49	C52	1.49 (2)
Si2	C54	1.787 (12)	C53	C54	1.240 (18)
Si2	C55	1.855 (15)	C55	C56	1.41 (2)
Si2	C61	1.892 (14)	C55	C60	1.39 (2)
Si2	C67	1.869 (14)	C56	C57	1.41 (2)
Si3	C74	1.860 (12)	C57	C58	1.35 (2)
Si3	C75	1.860 (12)	C58	C59	1.42 (3)
Si3	C81	1.847 (14)	C59	C60	1.41 (2)
Si3	C87	1.883 (13)	C61	C62	1.41 (2)
Si4	C98	1.861 (13)	C61	C66	1.36 (2)
Si4	C99	1.873 (13)	C62	C63	1.39 (2)
Si4	C105	1.883 (14)	C63	C64	1.44 (3)
Si4	C111	1.848 (14)	C64	C65	1.38 (3)
N1	C2	1.364 (16)	C65	C66	1.44 (2)
N1	C3	1.354 (15)	C67	C68	1.39 (2)
N2	C9	1.338 (15)	C67	C72	1.40 (2)
N2	C10	1.400 (16)	C68	C69	1.35 (3)
N3	C15	1.373 (16)	C69	C70	1.35 (3)
N3	C16	1.344 (17)	C70	C71	1.40 (3)

N4	C22	1.339 (16)	C71	C72	1.34 (2)
N4	C23	1.358 (16)	C73	C74	1.200 (17)
C1	C2	1.449 (17)	C75	C76	1.37 (2)
C1	C26	1.409 (18)	C75	C80	1.433 (17)
C1	C29	1.421 (16)	C76	C77	1.39 (2)
C2	C23	1.397 (16)	C77	C78	1.38 (3)
C3	C4	1.452 (16)	C78	C79	1.42 (3)
C3	C22	1.440 (15)	C79	C80	1.37 (2)
C4	C5	1.358 (16)	C81	C82	1.375 (18)
C4	C27	1.428 (16)	C81	C86	1.418 (19)
C5	C6	1.388 (17)	C82	C83	1.392 (19)
C6	C7	1.423 (17)	C83	C84	1.44 (2)
C6	C49	1.514 (18)	C84	C85	1.35 (2)
C7	C8	1.376 (16)	C85	C86	1.36 (2)
C8	C9	1.476 (16)	C87	C88	1.376 (19)
C8	C27	1.409 (16)	C87	C92	1.36 (2)
C9	C16	1.403 (15)	C88	C89	1.39 (2)
C10	C11	1.436 (17)	C89	C90	1.37 (2)
C10	C15	1.397 (16)	C90	C91	1.38 (2)
C11	C12	1.377 (19)	C91	C92	1.44 (2)
C11	C53	1.442 (17)	C93	C94	1.51 (3)
C12	C13	1.42 (2)	C93	C95	1.56 (2)
C13	C14	1.391 (19)	C93	C96	1.48 (2)
C14	C15	1.411 (17)	C97	C98	1.162 (19)
C14	C73	1.418 (17)	C99	C100	1.43 (2)
C16	C17	1.446 (17)	C99	C104	1.400 (18)
C17	C18	1.374 (17)	C100	C101	1.37 (2)
C17	C28	1.432 (16)	C101	C102	1.42 (3)
C18	C19	1.415 (18)	C102	C103	1.35 (3)
C19	C20	1.403 (18)	C103	C104	1.39 (2)
C19	C93	1.518 (18)	C105	C106	1.43 (2)
C20	C21	1.390 (17)	C105	C110	1.31 (2)
C21	C22	1.475 (17)	C106	C107	1.38 (3)
C21	C28	1.420 (16)	C107	C108	1.37 (3)
C23	C24	1.436 (15)	C108	C109	1.39 (3)
C24	C25	1.407 (16)	C109	C110	1.48 (3)
C24	C97	1.443 (16)	C111	C112	1.35 (2)
C25	C26	1.359 (18)	C111	C116	1.378 (19)
C27	C28	1.418 (13)	C112	C113	1.47 (2)
C29	C30	1.208 (17)	C113	C114	1.36 (2)
C31	C32	1.41 (2)	C114	C115	1.37 (2)
C31	C36	1.42 (2)	C115	C116	1.37 (2)
C32	C33	1.43 (2)	C1D	C2D	1.3900
C33	C34	1.36 (3)	C1D	C6D	1.3900
C34	C35	1.33 (3)	C1D	C7D	1.51 (3)
C35	C36	1.40 (3)	C2D	C3D	1.3900
C37	C38	1.382 (19)	C3D	C4D	1.3900
C37	C42	1.43 (2)	C4D	C5D	1.3900
C38	C39	1.40 (2)	C5D	C6D	1.3900
C39	C40	1.38 (2)	C8D	C13D	1.3900

C40	C41	1.39 (2)	C8D	C9D	1.3900
C41	C42	1.38 (2)	C8D	C14D	1.48 (4)
C43	C44	1.43 (2)	C13D	C12D	1.3900
C43	C48	1.429 (19)	C12D	C11D	1.3900
C44	C45	1.36 (2)	C11D	C10D	1.3900
C45	C46	1.39 (3)	C10D	C9D	1.3900
C46	C47	1.41 (3)			

Table 5 Bond Angles for a20180181_jmm181.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C30	Si1	C31	112.7 (6)	C44	C43	Si1	120.2 (11)
C30	Si1	C37	107.7 (6)	C44	C43	C48	116.5 (13)
C30	Si1	C43	108.3 (6)	C48	C43	Si1	123.0 (11)
C31	Si1	C37	107.9 (6)	C45	C44	C43	120.7 (14)
C31	Si1	C43	107.5 (7)	C44	C45	C46	121.0 (16)
C43	Si1	C37	112.9 (6)	C45	C46	C47	121.2 (17)
C54	Si2	C55	110.6 (7)	C48	C47	C46	117.2 (15)
C54	Si2	C61	110.8 (7)	C47	C48	C43	123.1 (16)
C54	Si2	C67	108.0 (6)	C6	C49	C51	110.3 (13)
C55	Si2	C61	107.9 (7)	C50	C49	C6	109.7 (12)
C55	Si2	C67	107.4 (7)	C50	C49	C51	103.9 (15)
C67	Si2	C61	112.1 (6)	C52	C49	C6	114.3 (13)
C74	Si3	C87	107.6 (6)	C52	C49	C50	107.8 (15)
C75	Si3	C74	111.4 (6)	C52	C49	C51	110.2 (15)
C75	Si3	C87	108.9 (6)	C54	C53	C11	172.5 (14)
C81	Si3	C74	106.7 (6)	C53	C54	Si2	175.0 (11)
C81	Si3	C75	109.4 (6)	C56	C55	Si2	119.6 (11)
C81	Si3	C87	112.7 (6)	C60	C55	Si2	122.9 (12)
C98	Si4	C99	111.1 (6)	C60	C55	C56	117.4 (13)
C98	Si4	C105	106.8 (6)	C57	C56	C55	121.2 (13)
C99	Si4	C105	107.5 (6)	C58	C57	C56	120.0 (16)
C111	Si4	C98	110.8 (6)	C57	C58	C59	121.1 (17)
C111	Si4	C99	107.0 (6)	C60	C59	C58	118.0 (16)
C111	Si4	C105	113.7 (6)	C55	C60	C59	122.1 (15)
C3	N1	C2	115.3 (10)	C62	C61	Si2	118.0 (11)
C9	N2	C10	113.5 (10)	C66	C61	Si2	120.9 (11)
C16	N3	C15	118.6 (11)	C66	C61	C62	121.0 (14)
C22	N4	C23	118.4 (10)	C63	C62	C61	122.2 (15)
C26	C1	C2	117.5 (11)	C62	C63	C64	116.4 (16)
C26	C1	C29	121.2 (12)	C65	C64	C63	121.6 (17)
C29	C1	C2	121.2 (11)	C64	C65	C66	120.0 (16)
N1	C2	C1	115.3 (11)	C61	C66	C65	118.7 (15)
N1	C2	C23	124.5 (11)	C68	C67	Si2	122.4 (11)
C23	C2	C1	120.1 (11)	C72	C67	Si2	122.9 (11)
N1	C3	C4	117.5 (10)	C72	C67	C68	114.5 (13)
N1	C3	C22	121.0 (10)	C69	C68	C67	123.8 (16)
C22	C3	C4	121.5 (10)	C70	C69	C68	120.2 (18)
C5	C4	C3	120.8 (11)	C69	C70	C71	118.2 (18)

C5	C4	C27	120.4 (11)	C72	C71	C70	120.9 (18)
C27	C4	C3	118.8 (10)	C71	C72	C67	122.1 (16)
C4	C5	C6	122.9 (11)	C74	C73	C14	176.0 (14)
C5	C6	C7	116.8 (11)	C73	C74	Si3	169.9 (13)
C5	C6	C49	120.7 (11)	C76	C75	Si3	125.9 (10)
C7	C6	C49	122.5 (11)	C76	C75	C80	112.3 (12)
C8	C7	C6	121.7 (11)	C80	C75	Si3	121.8 (10)
C7	C8	C9	121.9 (10)	C75	C76	C77	127.8 (15)
C7	C8	C27	120.2 (11)	C78	C77	C76	116.9 (17)
C27	C8	C9	117.9 (10)	C77	C78	C79	120.2 (17)
N2	C9	C8	115.6 (10)	C80	C79	C78	118.8 (15)
N2	C9	C16	125.4 (11)	C79	C80	C75	123.9 (14)
C16	C9	C8	118.9 (10)	C82	C81	Si3	123.3 (10)
N2	C10	C11	117.7 (10)	C82	C81	C86	116.0 (13)
N2	C10	C15	122.9 (11)	C86	C81	Si3	120.1 (10)
C15	C10	C11	119.3 (11)	C83	C82	C81	123.4 (12)
C10	C11	C53	125.8 (12)	C82	C83	C84	117.9 (12)
C12	C11	C10	118.3 (12)	C85	C84	C83	118.5 (14)
C12	C11	C53	115.7 (12)	C84	C85	C86	122.8 (14)
C11	C12	C13	121.7 (13)	C85	C86	C81	121.3 (13)
C14	C13	C12	120.5 (13)	C88	C87	Si3	119.9 (10)
C13	C14	C15	117.9 (12)	C92	C87	Si3	119.9 (11)
C13	C14	C73	120.7 (12)	C92	C87	C88	120.2 (13)
C15	C14	C73	121.4 (11)	C87	C88	C89	122.7 (13)
N3	C15	C10	119.9 (11)	C90	C89	C88	118.2 (15)
N3	C15	C14	118.1 (11)	C89	C90	C91	120.5 (15)
C10	C15	C14	121.8 (11)	C90	C91	C92	120.7 (14)
N3	C16	C9	119.5 (11)	C87	C92	C91	117.7 (14)
N3	C16	C17	117.9 (10)	C19	C93	C95	106.4 (13)
C9	C16	C17	122.6 (11)	C94	C93	C19	110.0 (14)
C18	C17	C16	121.3 (11)	C94	C93	C95	107.0 (16)
C18	C17	C28	121.1 (11)	C96	C93	C19	112.4 (13)
C28	C17	C16	117.6 (10)	C96	C93	C94	108.1 (15)
C17	C18	C19	122.9 (12)	C96	C93	C95	112.9 (15)
C18	C19	C93	120.3 (12)	C98	C97	C24	170.6 (15)
C20	C19	C18	116.3 (11)	C97	C98	Si4	175.3 (12)
C20	C19	C93	123.4 (12)	C100	C99	Si4	119.3 (10)
C21	C20	C19	121.8 (12)	C104	C99	Si4	123.3 (10)
C20	C21	C22	120.6 (11)	C104	C99	C100	116.9 (12)
C20	C21	C28	122.1 (11)	C101	C100	C99	121.5 (16)
C28	C21	C22	117.3 (10)	C100	C101	C102	118.1 (18)
N4	C22	C3	121.3 (10)	C103	C102	C101	121.2 (16)
N4	C22	C21	119.6 (10)	C102	C103	C104	120.3 (16)
C3	C22	C21	118.8 (10)	C103	C104	C99	121.1 (14)
N4	C23	C2	119.1 (10)	C106	C105	Si4	116.9 (11)
N4	C23	C24	120.8 (10)	C110	C105	Si4	123.6 (11)
C2	C23	C24	120.0 (11)	C110	C105	C106	119.5 (14)
C23	C24	C97	123.0 (11)	C107	C106	C105	119.7 (17)
C25	C24	C23	118.6 (10)	C108	C107	C106	121.0 (19)
C25	C24	C97	118.4 (10)	C107	C108	C109	121 (2)

C26	C25	C24	121.4 (11)	C108	C109	C110	116.0 (18)
C25	C26	C1	122.2 (12)	C105	C110	C109	122.1 (16)
C8	C27	C4	117.9 (10)	C112	C111	Si4	119.5 (11)
C8	C27	C28	122.8 (10)	C112	C111	C116	118.0 (13)
C28	C27	C4	119.3 (9)	C116	C111	Si4	122.3 (10)
C21	C28	C17	115.9 (10)	C111	C112	C113	120.3 (13)
C21	C28	C27	124.1 (10)	C114	C113	C112	119.3 (14)
C27	C28	C17	120.0 (10)	C113	C114	C115	119.3 (15)
C30	C29	C1	178.9 (13)	C116	C115	C114	120.6 (14)
C29	C30	Si1	172.3 (11)	C115	C116	C111	122.5 (13)
C32	C31	Si1	119.6 (12)	C2D	C1D	C6D	120.0
C32	C31	C36	119.9 (15)	C2D	C1D	C7D	116.0 (18)
C36	C31	Si1	120.4 (13)	C6D	C1D	C7D	123.8 (19)
C31	C32	C33	116.3 (14)	C1D	C2D	C3D	120.0
C34	C33	C32	122.4 (18)	C2D	C3D	C4D	120.0
C35	C34	C33	120.8 (18)	C5D	C4D	C3D	120.0
C34	C35	C36	121 (2)	C4D	C5D	C6D	120.0
C35	C36	C31	119.2 (18)	C5D	C6D	C1D	120.0
C38	C37	Si1	120.6 (11)	C13DC8D	C9D		120.0
C38	C37	C42	120.4 (13)	C13DC8D	C14D		114.7 (18)
C42	C37	Si1	119.0 (10)	C9D	C8D	C14D	125.3 (19)
C37	C38	C39	119.2 (13)	C8D	C13DC12D		120.0
C40	C39	C38	120.7 (14)	C11DC12DC13D			120.0
C41	C40	C39	120.1 (15)	C12DC11DC10D			120.0
C40	C41	C42	121.1 (14)	C9D	C10DC11D		120.0
C41	C42	C37	118.3 (13)	C10DC9D	C8D		120.0

Table 6 Torsion Angles for a20180181_jmm181.

A	B	C	D	Angle/°	A	B	C	D	Angle/°
Si1	C31	C32	C33	-179.2 (10)	C36	C31	C32	C33	-4 (2)
Si1	C31	C36	C35	-179.1 (13)	C37	Si1	C31	C32	170.2 (11)
Si1	C37	C38	C39	176.3 (11)	C37	Si1	C31	C36	-5.0 (14)
Si1	C37	C42	C41	-176.2 (11)	C37	Si1	C43	C44	-86.5 (13)
Si1	C43	C44	C45	-178.9 (14)	C37	Si1	C43	C48	100.0 (15)
Si1	C43	C48	C47	176.5 (15)	C37	C38	C39	C40	-1 (2)
Si2	C55	C56	C57	-174.0 (11)	C38	C37	C42	C41	3 (2)
Si2	C55	C60	C59	178.3 (11)	C38	C39	C40	C41	4 (2)
Si2	C61	C62	C63	176.2 (13)	C39	C40	C41	C42	-3 (2)
Si2	C61	C66	C65	-176.6 (12)	C40	C41	C42	C37	0 (2)
Si2	C67	C68	C69	-173.7 (14)	C42	C37	C38	C39	-3 (2)
Si2	C67	C72	C71	173.6 (14)	C43	Si1	C31	C32	48.2 (13)
Si3	C75	C76	C77	-179.4 (13)	C43	Si1	C31	C36	-127.1 (13)
Si3	C75	C80	C79	-178.4 (11)	C43	Si1	C37	C38	40.2 (13)
Si3	C81	C82	C83	169.8 (11)	C43	Si1	C37	C42	-140.9 (11)
Si3	C81	C86	C85	-171.5 (12)	C43	C44	C45	C46	6 (3)
Si3	C87	C88	C89	-179.5 (12)	C44	C43	C48	C47	3 (3)
Si3	C87	C92	C91	178.8 (13)	C44	C45	C46	C47	-4 (3)
Si4	C99	C100	C101	-177.1 (12)	C45	C46	C47	C48	2 (3)

Si4	C99	C104	C103	-179.3(11)	C46	C47	C48	C43	-1(3)
Si4	C105	C106	C107	-179.8(15)	C48	C43	C44	C45	-5(2)
Si4	C105	C110	C109	178.0(15)	C49	C6	C7	C8	176.5(12)
Si4	C111	C112	C113	-174.0(11)	C53	C11	C12	C13	-179.5(13)
Si4	C111	C116	C115	172.2(11)	C54	Si2	C55	C56	-68.0(13)
N1	C2	C23	N4	-4.0(19)	C54	Si2	C55	C60	115.4(13)
N1	C2	C23	C24	178.3(11)	C54	Si2	C61	C62	168.2(11)
N1	C3	C4	C5	1.1(17)	C54	Si2	C61	C66	-13.3(14)
N1	C3	C4	C27	-175.8(10)	C54	Si2	C67	C68	158.9(12)
N1	C3	C22	N4	1.4(17)	C54	Si2	C67	C72	-17.6(15)
N1	C3	C22	C21	176.0(10)	C55	Si2	C61	C62	-70.6(12)
N2	C9	C16	N3	5.2(19)	C55	Si2	C61	C66	107.9(13)
N2	C9	C16	C17	-175.6(12)	C55	Si2	C67	C68	39.6(14)
N2	C10	C11	C12	-176.5(12)	C55	Si2	C67	C72	-136.9(13)
N2	C10	C11	C53	-1.3(18)	C55	C56	C57	C58	-5(2)
N2	C10	C15	N3	-2.7(18)	C56	C55	C60	C59	2(2)
N2	C10	C15	C14	-178.1(11)	C56	C57	C58	C59	3(2)
N3	C16	C17	C18	-3.0(18)	C57	C58	C59	C60	1(2)
N3	C16	C17	C28	176.5(11)	C58	C59	C60	C55	-4(2)
N4	C23	C24	C25	-178.2(11)	C60	C55	C56	C57	3(2)
N4	C23	C24	C97	-1.4(18)	C61	Si2	C55	C56	170.6(11)
C1	C2	C23	N4	176.3(11)	C61	Si2	C55	C60	-5.9(14)
C1	C2	C23	C24	-1.4(18)	C61	Si2	C67	C68	-78.7(14)
C2	N1	C3	C4	-177.1(10)	C61	Si2	C67	C72	104.7(13)
C2	N1	C3	C22	1.3(16)	C61	C62	C63	C64	0(3)
C2	C1	C26	C25	-3(2)	C62	C61	C66	C65	2(2)
C2	C23	C24	C25	-0.4(17)	C62	C63	C64	C65	2(3)
C2	C23	C24	C97	176.3(12)	C63	C64	C65	C66	-2(3)
C3	N1	C2	C1	179.8(10)	C64	C65	C66	C61	0(3)
C3	N1	C2	C23	0.0(18)	C66	C61	C62	C63	-2(2)
C3	C4	C5	C6	-177.6(11)	C67	Si2	C55	C56	49.6(13)
C3	C4	C27	C8	177.6(11)	C67	Si2	C55	C60	-127.0(12)
C3	C4	C27	C28	-2.7(15)	C67	Si2	C61	C62	47.5(13)
C4	C3	C22	N4	179.6(11)	C67	Si2	C61	C66	-134.1(13)
C4	C3	C22	C21	-5.7(16)	C67	C68	C69	C70	-4(3)
C4	C5	C6	C7	2.5(18)	C68	C67	C72	C71	-3(2)
C4	C5	C6	C49	-178.4(12)	C68	C69	C70	C71	4(3)
C4	C27	C28	C17	-179.3(12)	C69	C70	C71	C72	-4(3)
C4	C27	C28	C21	-0.4(16)	C70	C71	C72	C67	4(3)
C5	C4	C27	C8	0.7(17)	C72	C67	C68	C69	3(2)
C5	C4	C27	C28	-179.6(11)	C73	C14	C15	N3	-0.3(18)
C5	C6	C7	C8	-4.4(18)	C73	C14	C15	C10	175.2(12)
C5	C6	C49	C50	64.6(18)	C74	Si3	C75	C76	60.6(13)
C5	C6	C49	C51	-49.3(18)	C74	Si3	C75	C80	-118.1(10)
C5	C6	C49	C52	-174.1(14)	C74	Si3	C81	C82	25.3(13)
C6	C7	C8	C9	-176.5(11)	C74	Si3	C81	C86	-162.8(11)
C6	C7	C8	C27	4.5(19)	C74	Si3	C87	C88	-156.4(12)
C7	C6	C49	C50	-116.3(15)	C74	Si3	C87	C92	22.5(16)
C7	C6	C49	C51	129.8(15)	C75	Si3	C74	C73	-179(100)
C7	C6	C49	C52	5(2)	C75	Si3	C81	C82	-95.4(12)

C7 C8 C9 N2	-1.1 (17)	C75 Si3 C81 C86	76.5 (12)
C7 C8 C9 C16	-178.8 (12)	C75 Si3 C87 C88	-35.4 (13)
C7 C8 C27 C4	-2.6 (17)	C75 Si3 C87 C92	143.4 (14)
C7 C8 C27 C28	177.8 (11)	C75 C76 C77 C78	-3 (2)
C8 C9 C16 N3	-177.4 (11)	C76 C75 C80 C79	2.7 (19)
C8 C9 C16 C17	1.8 (18)	C76 C77 C78 C79	4 (2)
C8 C27 C28 C17	0.3 (16)	C77 C78 C79 C80	-2 (2)
C8 C27 C28 C21	179.2 (13)	C78 C79 C80 C75	-2 (2)
C9 N2 C10 C11	179.5 (11)	C80 C75 C76 C77	-1 (2)
C9 N2 C10 C15	3.0 (16)	C81 Si3 C74 C73	61 (7)
C9 C8 C27 C4	178.4 (10)	C81 Si3 C75 C76	178.4 (11)
C9 C8 C27 C28	-1.2 (16)	C81 Si3 C75 C80	-0.3 (11)
C9 C16 C17 C18	177.8 (12)	C81 Si3 C87 C88	86.2 (13)
C9 C16 C17 C28	-2.7 (18)	C81 Si3 C87 C92	-95.0 (15)
C10N2 C9 C8	178.3 (10)	C81 C82 C83 C84	3 (2)
C10N2 C9 C16	-4.2 (17)	C82 C81 C86 C85	1 (2)
C10C11 C12 C13	-4 (2)	C82 C83 C84 C85	-1 (2)
C11C10 C15 N3	-179.2 (11)	C83 C84 C85 C86	0 (2)
C11C10 C15 C14	5.4 (18)	C84 C85 C86 C81	0 (3)
C11C12 C13 C14	2 (2)	C86 C81 C82 C83	-2 (2)
C12C13 C14 C15	3 (2)	C87 Si3 C74 C73	-60 (7)
C12C13 C14 C73	-178.9 (13)	C87 Si3 C75 C76	-58.0 (13)
C13C14 C15 N3	177.3 (12)	C87 Si3 C75 C80	123.3 (10)
C13C14 C15 C10	-7.2 (19)	C87 Si3 C81 C82	143.3 (11)
C15N3 C16 C9	-4.4 (17)	C87 Si3 C81 C86	-44.8 (13)
C15N3 C16 C17	176.4 (11)	C87 C88 C89 C90	-1 (2)
C15C10 C11 C12	0.2 (18)	C88 C87 C92 C91	-2 (3)
C15C10 C11 C53	175.4 (12)	C88 C89 C90 C91	2 (3)
C16N3 C15 C10	3.3 (17)	C89 C90 C91 C92	-2 (3)
C16N3 C15 C14	178.9 (11)	C90 C91 C92 C87	3 (3)
C16C17 C18 C19	177.2 (12)	C92 C87 C88 C89	2 (2)
C16C17 C28 C21	-177.4 (11)	C93 C19 C20 C21	179.6 (13)
C16C17 C28 C27	1.6 (16)	C97 C24 C25 C26	-176.5 (12)
C17C18 C19 C20	2.8 (19)	C98 Si4 C99 C100	71.2 (12)
C17C18 C19 C93	-180.0 (12)	C98 Si4 C99 C104	-116.5 (11)
C18C17 C28 C21	2.1 (17)	C98 Si4 C105 C106	-154.6 (12)
C18C17 C28 C27	-178.9 (11)	C98 Si4 C105 C110	25.7 (17)
C18C19 C20 C21	-3.2 (19)	C98 Si4 C111 C112	-166.5 (12)
C18C19 C93 C94	52.3 (18)	C98 Si4 C111 C116	19.8 (13)
C18C19 C93 C95	-63.3 (18)	C99 Si4 C105 C106	-35.3 (14)
C18C19 C93 C96	172.8 (14)	C99 Si4 C105 C110	145.0 (15)
C19C20 C21 C22	-178.8 (11)	C99 Si4 C111 C112	72.3 (13)
C19C20 C21 C28	3 (2)	C99 Si4 C111 C116	-101.4 (12)
C20C19 C93 C94	-130.6 (15)	C99 C100 C101 C102	-10 (2)
C20C19 C93 C95	113.8 (16)	C100 C99 C104 C103	-6.8 (19)
C20C19 C93 C96	-10 (2)	C100 C101 C102 C103	7 (2)
C20C21 C22 N4	-0.7 (18)	C101 C102 C103 C104	-4 (3)
C20C21 C22 C3	-175.5 (11)	C102 C103 C104 C99	4 (2)
C20C21 C28 C17	-2.6 (18)	C104 C99 C100 C101	10 (2)
C20C21 C28 C27	178.4 (11)	C105 Si4 C99 C100	-45.3 (12)

C22N4	C23	C2	6.4 (17)	C105 Si4	C99	C104	127.0 (11)
C22N4	C23	C24	-175.9 (11)	C105 Si4	C111	C112	-46.2 (14)
C22C3	C4	C5	-177.3 (11)	C105 Si4	C111	C116	140.1 (11)
C22C3	C4	C27	5.8 (16)	C105	C106	C107 C108	-2 (3)
C22C21	C28	C17	179.5 (10)	C106	C105	C110 C109	-2 (3)
C22C21	C28	C27	0.5 (17)	C106	C107	C108 C109	6 (3)
C23N4	C22	C3	-5.2 (16)	C107	C108	C109 C110	-8 (3)
C23N4	C22	C21	-179.8 (10)	C108	C109	C110 C105	5 (3)
C23C24	C25	C26	0.4 (18)	C110	C105	C106 C107	0 (3)
C24C25	C26	C1	2 (2)	C111 Si4	C99	C100	-167.8 (10)
C26C1	C2	N1	-176.5 (11)	C111 Si4	C99	C104	4.5 (12)
C26C1	C2	C23	3.3 (18)	C111 Si4	C105	C106	82.9 (14)
C27C4	C5	C6	-0.8 (19)	C111 Si4	C105	C110	-96.8 (16)
C27C8	C9	N2	177.8 (10)	C111	C112	C113 C114	2 (2)
C27C8	C9	C16	0.2 (16)	C112	C111	C116 C115	-2 (2)
C28C17	C18	C19	-2.4 (19)	C112	C113	C114 C115	-3 (2)
C28C21	C22	N4	177.3 (11)	C113	C114	C115 C116	2 (2)
C28C21	C22	C3	2.5 (16)	C114	C115	C116 C111	1 (2)
C29C1	C2	N1	5.9 (17)	C116	C111	C112 C113	0 (2)
C29C1	C2	C23	-174.4 (12)	C1D	C2D	C3D C4D	0.0
C29C1	C26	C25	174.3 (13)	C2D	C1D	C6D C5D	0.0
C30Si1	C31	C32	-71.1 (13)	C2D	C3D	C4D C5D	0.0
C30Si1	C31	C36	113.7 (13)	C3D	C4D	C5D C6D	0.0
C30Si1	C37	C38	159.7 (11)	C4D	C5D	C6D C1D	0.0
C30Si1	C37	C42	-21.4 (12)	C6D	C1D	C2D C3D	0.0
C30Si1	C43	C44	154.3 (12)	C7D	C1D	C2D C3D	175 (2)
C30Si1	C43	C48	-19.1 (16)	C7D	C1D	C6D C5D	-175 (2)
C31Si1	C37	C38	-78.4 (13)	C8D	C13D	C12D C11D	0.0
C31Si1	C37	C42	100.5 (12)	C13D	C8D	C9D C10D	0.0
C31Si1	C43	C44	32.3 (14)	C13D	C12D	C11D C10D	0.0
C31Si1	C43	C48	-141.2 (14)	C12D	C11D	C10D C9D	0.0
C31C32	C33	C34	1 (2)	C11D	C10D	C9D C8D	0.0
C32C31	C36	C35	6 (2)	C9D	C8D	C13D C12D	0.0
C32C33	C34	C35	1 (3)	C14D	C8D	C13D C12D	-179 (2)
C33C34	C35	C36	0 (3)	C14D	C8D	C9D C10D	178 (2)
C34C35	C36	C31	-4 (3)				

Table 7 Hydrogen Atom Coordinates ($\text{\AA}\times 10^4$) and Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2\times 10^3$) for a20180181_jmm181.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
H5	5804.73	5747.45	4522.15	29
H7	3159.98	4851.02	4638.56	32
H12	185.7	3473.69	6078.52	43
H13	1251.12	3422.58	7379.49	41
H18	5570.13	4780.18	8351.84	32
H20	8116.19	5694.98	8246.74	34
H25	11170.11	7072.58	6747.16	28
H26	10191.83	7093.44	5473.59	37

H32	5750.86	7513.9	3039.47	54
H33	6404.64	7999.34	2251.02	55
H34	7718.04	7895.53	1253.19	69
H35	8396.91	7325.12	958.25	74
H36	7718.47	6819.9	1647.84	55
H38	4793.09	6284.12	1734.77	45
H39	5499.42	5766.14	1093.37	47
H40	7886.57	5487.23	1482.33	47
H41	9489.45	5680.25	2589.23	45
H42	8846.15	6191.87	3252.46	47
H44	3464.47	6995.99	2053.06	44
H45	867	7032.06	2137.03	63
H46	-3.66	6907.96	3277.94	65
H47	1698.81	6656.17	4328.58	54
H48	4303.28	6583.22	4218.16	54
H50A	6174.26	5435.99	3386.1	92
H50B	5061.78	5301.91	2629.23	92
H50C	5749.78	5013.78	3272.72	92
H51A	2432.27	5753.64	3512.46	95
H51B	3240.02	5722.05	2767.25	95
H51C	4198.65	5880.4	3544.21	95
H52A	3143.44	4799.86	3399.57	87
H52B	2577.04	5062.37	2688.97	87
H52C	1803.16	5092.9	3444.8	87
H56	-1511.85	4594.74	3369.45	38
H57	-1248.98	5044.41	2455.37	49
H58	-34.33	4908.91	1434.26	61
H59	761.22	4305.06	1225.77	52
H60	194.98	3842.79	2061.62	42
H62	-2704.58	3380.59	2211.58	49
H63	-2291.33	2834	1586.87	66
H64	-39.03	2480.95	2098.67	62
H65	1571.38	2658	3208.42	60
H66	1105.45	3222.85	3814.49	59
H68	-4135.2	3965.46	2471.44	45
H69	-6609.1	4108.93	2601.35	65
H70	-7416.98	4049.66	3774.53	66
H71	-5539.09	3924.24	4854.35	65
H72	-3065.3	3777.94	4722.74	51
H76	5070.21	2996.27	9821.5	49
H77	4350.38	2513.72	10513.61	58
H78	3470.91	2637.53	11671.25	63
H79	3062.04	3249.73	12018.25	45
H80	3674.06	3714.77	11251.06	39
H82	2569.97	4346.31	9614.46	33
H83	1811.1	4834.28	10309.82	38
H84	3575.94	5043.27	11415.07	46
H85	5864.67	4738.15	11775.59	49
H86	6544.18	4247.35	11117.15	41
H88	7844.51	3553.94	10815.21	35

H89	10492.32	3501.22	10764.85	49
H90	11384.86	3659.7	9639.36	53
H91	9683.11	3897.63	8618.17	55
H92	6948.98	3936.63	8668.52	56
H94A	7258.85	4647.66	9370.93	96
H94B	8378.94	4814.2	10093.12	96
H94C	8981.82	4774.9	9292.01	96
H95A	5520.48	5499.31	9519.92	96
H95B	6214.24	5242.92	10222.4	96
H95C	5207.31	5070.23	9472.73	96
H96A	9555.55	5450.14	9305.62	90
H96B	9103.56	5418.23	10141.84	90
H96C	8275.88	5716.69	9555.45	90
H100	13224.95	5943.54	9547.94	50
H101	12521.44	5462.5	10271.63	63
H102	11539.69	5602.07	11414.59	56
H103	10739.23	6179.64	11635.88	55
H104	11229.02	6658.23	10844.72	35
H106	15353.69	6506.92	10370.67	59
H107	17975.69	6450.92	10273.42	67
H108	18808.37	6531.09	9118.14	73
H109	17126.14	6788.15	8072.64	79
H110	14359.16	6816.37	8174.93	55
H112	13989.66	7160.72	10617.03	47
H113	13331.81	7706.13	11260.61	50
H114	10948.94	7983.22	10863.34	46
H115	9336.89	7765.89	9783.1	50
H116	10034.37	7262.95	9143.81	35
H2D	7385.71	4502.1	5138.33	140
H3D	6695.9	4138.32	6112.46	111
H4D	8013.36	4200.77	7364.82	88
H5D	10020.65	4627.01	7643.07	108
H6D	10710.47	4990.8	6668.96	118
H7DA	9519.48	5243.92	5226.8	148
H7DB	8825.32	4918.49	4675.22	148
H7DC	10611.74	4911.39	5071.55	148
H13D	4234.66	6059.64	7747.41	81
H12D	5008.19	6413.07	6778.48	104
H11D	3674.52	6367.34	5525.84	97
H10D	1567.38	5968.17	5242.08	100
H9D	793.86	5614.72	6210.98	103
H14A	2914.3	5619.24	8162.36	192
H14B	1851.74	5346.57	7598.2	192
H14C	1111.97	5708.62	7889	192

Table 8 Solvent masks information for a20180181_jmm181.

Number	X	Y	Z	Volume	Electron count	Content
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1	-0.207	-0.007	0.128	26.1	4.7?
2	0.055	0.066	0.581	25.2	5.2?
3	-0.353	0.280	0.528	396.8	110.2?
4	0.207	0.493	0.872	26.1	4.7?
5	-0.055	0.566	0.419	25.2	5.2?
6	-0.211	0.780	0.472	396.8	110.2?

Experimental

Single crystals of $C_{130}H_{102}N_4Si_4$ [**a20180181_jmm181**]. A suitable crystal was selected and **mounted** on a **SuperNova, Single source at offset/far, Atlas** diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 149.99(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the ShelXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the ShelXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

1. Dolomanov, O.V., Bourhis, L.J., Gildea, R.J., Howard, J.A.K. & Puschmann, H. (2009), *J. Appl. Cryst.* 42, 339-341.
2. Sheldrick, G.M. (2015). *Acta Cryst.* A71, 3-8.
3. Sheldrick, G.M. (2015). *Acta Cryst.* C71, 3-8.

Crystal structure determination of [**a20180181_jmm181**]

Crystal Data for $C_{130}H_{102}N_4Si_4$ ($M=1832.51$ g/mol): monoclinic, space group $P2_1$ (no. 4), $a = 8.7139(4)$ Å, $b = 36.754(2)$ Å, $c = 17.7432(6)$ Å, $\beta = 99.394(4)^\circ$, $V = 5606.5(5)$ Å³, $Z = 2$, $T = 149.99(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 0.868$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.086$ g/cm³, 43779 reflections measured ($6.974^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 136^\circ$), 19917 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.1275$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.1535$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.1375 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.3943 (all data).

Refinement model description

Number of restraints - 781, number of constraints - unknown.

Details:

1. Twinned data refinement

Scales: 0.61(9)
0.39(9)

2. Fixed Uiso

At 1.2 times of:

All C(H) groups

At 1.5 times of:

All C(H,H,H) groups

3. Uiso/Uanis restraints and constraints

Uanis(C62) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C61) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C55) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C59) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C39) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C37) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C100) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C91) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C19) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C21) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C27) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C4) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C3) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C22) ~ Ueq, Uanis(N4) ~ Ueq, Uanis(N1) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C23) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C2) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C25) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C26) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C53) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C16) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C9) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C51) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C24) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C31) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C47) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C46) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C70) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C69) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C71) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C95) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C85) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C86) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C7) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C50) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C99) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C108) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C35) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
Uanis(C109) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C90) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C88) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
Uanis(C116) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C115) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C44) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C56) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C75) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C43) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C38) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C1) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C112) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C113) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C114) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C76) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C78) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C103) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C104) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C79) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C58) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C65) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C84) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C41) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C107) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C40) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C42) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C29) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006
Uanis(C66) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C64) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C63) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
Uanis(C34) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C105) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C110) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C106)

~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
 Uanis(C102) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
 Uanis(C74) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
 Uanis(C13D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C8D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C9D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C14D)
 ~ Ueq, Uanis(C10D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C12D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C11D) ~ Ueq,
 Uanis(C7D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C3D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C4D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C2D)
 ~ Ueq, Uanis(C5D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C1D) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C6D) ~ Ueq, :
 with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
 Uanis(Si4) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.002 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.004
 Uanis(C98) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C87) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.002 and sigma for
 terminal atoms of 0.004
 Uanis(C72) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C68) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C67) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C80)
 ~ Ueq, Uanis(C82) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C20) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C111) ~ Ueq,
 Uanis(C57) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C60) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C52) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C49)
 ~ Ueq, Uanis(C8) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C5) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C6) ~ Ueq,
 Uanis(C11) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C12) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C13) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C14)
 ~ Ueq, Uanis(C73) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C15) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C10) ~ Ueq,
 Uanis(N2) ~ Ueq, Uanis(N3) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C18) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C17)
 ~ Ueq, Uanis(C28) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C93) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C94) ~ Ueq,
 Uanis(C96) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.002 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.004
 Uanis(C81) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002
 Uanis(Si1) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002
 Uanis(Si3) ~ Ueq, Uanis(C75) ~ Ueq, Uanis(Si2) ~ Ueq: with sigma of
 0.01 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.02
 Uanis(C30) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.002 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.004
 Uanis(C97) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
 Uanis(C77) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
 Uanis(C83) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
 Uanis(C89) ~ Ueq: with sigma of 0.005 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.01
 Uanis(C111) = Uanis(C116)
 Uanis(C8D) = Uanis(C13D)
 Uanis(C1D) = Uanis(C7D) = Uanis(C6D)
 Uanis(C82) = Uanis(C81)
 Uanis(C81) = Uanis(Si3)
 4.a Aromatic/amide H refined with riding coordinates:
 C5 (H5), C7 (H7), C12 (H12), C13 (H13), C18 (H18), C20 (H20), C25 (H25), C26 (H26),
 C32 (H32), C33 (H33), C34 (H34), C35 (H35), C36 (H36), C38 (H38), C39 (H39), C40 (H40),
 C41 (H41), C42 (H42), C44 (H44), C45 (H45), C46 (H46), C47 (H47), C48 (H48),
 C56 (H56), C57 (H57), C58 (H58), C59 (H59), C60 (H60), C62 (H62), C63 (H63), C64 (H64),
 C65 (H65), C66 (H66), C68 (H68), C69 (H69), C70 (H70), C71 (H71), C72 (H72),
 C76 (H76), C77 (H77), C78 (H78), C79 (H79), C80 (H80), C82 (H82), C83 (H83), C84 (H84),
 C85 (H85), C86 (H86), C88 (H88), C89 (H89), C90 (H90), C91 (H91), C92 (H92),
 C100 (H100), C101 (H101), C102 (H102), C103 (H103), C104 (H104), C106 (H106),
 C107 (H107), C108 (H108), C109 (H109), C110 (H110), C112 (H112), C113 (H113),
 C114 (H114), C115 (H115), C116 (H116), C2D (H2D), C3D (H3D), C4D (H4D), C5D (H5D),
 C6D (H6D), C13D (H13D), C12D (H12D), C11D (H11D), C10D (H10D), C9D (H9D)
 4.b Fitted hexagon refined as free rotating group:
 C1D (C2D, C3D, C4D, C5D, C6D), C8D (C13D, C12D, C11D, C10D, C9D)
 4.c Idealised Me refined as rotating group:
 C50 (H50A, H50B, H50C), C51 (H51A, H51B, H51C), C52 (H52A, H52B, H52C), C94 (H94A, H94B,
 H94C), C95 (H95A, H95B, H95C), C96 (H96A, H96B, H96C), C7D (H7DA, H7DB, H7DC),
 C14D (H14A, H14B, H14C)

X-Ray Data Compound 3

SERVICIO GENERAL RAYOS X Unidad de Moléculas y Materiales

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a20180338_JM214

Comentario:

El usuario envió una muestra del compuesto **JM214** (agujas amarillas) para determinar su estructura molecular. Se selecciona uno de ellos de tamaño aproximado $0.79 \times 0.12 \times 0.05 \text{ mm}^3$ para realizar la toma de datos.

Se confirma la estructura molecular coincidente con la propuesta por el usuario. La estructura cristalina determinada no es centrosimétrica (grupo espacial $P2_1$), en principio solo un enantiómero está presente en la estructura.

Table 1 Crystal data and structure refinement for a20180338_JM214.

Identification code	a20180338_JM214
Empirical formula	$C_{126}H_{110}N_4Si_6$
Formula weight	1848.71
Temperature/K	150.01(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	9.4345(6)
b/Å	17.9860(9)
c/Å	18.1448(7)
$\alpha/^\circ$	101.325(4)
$\beta/^\circ$	95.447(4)
$\gamma/^\circ$	105.097(5)
Volume/Å ³	2879.9(3)
Z	1
$\rho_{\text{calc}}/\text{cm}^3$	1.066
μ/mm^{-1}	1.039
F(000)	978.0
Crystal size/mm ³	$0.79 \times 0.12 \times 0.05$
Radiation	CuK α ($\lambda = 1.54184$)
2 Θ range for data collection/ $^\circ$	8.048 to 137.958
Index ranges	$-11 \leq h \leq 10$, $-14 \leq k \leq 21$, $-21 \leq l \leq 20$
Reflections collected	19720
Independent reflections	10584 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0977$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.1084$]
Data/restraints/parameters	10584/438/803
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.378

Final R indexes [$I \geq 2\sigma(I)$] $R_1 = 0.1321$, $wR_2 = 0.3585$

Final R indexes [all data] $R_1 = 0.1796$, $wR_2 = 0.4123$

Largest diff. peak/hole / $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$ 1.07/-0.52

[a] Esquema de pesado: $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.2000P)^2]$ donde $P = [\text{Max}(F_o^2, 0) + 2F_c^2]/3$.

[b] Expresión de extinción secundaria tipo SHELXL: $F_c^* = kF_c[1 + 0.001F_c^2\lambda^3/\text{sen}(2\theta)]^{-1/4}$

Table 2 Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for a20180338_JM214. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} tensor.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
Si1	3945 (2)	3321.1 (10)	-4851.5 (9)	42.4 (4)
Si2	843 (2)	8503.3 (10)	-989.7 (11)	48.0 (5)
Si3	1927.4 (17)	6674.3 (10)	1712.3 (8)	37.3 (4)
N1	3084 (5)	6108 (3)	-1216 (2)	31.6 (9)
N2	4208 (5)	5018 (3)	-2136 (2)	32.4 (9)
C1	3224 (7)	5359 (3)	-3250 (3)	37.5 (12)
C1A	3576 (7)	4720 (3)	-3735 (3)	40.0 (13)
C2	2570 (8)	5843 (4)	-3558 (3)	45.8 (15)
C2A	3770 (7)	4176 (4)	-4181 (3)	45.4 (14)
C3	2164 (8)	6448 (4)	-3085 (3)	46.2 (15)
C3A	1886 (8)	7163 (4)	-1856 (3)	43.8 (15)
C4	2341 (7)	6551 (4)	-2312 (3)	40.8 (13)
C4A	1443 (9)	7702 (4)	-1520 (4)	52.6 (16)
C5	2991 (6)	6047 (3)	-1974 (3)	34.7 (12)
C6	3729 (6)	5644 (3)	-922 (3)	25.8 (10)
C7	3804 (6)	5676 (3)	-106 (3)	27.5 (10)
C8	5367 (5)	4755 (3)	-231 (3)	24.9 (10)
C9	5262 (6)	4690 (3)	-1025 (3)	28.4 (10)
C10	4380 (6)	5114 (3)	-1383 (3)	27.7 (10)
C11	3489 (6)	5464 (3)	-2438 (3)	33.8 (11)
C14	2481 (13)	2464 (6)	-4653 (6)	61 (3)
C15B	2355 (12)	2455 (6)	-3897 (6)	67 (4)
C16	1293 (12)	1846 (6)	-3721 (5)	102 (3)
C17	358 (12)	1246 (6)	-4301 (6)	97 (6)
C18	485 (13)	1254 (6)	-5056 (5)	76 (4)
C19	1546 (14)	1863 (7)	-5232 (5)	75 (4)
C26	3290 (7)	3382 (4)	-5834 (4)	47.0 (14)
C27	2323 (10)	3831 (5)	-5970 (5)	71 (2)
C28	1860 (12)	3896 (6)	-6687 (6)	86 (3)
C29	2321 (11)	3507 (6)	-7312 (6)	77 (2)
C30	3278 (11)	3083 (6)	-7212 (5)	74 (2)
C31	3796 (9)	3042 (5)	-6481 (4)	62.2 (18)
C32	820 (13)	9244 (6)	-1660 (6)	54 (4)
C33	28 (15)	8975 (6)	-2393 (7)	76 (5)
C34	-45 (17)	9508 (8)	-2846 (6)	106 (7)
C35	674 (17)	10309 (8)	-2567 (8)	93 (6)

C36	1466 (15)	10578 (5)	-1833 (8)	83 (5)
C37	1539 (13)	10045 (6)	-1380 (6)	62 (4)
C38	1974 (10)	8748 (7)	17 (5)	49 (3)
C39	1570 (9)	9219 (7)	617 (6)	45 (5)
C40	2502 (12)	9503 (7)	1313 (5)	60 (6)
C41	3837 (11)	9316 (7)	1410 (5)	71 (4)
C42	4240 (10)	8845 (7)	810 (6)	82 (5)
C43	3309 (11)	8561 (6)	114 (5)	72 (4)
C44	-1113 (7)	8142 (4)	-846 (4)	45.3 (13)
C45	-1624 (10)	7443 (5)	-635 (5)	69 (2)
C46	-3030 (11)	7190 (6)	-493 (6)	82 (3)
C47	-3982 (11)	7638 (6)	-538 (6)	78 (2)
C48	-3551 (10)	8329 (6)	-793 (6)	77 (2)
C49	-2098 (9)	8583 (5)	-948 (5)	63.1 (18)
C50	3051 (6)	6120 (3)	340 (3)	29.6 (10)
C51	3071 (6)	6152 (3)	1111 (3)	30.5 (10)
C52	470 (6)	6861 (3)	1050 (3)	39.1 (12)
C53	-327 (8)	7441 (4)	1429 (4)	51.9 (15)
C54	-692 (7)	6088 (4)	590 (4)	50.2 (15)
C55	3201 (9)	7632 (5)	2302 (5)	63.3 (18)
C62	6040 (6)	4243 (3)	-1446 (3)	31.1 (11)
C20	5749 (15)	3230 (8)	-4808 (7)	29 (3)
C21	6934 (18)	3883 (11)	-4467 (8)	38 (3)
C22	8463 (15)	3945 (9)	-4438 (8)	43 (3)
C23	8723 (17)	3213 (11)	-4773 (8)	44 (3)
C24	7560 (20)	2514 (13)	-5117 (10)	66 (4)
C25	6158 (19)	2557 (11)	-5099 (9)	53 (3)
C57	4760 (20)	7704 (13)	2458 (13)	85 (5)
C58	2700 (20)	7909 (13)	3121 (12)	83 (5)
C59B	962 (13)	5840 (9)	2296 (7)	28 (2)
C60B	-282 (14)	6060 (9)	2642 (8)	40 (3)
C61B	574 (16)	4998 (9)	1856 (9)	47 (3)
C17B	1240 (30)	1043 (16)	-4212 (15)	105 (7)
C18B	2060 (40)	1030 (20)	-4700 (20)	134 (9)
C19B	2910 (30)	1680 (17)	-4907 (17)	116 (8)
C20B	6170 (20)	3476 (11)	-4713 (9)	40 (4)
C21B	7128 (19)	4179 (13)	-4416 (10)	53 (4)
C22B	8650 (30)	4311 (17)	-4371 (15)	93 (7)
C23B	9050 (20)	3598 (14)	-4695 (11)	72 (5)
C24B	8120 (20)	2851 (13)	-5033 (11)	59 (4)
C25B	6690 (20)	2856 (13)	-5036 (11)	68 (5)
C56	4070 (30)	8074 (14)	1780 (14)	99 (6)
C57B	4400 (30)	7523 (15)	2890 (15)	98 (6)
C59	1253 (16)	6123 (10)	2402 (8)	41 (3)
C60	-31 (19)	6384 (11)	2767 (11)	57 (4)

C61	610 (20)	5248 (12)	2067 (12)	62 (5)
C38B	2117 (10)	9057 (7)	-119 (6)	45 (3)
C39B	1564 (11)	9120 (10)	567 (7)	78 (9)
C40B	2512 (17)	9518 (11)	1243 (6)	112 (14)
C41B	4013 (16)	9851 (8)	1234 (6)	83 (5)
C42B	4566 (10)	9788 (8)	548 (7)	96 (6)
C43B	3618 (11)	9391 (8)	-128 (6)	75 (4)
C32B	1175 (14)	9317 (6)	-1443 (7)	47 (3)
C33B	882 (19)	9137 (7)	-2233 (7)	112 (7)
C34B	1060 (20)	9741 (10)	-2620 (6)	131 (9)
C35B	1525 (19)	10526 (8)	-2217 (8)	96 (6)
C36B	1817 (16)	10707 (5)	-1427 (8)	71 (4)
C37B	1642 (14)	10102 (6)	-1040 (6)	68 (4)
C14B	2930 (20)	2406 (11)	-4577 (11)	67 (4)
C15	2100 (20)	2500 (10)	-3920 (10)	61 (3)

**Table 3 Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for a20180338_JM214.
The Anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: -
 $2\pi^2[h^2a^*2U_{11}+2hka^*b^*U_{12}+\dots]$.**

Atom	U ₁₁	U ₂₂	U ₃₃	U ₂₃	U ₁₃	U ₁₂
Si1	60.2 (9)	41.6 (9)	32.5 (8)	5.5 (6)	17.8 (7)	25.1 (7)
Si2	59.0 (10)	43.2 (9)	53.1 (10)	6.9 (7)	17.9 (8)	33.9 (8)
Si3	49.3 (8)	50.9 (9)	22.6 (7)	6.1 (6)	11.6 (6)	32.4 (7)
N1	50 (2)	35 (2)	18 (2)	6.3 (16)	10.6 (17)	25 (2)
N2	47 (2)	40 (2)	18 (2)	7.9 (17)	8.8 (17)	23 (2)
C1	63 (3)	42 (3)	22 (3)	12 (2)	13 (2)	34 (3)
C1A	65 (3)	43 (3)	25 (3)	8 (2)	17 (2)	34 (3)
C2	78 (4)	58 (4)	17 (2)	9 (2)	13 (3)	44 (3)
C2A	57 (3)	60 (4)	27 (3)	11 (3)	10 (2)	29 (3)
C3	79 (4)	54 (4)	26 (3)	13 (2)	11 (3)	51 (3)
C3A	75 (4)	52 (3)	26 (3)	11 (2)	10 (3)	53 (3)
C4	70 (4)	46 (3)	23 (3)	14 (2)	13 (2)	39 (3)
C4A	81 (4)	60 (4)	37 (3)	22 (3)	19 (3)	43 (4)
C5	50 (3)	39 (3)	24 (3)	6 (2)	12 (2)	27 (2)
C6	45 (2)	28 (2)	16 (2)	10.3 (18)	8.0 (19)	24 (2)
C7	39 (2)	32 (2)	19 (2)	5.9 (18)	10.7 (19)	21 (2)
C8	40 (2)	28 (2)	16 (2)	8.2 (18)	8.4 (19)	22 (2)
C9	43 (2)	30 (2)	18 (2)	5.2 (18)	7.8 (19)	18 (2)
C10	46 (3)	31 (2)	15 (2)	7.2 (18)	8.5 (19)	24 (2)
C11	53 (3)	38 (3)	21 (2)	6 (2)	11 (2)	29 (2)
C14	61 (4)	61 (4)	61 (4)	14.1 (11)	9.9 (9)	17.5 (12)
C15B	67 (4)	66 (4)	67 (4)	15.4 (11)	10.5 (9)	19.1 (13)
C16	102 (3)	102 (3)	102 (3)	23.7 (13)	16.1 (11)	28.9 (14)
C17	97 (6)	97 (6)	97 (6)	22.5 (17)	15.0 (14)	27 (2)

C18	76 (4)	75 (4)	75 (4)	17.5 (14)	11.8 (12)	21.1 (16)
C19	75 (4)	75 (4)	75 (4)	17.2 (14)	12.1 (12)	20.9 (16)
C26	53 (2)	46 (2)	41 (2)	4.4 (19)	10 (2)	17 (2)
C27	74 (3)	73 (3)	66 (3)	13 (2)	13 (2)	25 (2)
C28	88 (4)	89 (4)	83 (4)	17 (3)	11 (3)	30 (3)
C29	81 (3)	78 (3)	69 (3)	14 (2)	7 (3)	23 (3)
C30	79 (3)	76 (3)	62 (3)	12 (2)	17 (2)	16 (2)
C31	68 (3)	64 (3)	56 (3)	11 (2)	18 (2)	22 (2)
C32	54 (4)	54 (4)	54 (4)	12.1 (13)	8.7 (12)	15.9 (14)
C33	77 (5)	76 (5)	76 (5)	17.7 (14)	12.0 (12)	22.1 (16)
C34	106 (7)	106 (7)	106 (7)	24.6 (19)	16.5 (15)	30 (2)
C35	93 (6)	93 (6)	93 (6)	21.6 (17)	14.3 (14)	26.7 (19)
C36	83 (5)	83 (5)	83 (5)	19.1 (15)	12.8 (13)	24.1 (17)
C37	62 (4)	62 (4)	63 (4)	14.4 (13)	9.6 (12)	18.3 (14)
C38	51 (4)	49 (4)	47 (4)	12 (3)	13 (3)	12 (3)
C39	51 (6)	43 (6)	45 (6)	9 (3)	5 (3)	22 (3)
C40	63 (7)	59 (7)	58 (7)	11 (3)	6 (3)	20 (3)
C41	74 (5)	70 (5)	68 (5)	21 (3)	9 (3)	16 (3)
C42	80 (6)	85 (6)	83 (6)	20 (3)	11 (3)	25 (3)
C43	71 (5)	75 (5)	71 (5)	16 (3)	13 (3)	22 (3)
C44	53 (2)	40 (2)	44 (2)	4.7 (19)	11 (2)	19 (2)
C45	67 (3)	68 (3)	71 (3)	25 (2)	-1 (2)	17 (2)
C46	80 (3)	83 (3)	81 (3)	27 (3)	8 (3)	15 (3)
C47	74 (3)	78 (3)	75 (3)	14 (3)	18 (3)	12 (2)
C48	75 (3)	74 (3)	82 (3)	6 (2)	19 (3)	31 (3)
C49	65 (3)	58 (3)	71 (3)	11 (2)	15 (2)	27 (2)
C50	45 (3)	35 (3)	20 (2)	8.3 (19)	7.2 (19)	27 (2)
C51	43 (3)	34 (3)	22 (2)	9.1 (19)	13 (2)	21 (2)
C52	40.1 (14)	39.5 (15)	38.9 (15)	9.2 (9)	6.9 (10)	13.0 (10)
C53	55 (2)	51 (2)	53 (2)	10.4 (16)	8.5 (17)	23.0 (17)
C54	51 (2)	51 (2)	50 (2)	12.8 (16)	5.5 (16)	17.9 (16)
C55	63 (2)	63 (2)	64 (2)	12.5 (10)	9.3 (10)	19.7 (11)
C62	50 (3)	33 (3)	18 (2)	6.6 (19)	12 (2)	25 (2)
C20	30 (4)	30 (4)	26 (4)	4 (3)	8 (3)	6 (3)
C21	42 (4)	36 (4)	35 (4)	11 (3)	7 (3)	8 (3)
C22	45 (4)	45 (4)	40 (4)	14 (3)	4 (3)	13 (3)
C23	42 (4)	45 (4)	42 (4)	8 (3)	5 (3)	11 (3)
C24	64 (5)	67 (5)	67 (5)	11 (3)	10 (3)	24 (3)
C25	53 (4)	53 (4)	54 (4)	6 (3)	9 (3)	18 (3)
C57	84 (5)	85 (6)	86 (6)	18 (2)	13 (2)	25 (2)
C58	83 (5)	84 (5)	83 (5)	18 (2)	14 (2)	25 (2)
C59B	29 (3)	28 (3)	28 (3)	7.6 (11)	3.8 (11)	7.7 (12)
C60B	41 (3)	40 (3)	38 (3)	11 (2)	6.1 (19)	10 (2)
C61B	49 (4)	45 (4)	46 (4)	13 (2)	7 (2)	13 (2)
C17B	105 (7)	105 (7)	105 (7)	24.4 (18)	16.4 (15)	30 (2)

C18B	134 (9)	134 (9)	134 (9)	31 (2)	20.9 (18)	38 (3)
C19B	116 (8)	116 (8)	116 (8)	26 (2)	18.2 (16)	33 (2)
C20B	39 (4)	42 (4)	38 (4)	9 (3)	9 (3)	8 (3)
C21B	54 (5)	56 (5)	48 (5)	12 (3)	10 (3)	13 (3)
C22B	94 (7)	94 (7)	90 (7)	22 (3)	15 (3)	25 (3)
C23B	72 (6)	72 (6)	72 (6)	18 (3)	11 (3)	22 (3)
C24B	59 (4)	59 (5)	62 (5)	12 (3)	14 (3)	19 (3)
C25B	67 (5)	69 (5)	70 (5)	16 (3)	13 (3)	23 (3)
C56	98 (7)	98 (7)	100 (7)	22 (2)	14 (2)	28 (3)
C57B	98 (7)	97 (7)	98 (7)	22 (2)	13 (2)	29 (3)
C59	42 (3)	42 (3)	41 (3)	9.8 (12)	6.1 (11)	11.9 (14)
C60	58 (4)	58 (4)	56 (4)	13 (2)	10 (2)	17 (2)
C61	63 (5)	63 (5)	61 (5)	16 (2)	10 (2)	17 (2)
C38B	46 (3)	45 (3)	46 (3)	10.2 (12)	7.0 (11)	13.9 (13)
C39B	79 (9)	78 (9)	78 (9)	18 (2)	11.8 (18)	23 (3)
C40B	112 (14)	112 (14)	112 (14)	26 (3)	17 (2)	32 (4)
C41B	85 (6)	82 (6)	85 (6)	21 (3)	7 (3)	26 (3)
C42B	96 (7)	95 (7)	98 (7)	22 (3)	13 (3)	29 (3)
C43B	73 (5)	76 (5)	76 (5)	16 (3)	12 (3)	24 (3)
C32B	47 (3)	47 (3)	47 (3)	10.4 (12)	7.4 (11)	14.2 (13)
C33B	112 (7)	112 (7)	112 (7)	26 (2)	17.3 (15)	32 (2)
C34B	132 (9)	131 (9)	131 (9)	30 (2)	20.4 (18)	38 (3)
C35B	96 (6)	96 (6)	96 (6)	22.4 (17)	14.7 (14)	27 (2)
C36B	71 (4)	71 (4)	71 (4)	16.7 (14)	10.5 (12)	20.4 (16)
C37B	68 (4)	68 (4)	68 (4)	15.3 (14)	10.5 (12)	19.6 (15)
C14B	67 (4)	66 (4)	67 (4)	15.4 (11)	10.5 (9)	19.1 (13)
C15	61 (4)	61 (4)	61 (4)	14.1 (11)	9.9 (9)	17.5 (12)

Table 4 Bond Lengths for a20180338_JM214.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å	Atom	Atom	Length/Å
Si1	C2A	1.819 (6)	C33	C34	1.3900
Si1	C14	1.902 (8)	C34	C35	1.3900
Si1	C26	1.864 (7)	C35	C36	1.3900
Si1	C20	1.748 (12)	C36	C37	1.3900
Si1	C20B	2.027 (17)	C38	C39	1.3900
Si1	C14B	1.862 (18)	C38	C43	1.3900
Si2	C4A	1.818 (7)	C39	C40	1.3900
Si2	C32	1.975 (9)	C40	C41	1.3900
Si2	C38	1.934 (8)	C41	C42	1.3900
Si2	C44	1.852 (7)	C42	C43	1.3900
Si2	C38B	1.825 (9)	C44	C45	1.366 (10)
Si2	C32B	1.788 (9)	C44	C49	1.391 (10)
Si3	C51	1.893 (5)	C45	C46	1.352 (13)

Si3	C52	1.880 (6)	C46	C47	1.362 (15)
Si3	C55	1.873 (8)	C47	C48	1.386 (13)
Si3	C59B	2.073 (13)	C48	C49	1.402 (12)
Si3	C59	1.806 (14)	C50	C51	1.387 (7)
N1	C5	1.350 (7)	C51	C62 ¹	1.400 (7)
N1	C6	1.316 (6)	C52	C53	1.533 (8)
N2	C10	1.330 (6)	C52	C54	1.552 (9)
N2	C11	1.338 (7)	C55	C57	1.44 (2)
C1	C1A	1.437 (7)	C55	C58	1.63 (2)
C1	C2	1.362 (8)	C55	C56	1.52 (2)
C1	C11	1.437 (7)	C55	C57B	1.56 (3)
C1A	C2A	1.206 (9)	C20	C21	1.38 (2)
C2	C3	1.406 (7)	C20	C25	1.387 (19)
C3	C4	1.366 (8)	C21	C22	1.41 (2)
C3A	C4	1.427 (7)	C22	C23	1.43 (2)
C3A	C4A	1.231 (9)	C23	C24	1.42 (2)
C4	C5	1.418 (8)	C24	C25	1.35 (2)
C5	C11	1.419 (6)	C59B	C60B	1.487 (16)
C6	C7	1.464 (6)	C59B	C61B	1.499 (19)
C6	C10	1.441 (6)	C17B	C18B	1.24 (4)
C7	C8 ¹	1.413 (7)	C18B	C19B	1.37 (4)
C7	C50	1.396 (6)	C19B	C14B	1.32 (3)
C8	C8 ¹	1.448 (8)	C20B	C21B	1.32 (2)
C8	C9	1.415 (7)	C20B	C25B	1.38 (2)
C9	C10	1.456 (7)	C21B	C22B	1.39 (3)
C9	C62	1.394 (6)	C22B	C23B	1.46 (3)
C14	C19	1.3900	C23B	C24B	1.38 (3)
C14	C15	1.40 (2)	C24B	C25B	1.35 (3)
C15B	C16	1.3900	C59	C60	1.57 (2)
C15B	C14B	1.39 (2)	C59	C61	1.51 (2)
C16	C17	1.3900	C38B	C39B	1.3900
C16	C17B	1.53 (3)	C38B	C43B	1.3900
C16	C15	1.36 (2)	C39B	C40B	1.3900
C17	C18	1.3900	C40B	C41B	1.3900
C18	C19	1.3900	C41B	C42B	1.3900
C26	C27	1.401 (11)	C42B	C43B	1.3900
C26	C31	1.399 (10)	C32B	C33B	1.3900
C27	C28	1.370 (14)	C32B	C37B	1.3900
C28	C29	1.381 (14)	C33B	C34B	1.3900
C29	C30	1.346 (14)	C34B	C35B	1.3900
C30	C31	1.391 (12)	C35B	C36B	1.3900
C32	C33	1.3900	C36B	C37B	1.3900
C32	C37	1.3900			

¹1-X,1-Y,-Z

Table 5 Bond Angles for a20180338_JM214.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C2A	Si1	C14	103.2 (4)	C33	C32	Si2	120.4 (6)
C2A	Si1	C26	108.8 (3)	C33	C32	C37	120.0
C2A	Si1	C20B	102.8 (6)	C37	C32	Si2	119.5 (6)
C2A	Si1	C14B	108.8 (6)	C32	C33	C34	120.0
C26	Si1	C14	105.1 (4)	C35	C34	C33	120.0
C26	Si1	C20B	109.6 (5)	C34	C35	C36	120.0
C20	Si1	C2A	114.2 (5)	C35	C36	C37	120.0
C20	Si1	C14	116.0 (7)	C36	C37	C32	120.0
C20	Si1	C26	108.8 (4)	C39	C38	Si2	119.4 (6)
C14B	Si1	C26	114.4 (6)	C39	C38	C43	120.0
C14B	Si1	C20B	111.7 (8)	C43	C38	Si2	119.8 (6)
C4A	Si2	C32	106.1 (4)	C38	C39	C40	120.0
C4A	Si2	C38	104.1 (4)	C39	C40	C41	120.0
C4A	Si2	C44	110.7 (3)	C42	C41	C40	120.0
C4A	Si2	C38B	113.3 (4)	C41	C42	C43	120.0
C38	Si2	C32	126.5 (5)	C42	C43	C38	120.0
C44	Si2	C32	104.9 (4)	C45	C44	Si2	121.3 (6)
C44	Si2	C38	104.3 (4)	C45	C44	C49	118.4 (7)
C38B	Si2	C44	114.0 (4)	C49	C44	Si2	120.3 (5)
C32B	Si2	C4A	110.2 (4)	C46	C45	C44	122.0 (9)
C32B	Si2	C44	113.5 (5)	C45	C46	C47	120.6 (9)
C32B	Si2	C38B	94.4 (6)	C46	C47	C48	119.8 (9)
C51	Si3	C59B	102.6 (4)	C47	C48	C49	119.0 (9)
C52	Si3	C51	107.8 (2)	C44	C49	C48	119.9 (8)
C52	Si3	C59B	110.6 (4)	C51	C50	C7	122.3 (5)
C55	Si3	C51	108.0 (3)	C50	C51	Si3	123.3 (4)
C55	Si3	C52	110.5 (3)	C50	C51	C62 ¹	117.4 (4)
C55	Si3	C59B	116.6 (5)	C62 ¹	C51	Si3	119.3 (3)
C59	Si3	C51	110.1 (5)	C53	C52	Si3	114.6 (4)
C59	Si3	C52	116.0 (5)	C53	C52	C54	109.7 (5)
C59	Si3	C55	104.2 (6)	C54	C52	Si3	112.9 (4)
C6	N1	C5	117.8 (4)	C57	C55	Si3	118.6 (11)
C10	N2	C11	117.5 (4)	C57	C55	C58	105.9 (13)
C2	C1	C1A	120.1 (5)	C58	C55	Si3	113.4 (9)
C2	C1	C11	119.8 (5)	C56	C55	Si3	108.5 (11)
C11	C1	C1A	120.0 (5)	C56	C55	C57B	105.0 (15)
C2A	C1A	C1	174.8 (7)	C57B	C55	Si3	113.5 (10)
C1	C2	C3	120.3 (5)	C9	C62	C51 ¹	122.3 (4)
C1A	C2A	Si1	176.4 (6)	C21	C20	Si1	119.2 (10)
C4	C3	C2	122.1 (5)	C21	C20	C25	114.0 (13)
C4A	C3A	C4	174.4 (6)	C25	C20	Si1	126.7 (12)

C3	C4	C3A	120.2 (5)	C20	C21	C22	127.4 (15)
C3	C4	C5	119.0 (5)	C21	C22	C23	112.4 (14)
C5	C4	C3A	120.8 (5)	C24	C23	C22	123.0 (13)
C3A	C4A	Si2	177.6 (6)	C25	C24	C23	116.9 (17)
N1	C5	C4	119.7 (4)	C24	C25	C20	126.0 (18)
N1	C5	C11	120.5 (5)	C60B	C59B	Si3	109.9 (9)
C4	C5	C11	119.8 (5)	C60B	C59B	C61B	114.2 (13)
N1	C6	C7	119.3 (4)	C61B	C59B	Si3	114.8 (8)
N1	C6	C10	121.3 (4)	C18B	C17B	C16	118 (3)
C10	C6	C7	119.4 (4)	C17B	C18B	C19B	125 (4)
C8 ¹	C7	C6	119.6 (4)	C14B	C19B	C18B	122 (3)
C50	C7	C6	120.6 (4)	C21B	C20B	Si1	121.7 (12)
C50	C7	C8 ¹	119.7 (4)	C21B	C20B	C25B	119.3 (18)
C7 ¹	C8	C8 ¹	120.3 (5)	C25B	C20B	Si1	118.4 (15)
C7 ¹	C8	C9	118.6 (4)	C20B	C21B	C22B	123 (2)
C9	C8	C8 ¹	121.1 (5)	C21B	C22B	C23B	112 (2)
C8	C9	C10	119.2 (4)	C24B	C23B	C22B	128 (2)
C62	C9	C8	119.5 (5)	C25B	C24B	C23B	109.7 (18)
C62	C9	C10	121.2 (4)	C24B	C25B	C20B	127 (2)
N2	C10	C6	120.7 (4)	C60	C59	Si3	112.8 (11)
N2	C10	C9	119.3 (4)	C61	C59	Si3	113.2 (11)
C6	C10	C9	119.9 (4)	C61	C59	C60	104.6 (14)
N2	C11	C1	119.6 (4)	C39B	C38B	Si2	118.5 (7)
N2	C11	C5	121.5 (5)	C39B	C38B	C43B	120.0
C5	C11	C1	118.9 (5)	C43B	C38B	Si2	121.5 (7)
C19	C14	Si1	122.3 (6)	C40B	C39B	C38B	120.0
C19	C14	C15	116.4 (9)	C39B	C40B	C41B	120.0
C15	C14	Si1	120.1 (10)	C40B	C41B	C42B	120.0
C16	C15B	C14B	124.8 (10)	C43B	C42B	C41B	120.0
C15B	C16	C17B	111.5 (12)	C42B	C43B	C38B	120.0
C15	C16	C17	117.3 (10)	C33B	C32B	Si2	117.0 (7)
C16	C17	C18	120.0	C33B	C32B	C37B	120.0
C19	C18	C17	120.0	C37B	C32B	Si2	122.9 (7)
C18	C19	C14	120.0	C32B	C33B	C34B	120.0
C27	C26	Si1	121.5 (5)	C35B	C34B	C33B	120.0
C31	C26	Si1	123.6 (6)	C34B	C35B	C36B	120.0
C31	C26	C27	114.7 (7)	C37B	C36B	C35B	120.0
C28	C27	C26	122.2 (8)	C36B	C37B	C32B	120.0
C27	C28	C29	120.7 (10)	C15B	C14B	Si1	120.3 (13)
C30	C29	C28	119.5 (10)	C19B	C14B	Si1	125.2 (19)
C29	C30	C31	119.8 (9)	C19B	C14B	C15B	113 (2)
C30	C31	C26	122.8 (8)	C16	C15	C14	121.3 (16)

¹I-X,I-Y,-Z

Table 6 Torsion Angles for a20180338_JM214.

A	B	C	D	Angle/°	A	B	C	D	Angle/°
Si1	C14	C19	C18	-179.4(11)	C35	C36	C37	C32	0.0
Si1	C14	C15	C16	-166.7(13)	C37	C32	C33	C34	0.0
Si1	C26	C27	C28	178.4(7)	C38	Si2	C44	C45	-67.6(7)
Si1	C26	C31	C30	179.0(6)	C38	Si2	C44	C49	112.2(7)
Si1	C20	C21	C22	-173.9(11)	C38	C39	C40	C41	0.0
Si1	C20	C25	C24	174.1(14)	C39	C38	C43	C42	0.0
Si1	C20B	C21B	C22B	-174.7(16)	C39	C40	C41	C42	0.0
Si1	C20B	C25B	C24B	177.3(16)	C40	C41	C42	C43	0.0
Si2	C32	C33	C34	176.7(9)	C41	C42	C43	C38	0.0
Si2	C32	C37	C36	-176.7(9)	C43	C38	C39	C40	0.0
Si2	C38	C39	C40	-169.8(8)	C44	Si2	C38B	C39B	3.9(8)
Si2	C38	C43	C42	169.8(8)	C44	Si2	C38B	C43B	-178.0(7)
Si2	C44	C45	C46	176.8(7)	C44	Si2	C32B	C33B	-84.6(8)
Si2	C44	C49	C48	-176.1(6)	C44	Si2	C32B	C37B	92.7(8)
Si2	C38B	C39B	C40B	178.1(9)	C44	C45	C46	C47	-1.6(15)
Si2	C38B	C43B	C42B	-178.0(9)	C45	C44	C49	C48	3.7(12)
Si2	C32B	C33B	C34B	177.3(9)	C45	C46	C47	C48	5.3(16)
Si2	C32B	C37B	C36B	-177.2(9)	C46	C47	C48	C49	-4.4(15)
N1	C5	C11	N2	-7.4(9)	C47	C48	C49	C44	-0.1(13)
N1	C5	C11	C1	173.2(5)	C49	C44	C45	C46	-2.9(13)
N1	C6	C7	C8 ¹	-173.1(5)	C51	Si3	C52	C53	-166.8(4)
N1	C6	C7	C50	7.6(8)	C51	Si3	C52	C54	66.6(5)
N1	C6	C10	N2	-7.3(8)	C51	Si3	C55	C57	-23.5(13)
N1	C6	C10	C9	171.5(5)	C51	Si3	C55	C58	-148.6(10)
C1	C2	C3	C4	-3.1(11)	C51	Si3	C55	C56	51.6(12)
C1A	C1	C2	C3	177.2(6)	C51	Si3	C55	C57B	-64.6(12)
C1A	C1	C11	N2	7.1(9)	C51	Si3	C59	C60	-164.6(11)
C1A	C1	C11	C5	-173.5(6)	C51	Si3	C59	C61	-46.0(12)
C2	C1	C11	N2	-176.2(6)	C52	Si3	C51	C50	15.3(5)
C2	C1	C11	C5	3.2(9)	C52	Si3	C51	C62 ¹	-163.0(4)
C2	C3	C4	C3A	-178.7(7)	C52	Si3	C55	C57	-141.2(12)
C2	C3	C4	C5	1.7(11)	C52	Si3	C55	C58	93.7(10)
C2A	Si1	C26	C27	-22.2(7)	C52	Si3	C55	C56	-66.1(12)
C2A	Si1	C26	C31	152.8(6)	C52	Si3	C55	C57B	177.7(12)
C2A	Si1	C20	C21	-18.8(12)	C52	Si3	C59	C60	-41.9(14)
C2A	Si1	C20	C25	162.6(12)	C52	Si3	C59	C61	76.7(12)
C2A	Si1	C14B	C15B	-7.6(15)	C55	Si3	C51	C50	-104.1(5)
C2A	Si1	C14B	C19B	-175(2)	C55	Si3	C51	C62 ¹	77.6(5)
C3	C4	C5	N1	-175.6(6)	C55	Si3	C52	C53	-49.0(5)
C3	C4	C5	C11	2.1(9)	C55	Si3	C52	C54	-175.6(5)
C3A	C4	C5	N1	4.8(9)	C55	Si3	C59	C60	79.8(13)
C3A	C4	C5	C11	-177.5(6)	C55	Si3	C59	C61	-161.6(11)
C4	C5	C11	N2	174.9(6)	C62	C9	C10	N2	6.0(8)

C4	C5	C11	C1	-4.5 (9)	C62	C9	C10	C6	-172.8 (5)
C4A	Si2	C44	C45	43.8 (7)	C20	Si1	C26	C27	-147.2 (8)
C4A	Si2	C44	C49	-136.5 (6)	C20	Si1	C26	C31	27.7 (8)
C4A	Si2	C38B	C39B	-123.8 (7)	C20	C21	C22	C23	-4 (2)
C4A	Si2	C38B	C43B	54.2 (9)	C21	C20	C25	C24	-5 (2)
C4A	Si2	C32B	C33B	40.1 (8)	C21	C22	C23	C24	2 (2)
C4A	Si2	C32B	C37B	-142.6 (8)	C22	C23	C24	C25	-2 (2)
C5	N1	C6	C7	-178.0 (5)	C23	C24	C25	C20	3 (3)
C5	N1	C6	C10	2.9 (8)	C25	C20	C21	C22	5 (2)
C6	N1	C5	C4	-178.3 (5)	C59B	Si3	C51	C50	132.2 (6)
C6	N1	C5	C11	4.0 (8)	C59B	Si3	C51	C62 ¹	-46.2 (6)
C6	C7	C50	C51	178.7 (5)	C59B	Si3	C52	C53	81.7 (6)
C7	C6	C10	N2	173.6 (5)	C59B	Si3	C52	C54	-44.9 (6)
C7	C6	C10	C9	-7.6 (7)	C59B	Si3	C55	C57	91.4 (13)
C7 ¹	C8	C9	C10	178.5 (5)	C59B	Si3	C55	C58	-33.8 (11)
C7 ¹	C8	C9	C62	-3.5 (7)	C17B	C18B	C19B	C14B	1 (6)
C7	C50	C51	Si3	-174.4 (4)	C18B	C19B	C14B	Si1	-176 (2)
C7	C50	C51	C62 ¹	3.9 (8)	C18B	C19B	C14B	C15B	16 (4)
C8 ¹	C7	C50	C51	-0.7 (8)	C20B	Si1	C26	C27	-133.9 (8)
C8 ¹	C8	C9	C10	-1.1 (9)	C20B	Si1	C26	C31	41.0 (9)
C8 ¹	C8	C9	C62	176.9 (6)	C20B	Si1	C14B	C15B	105.2 (14)
C8	C9	C10	N2	-176.0 (5)	C20B	Si1	C14B	C19B	-62 (2)
C8	C9	C10	C6	5.2 (8)	C20B	C21B	C22B	C23B	1 (3)
C8	C9	C62	C51 ¹	0.2 (8)	C21B	C20B	C25B	C24B	6 (3)
C10	N2	C11	C1	-177.6 (5)	C21B	C22B	C23B	C24B	1 (3)
C10	N2	C11	C5	3.1 (8)	C22B	C23B	C24B	C25B	1 (3)
C10	C6	C7	C8 ¹	6.0 (7)	C23B	C24B	C25B	C20B	-4 (3)
C10	C6	C7	C50	-173.3 (5)	C25B	C20B	C21B	C22B	-4 (3)
C10	C9	C62	C51 ¹	178.2 (5)	C59	Si3	C51	C50	142.7 (7)
C11	N2	C10	C6	3.9 (8)	C59	Si3	C51	C62 ¹	-35.6 (7)
C11	N2	C10	C9	-174.9 (5)	C59	Si3	C52	C53	69.3 (7)
C11	C1	C2	C3	0.5 (10)	C59	Si3	C52	C54	-57.3 (7)
C14	Si1	C26	C27	87.9 (8)	C59	Si3	C55	C56	168.7 (12)
C14	Si1	C26	C31	-97.2 (8)	C59	Si3	C55	C57B	52.4 (13)
C14	Si1	C20	C21	-138.7 (10)	C38B	Si2	C44	C45	-85.3 (7)
C14	Si1	C20	C25	42.6 (14)	C38B	Si2	C44	C49	94.5 (7)
C15B	C16	C17B	C18B	-2 (3)	C38B	Si2	C32B	C33B	156.9 (8)
C16	C15B	C14B	Si1	163.6 (11)	C38B	Si2	C32B	C37B	-25.9 (9)
C16	C15B	C14B	C19B	-27 (2)	C38B	C39B	C40B	C41B	0.0
C16	C17	C18	C19	0.0	C39B	C38B	C43B	C42B	0.0
C16	C17B	C18B	C19B	-8 (5)	C39B	C40B	C41B	C42B	0.0
C17	C16	C15	C14	-26 (2)	C40B	C41B	C42B	C43B	0.0
C17	C18	C19	C14	0.0	C41B	C42B	C43B	C38B	0.0
C19	C14	C15	C16	26 (2)	C43B	C38B	C39B	C40B	0.0
C26	Si1	C20	C21	103.0 (10)	C32B	Si2	C44	C45	168.2 (7)

C26	Si1	C20	C25	-75.6 (13)	C32B	Si2	C44	C49	-12.1 (8)
C26	Si1	C14B	C15B	-129.5 (12)	C32B	Si2	C38B	C39B	122.0 (8)
C26	Si1	C14B	C19B	63 (2)	C32B	Si2	C38B	C43B	-59.9 (9)
C26	C27	C28	C29	0.9 (15)	C32B	C33B	C34B	C35B	0.0
C27	C26	C31	C30	-5.7 (11)	C33B	C32B	C37B	C36B	0.0
C27	C28	C29	C30	-2.4 (15)	C33B	C34B	C35B	C36B	0.0
C28	C29	C30	C31	-0.2 (14)	C34B	C35B	C36B	C37B	0.0
C29	C30	C31	C26	4.5 (13)	C35B	C36B	C37B	C32B	0.0
C31	C26	C27	C28	3.0 (12)	C37B	C32B	C33B	C34B	0.0
C32	Si2	C44	C45	157.8 (7)	C14B	Si1	C26	C27	99.8 (9)
C32	Si2	C44	C49	-22.5 (7)	C14B	Si1	C26	C31	-85.3 (9)
C32	C33	C34	C35	0.0	C14B	C15B	C16	C17B	20.6 (16)
C33	C32	C37	C36	0.0	C15	C14	C19	C18	-12.1 (11)
C33	C34	C35	C36	0.0	C15	C16	C17	C18	12.6 (12)
C34	C35	C36	C37	0.0					

¹i-X,i-Y,-Z

Table 7 Hydrogen Atom Coordinates ($\text{\AA} \times 10^4$) and Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for a20180338_JM214.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
H2	2386.69	5771.36	-4094.82	55
H3	1753.87	6794.63	-3310.54	55
H15B	2712.48	2941.04	-3526.16	80
H16A	680.37	1920.39	-3343.18	122
H16	1364.17	1801.11	-3206.98	122
H17	-367.03	829.09	-4180.6	116
H18	-153.91	843.73	-5452.4	91
H19	1633.02	1869.43	-5748.56	90
H27	1977.25	4098.51	-5550.2	85
H28	1215.22	4212.58	-6754.29	104
H29	1965.31	3538.46	-7809.3	92
H30	3598.8	2812.27	-7639.19	89
H31	4524.97	2771.91	-6419.32	75
H33	-463.01	8427.96	-2583.96	92
H34	-585.74	9324.34	-3347.4	128
H35	624.3	10672.99	-2876.57	111
H36	1957.09	11125.28	-1642.29	100
H37	2079.84	10228.91	-878.83	75
H39	657.99	9347.03	550.88	54
H40	2225.74	9824.95	1723.5	72
H41	4473.09	9510.11	1886.14	86
H42	5152.72	8717.35	876.17	99
H43	3584.99	8239.43	-296.45	87

H45	-973.06	7126.23	-586.74	82
H46	-3355.86	6694.31	-360.1	99
H47	-4938.81	7478.1	-396.04	94
H48	-4229.92	8627.31	-860.33	92
H49	-1786.24	9054.75	-1123.47	76
H50	2505.78	6411.11	107.05	36
H52	1001.06	7111.95	669.7	47
H53A	-878.2	7217.57	1804.01	78
H53B	-1018.82	7531.54	1041.63	78
H53C	406.94	7943.93	1683.96	78
H54A	-178.4	5718.98	350.09	75
H54B	-1320.76	6211.52	196.68	75
H54C	-1311.02	5846.84	933.15	75
H55	3120.79	8043.73	2013.86	76
H55A	2608.64	7957.24	2569.25	76
H62	5964.74	4204.36	-1979.02	37
H21	6692.55	4342.71	-4225.67	45
H22	9232.63	4419.73	-4219.91	51
H23	9720.75	3193.41	-4764.47	52
H24	7757.53	2038.12	-5349.23	79
H25	5379.22	2083.35	-5304.44	64
H57A	4900.6	7309.9	2739.44	128
H57B	5283.02	8236.03	2764.45	128
H57C	5152.92	7616.79	1978.49	128
H58A	2331.79	8370.11	3120.88	125
H58B	3558.78	8049.1	3523.78	125
H58C	1914.86	7475.09	3212.32	125
H59B	1736.52	5889.37	2732.97	34
H60A	55.54	6616.06	2919.98	60
H60B	-610.1	5724.11	2993.52	60
H60C	-1111.35	5986.12	2240.08	60
H61A	-199.18	4910.48	1421.75	70
H61B	208.91	4643.57	2186.57	70
H61C	1460.29	4889.61	1671.95	70
H17B	586.6	569.08	-4143.25	126
H18B	2119.57	524.06	-4959.12	161
H19B	3495.83	1606.74	-5297.9	139
H21B	6756.68	4610.42	-4226.12	63
H22B	9355.45	4810.08	-4154.19	112
H23B	10084.58	3654.19	-4670.53	86
H24B	8433.63	2402.52	-5232.86	71
H25B	5951.71	2379.14	-5289.13	82
H56A	4804.1	7809.67	1606.07	148
H56B	4578.46	8618.89	2057.58	148
H56C	3386.11	8078.09	1340.1	148

H57D	3921.14	7271.31	3268.64	147
H57E	5089.99	8041.47	3143.83	147
H57F	4956.71	7189.07	2625.75	147
H59	2095.87	6204.13	2815.03	50
H60D	308.37	6953.12	2998.72	86
H60E	-311.45	6091.86	3157.98	86
H60F	-892.05	6271.81	2372.56	86
H61D	-159.79	5163.38	1629.13	93
H61E	161.26	4990.3	2451.51	93
H61F	1393.56	5022.3	1900.98	93
H39B	537.98	8892.36	573.09	94
H40B	2134.47	9560.88	1712.13	134
H41B	4661.64	10122.77	1696.63	100
H42B	5592.35	10016.13	542.09	116
H43B	3995.88	9347.62	-596.97	89
H33B	563.19	8599.99	-2508.23	134
H34B	857.76	9617.97	-3159.93	158
H35B	1644.21	10939.71	-2481.6	115
H36B	2136.09	11243.48	-1151.55	86
H37B	1841.53	10225.51	-499.82	82
H15	2416.09	2991.32	-3555.34	74

Table 8 Atomic Occupancy for a20180338_JM214.

Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy
C14	0.5	C15B	0.5	H15B	0.5
H16A	0.5	H16	0.5	C17	0.5
H17	0.5	C18	0.5	H18	0.5
C19	0.5	H19	0.5	C32	0.5
C33	0.5	H33	0.5	C34	0.5
H34	0.5	C35	0.5	H35	0.5
C36	0.5	H36	0.5	C37	0.5
H37	0.5	C38	0.5	C39	0.5
H39	0.5	C40	0.5	H40	0.5
C41	0.5	H41	0.5	C42	0.5
H42	0.5	C43	0.5	H43	0.5
H55	0.5	H55A	0.5	C20	0.5
C21	0.5	H21	0.5	C22	0.5
H22	0.5	C23	0.5	H23	0.5
C24	0.5	H24	0.5	C25	0.5
H25	0.5	C57	0.5	H57A	0.5
H57B	0.5	H57C	0.5	C58	0.5
H58A	0.5	H58B	0.5	H58C	0.5
C59B	0.5	H59B	0.5	C60B	0.5

H60A	0.5	H60B	0.5	H60C	0.5
C61B	0.5	H61A	0.5	H61B	0.5
H61C	0.5	C17B	0.5	H17B	0.5
C18B	0.5	H18B	0.5	C19B	0.5
H19B	0.5	C20B	0.5	C21B	0.5
H21B	0.5	C22B	0.5	H22B	0.5
C23B	0.5	H23B	0.5	C24B	0.5
H24B	0.5	C25B	0.5	H25B	0.5
C56	0.5	H56A	0.5	H56B	0.5
H56C	0.5	C57B	0.5	H57D	0.5
H57E	0.5	H57F	0.5	C59	0.5
H59	0.5	C60	0.5	H60D	0.5
H60E	0.5	H60F	0.5	C61	0.5
H61D	0.5	H61E	0.5	H61F	0.5
C38B	0.5	C39B	0.5	H39B	0.5
C40B	0.5	H40B	0.5	C41B	0.5
H41B	0.5	C42B	0.5	H42B	0.5
C43B	0.5	H43B	0.5	C32B	0.5
C33B	0.5	H33B	0.5	C34B	0.5
H34B	0.5	C35B	0.5	H35B	0.5
C36B	0.5	H36B	0.5	C37B	0.5
H37B	0.5	C14B	0.5	C15	0.5
H15	0.5				

Table 9 Solvent masks information for a20180338_JM214.

Number	X	Y	Z	Volume	Electron count	Content
1	-0.500	0.000	0.500	332.2	89.6?	
2	0.361	0.296	0.896	8.8	0.0?	
3	0.639	0.704	0.104	8.8	0.0?	

Experimental

Single crystals of $C_{126}H_{110}N_4Si_6$ [a20180338_JM214] A suitable crystal was selected and **mounted** on a **SuperNova, Single source at offset/far, Atlas** diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 150.01(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the ShelXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the ShelXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

1. Dolomanov, O.V., Bourhis, L.J., Gildea, R.J, Howard, J.A.K. & Puschmann, H. (2009), *J. Appl. Cryst.* 42, 339-341.
2. Sheldrick, G.M. (2015). *Acta Cryst.* A71, 3-8.
3. Sheldrick, G.M. (2015). *Acta Cryst.* C71, 3-8.

Crystal structure determination of [a20180338_JM214]

Crystal Data for $C_{126}H_{110}N_4Si_6$ ($M=1848.71$ g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), $a = 9.4345(6)$ Å, $b = 17.9860(9)$ Å, $c = 18.1448(7)$ Å, $\alpha = 101.325(4)^\circ$, $\beta = 95.447(4)^\circ$, $\gamma = 105.097(5)^\circ$, $V = 2879.9(3)$ Å³, $Z = 1$, $T = 150.01(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 1.039$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.066$ g/cm³, 19720 reflections

measured ($8.048^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 137.958^\circ$), 10584 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0977$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.1084$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.1321 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.4123 (all data).

Refinement model description

Number of restraints - 438, number of constraints - unknown.

Details:

1. Fixed Uiso

At 1.2 times of:

All C(H) groups, All C(H,H) groups

At 1.5 times of:

All C(H,H,H) groups

2. Uiso/Uanis restraints and constraints

Uanis(C52) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C53) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C56) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C55)

$\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C57) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C57B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C58) $\approx$ Ueq,

Uanis(C60) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C59) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C59B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C60B)

$\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C61) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C61B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C54) $\approx$ Ueq:

with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C15B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C19B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C19) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C16)

$\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C17B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C17) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C18) $\approx$ Ueq:

with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C32) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C37) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C37B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C36B)

$\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C36) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C35B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C35) $\approx$ Ueq,

Uanis(C34B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C34) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C33B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C33)

$\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C18B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C14) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C39B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C40B) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C40B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C39B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C38B) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C14B) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C15) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C45) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C44) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C49) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C48)

$\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C47) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C46) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C41B) $\approx$ Ueq,

Uanis(C40) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C39) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C41) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C42)

$\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C43) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C42B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C43B) $\approx$ Ueq,

Uanis(C38) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006

Uanis(C21B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C21) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C20B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C20)

$\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C25) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C25B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C22) $\approx$ Ueq,

Uanis(C22B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C23B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C23) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C24B)

$\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C24) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C26) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C27) $\approx$ Ueq,

Uanis(C28) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C29) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C30) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C31)

$\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.003 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.006

Uanis(C32B) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C14B) = Uanis(C15B)

Uanis(C14) = Uanis(C15)

3. Others

Fixed Sof: C14(0.5) C15B(0.5) H15B(0.5) H16A(0.5) H16(0.5) C17(0.5) H17(0.5)

C18(0.5) H18(0.5) C19(0.5) H19(0.5) C32(0.5) C33(0.5) H33(0.5) C34(0.5)

H34(0.5) C35(0.5) H35(0.5) C36(0.5) H36(0.5) C37(0.5) H37(0.5) C38(0.5)

C39(0.5) H39(0.5) C40(0.5) H40(0.5) C41(0.5) H41(0.5) C42(0.5) H42(0.5)

C43(0.5) H43(0.5) H55(0.5) H55A(0.5) C20(0.5) C21(0.5) H21(0.5) C22(0.5)

H22(0.5) C23(0.5) H23(0.5) C24(0.5) H24(0.5) C25(0.5) H25(0.5) C57(0.5)

H57A(0.5) H57B(0.5) H57C(0.5) C58(0.5) H58A(0.5) H58B(0.5) H58C(0.5)

C59B(0.5)

H59B(0.5) C60B(0.5) H60A(0.5) H60B(0.5) H60C(0.5) C61B(0.5) H61A(0.5)

H61B(0.5) H61C(0.5) C17B(0.5) H17B(0.5) C18B(0.5) H18B(0.5) C19B(0.5)

H19B(0.5) C20B(0.5) C21B(0.5) H21B(0.5) C22B(0.5) H22B(0.5) C23B(0.5)

H23B(0.5) C24B(0.5) H24B(0.5) C25B(0.5) H25B(0.5) C56(0.5) H56A(0.5)

H56B(0.5)

H56C(0.5) C57B(0.5) H57D(0.5) H57E(0.5) H57F(0.5) C59(0.5) H59(0.5) C60(0.5)

H60D(0.5) H60E(0.5) H60F(0.5) C61(0.5) H61D(0.5) H61E(0.5) H61F(0.5)

C38B(0.5)

C39B(0.5) H39B(0.5) C40B(0.5) H40B(0.5) C41B(0.5) H41B(0.5) C42B(0.5)

H42B(0.5) C43B(0.5) H43B(0.5) C32B(0.5) C33B(0.5) H33B(0.5) C34B(0.5)

H34B(0.5) C35B(0.5) H35B(0.5) C36B(0.5) H36B(0.5) C37B(0.5) H37B(0.5)

C14B(0.5) C15(0.5) H15(0.5)

4.a Ternary CH refined with riding coordinates:

C52(H52), C55(H55), C55(H55A), C59B(H59B), C59(H59)
4.b Aromatic/amide H refined with riding coordinates:
C2(H2), C3(H3), C15B(H15B), C16(H16A), C16(H16), C17(H17), C18(H18),
C19(H19),
C27(H27), C28(H28), C29(H29), C30(H30), C31(H31), C33(H33), C34(H34),
C35(H35), C36(H36), C37(H37), C39(H39), C40(H40), C41(H41), C42(H42),
C43(H43),
C45(H45), C46(H46), C47(H47), C48(H48), C49(H49), C50(H50), C62(H62),
C21(H21), C22(H22), C23(H23), C24(H24), C25(H25), C17B(H17B), C18B(H18B),
C19B(H19B), C21B(H21B), C22B(H22B), C23B(H23B), C24B(H24B), C25B(H25B),
C39B(H39B), C40B(H40B), C41B(H41B), C42B(H42B), C43B(H43B), C33B(H33B),
C34B(H34B), C35B(H35B), C36B(H36B), C37B(H37B), C15(H15)
4.c Fitted hexagon refined as free rotating group:
C14(C15B,C16,C17,C18,C19), C32(C33,C34,C35,C36,C37),
C38(C39,C40,C41,C42,C43),
C38B(C39B,C40B,C41B,C42B,C43B), C32B(C33B,C34B,C35B,C36B,C37B)
4.d Idealised Me refined as rotating group:
C53(H53A,H53B,H53C), C54(H54A,H54B,H54C), C57(H57A,H57B,H57C), C58(H58A,H58B,
H58C), C60B(H60A,H60B,H60C), C61B(H61A,H61B,H61C), C56(H56A,H56B,H56C),
C57B(H57D,H57E,H57F), C60(H60D,H60E,H60F), C61(H61D,H61E,H61F)

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X-Ray Data Compound 4

a20180240_JMM199

Table 1 Crystal data and structure refinement for a20180240_JMM199.

Identification code	a20180240_JMM199
Empirical formula	C ₁₀₈ H ₁₂₂ N ₄ Si ₆
Formula weight	1644.63
Temperature/K	150.00(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
a/Å	9.8868(7)
b/Å	14.5757(6)
c/Å	16.8086(13)
α/°	92.729(5)
β/°	91.415(6)
γ/°	90.226(4)
Volume/Å ³	2418.7(3)
Z	1
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.129
μ/mm ⁻¹	1.164
F(000)	882.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.311 × 0.147 × 0.048
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	7.846 to 137.976
Index ranges	-11 ≤ h ≤ 11, -17 ≤ k ≤ 13, -18 ≤ l ≤ 20
Reflections collected	17000
Independent reflections	8946 [R _{int} = 0.0667, R _{sigma} = 0.1116]
Data/restraints/parameters	8946/14/554
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	0.985
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0618, wR ₂ = 0.1306
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.1055, wR ₂ = 0.1544
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.48/-0.38

Table 2 Fractional Atomic Coordinates (×10⁴) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters (Å²×10³) for a20180240_JMM199. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} tensor.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
Si1	7409.8 (10)	-3203.8 (7)	9157.4 (6)	38.1 (2)
Si2	-1759.7 (9)	1483.1 (6)	7579.5 (6)	31.7 (2)
Si3	1916.2 (8)	3069.2 (5)	5056.6 (5)	22.72 (17)
N1	4718 (3)	-1221.6 (16)	6995.4 (15)	25.8 (5)
N2	2734 (2)	139.9 (15)	6845.0 (15)	24.1 (5)

C1	4593 (3)	-749.4 (18)	6335.1 (17)	23.2 (6)
C2	3872 (3)	-1022.8 (19)	7588.1 (19)	27.1 (6)
C3	4009 (3)	-1479 (2)	8322.9 (19)	31.1 (7)
C4	3080 (4)	-1297 (2)	8908 (2)	40.3 (8)
C5	2009 (4)	-686 (2)	8807 (2)	38.4 (8)
C6	1858 (3)	-211 (2)	8114 (2)	31.0 (7)
C7	2818 (3)	-360.6 (19)	7504.9 (19)	26.6 (6)
C8	3610 (3)	-27.8 (18)	6281.8 (18)	23.4 (6)
C9	3621 (3)	562.2 (18)	5598.3 (18)	23.8 (6)
C10	2779 (3)	1327.1 (19)	5579.0 (18)	25.1 (6)
C11	2857 (3)	1951.7 (18)	4975.5 (18)	24.9 (6)
C12	3712 (3)	1746.2 (19)	4347.8 (19)	26.7 (6)
C13	4538 (3)	961.7 (18)	4332.4 (18)	23.7 (6)
C14	4530 (3)	384.3 (18)	4984.5 (18)	22.2 (6)
C15	5122 (4)	-2086 (2)	8476 (2)	34.8 (7)
C16	6025 (4)	-2558 (2)	8695 (2)	40.4 (8)
C17	8772 (4)	-3415 (3)	8402 (2)	54.5 (10)
C18	8947 (6)	-2623 (4)	7861 (3)	73.0 (14)
C19	10220 (8)	-3517 (8)	8783 (7)	62 (3)
C19B	9993 (12)	-3881 (8)	8791 (10)	63 (4)
C20	6613 (5)	-4306 (3)	9499 (2)	50.3 (10)
C21	7551 (6)	-4825 (3)	10066 (3)	73.1 (16)
C22	6139 (6)	-4933 (3)	8796 (3)	68.6 (14)
C23	8028 (4)	-2502 (3)	10059 (2)	44.0 (9)
C24	6909 (5)	-2322 (3)	10653 (3)	62.9 (12)
C25	8664 (6)	-1587 (3)	9864 (3)	63.6 (12)
C26	737 (3)	391 (2)	7998 (2)	33.2 (7)
C27	-239 (3)	856 (2)	7891 (2)	35.1 (7)
C28	-3293 (4)	820 (2)	7892 (3)	45.1 (9)
C29	-3060 (5)	313 (4)	8654 (3)	71.4 (14)
C30	-4558 (4)	1425 (4)	7943 (3)	66.0 (13)
C31	-1645 (4)	2673 (2)	8073 (2)	40.7 (8)
C32	-1768 (5)	2664 (3)	8975 (3)	56.7 (11)
C33	-321 (4)	3150 (3)	7868 (3)	56.9 (11)
C34	-1721 (5)	1516 (3)	6458 (2)	54.9 (11)
C35	-3087 (6)	1800 (4)	6115 (3)	78.6 (18)
C36	-1278 (6)	606 (4)	6060 (3)	73.1 (15)
C37	2209 (3)	3642 (2)	6074.8 (18)	25.9 (6)
C38	2974 (3)	3277 (2)	6689 (2)	33.7 (7)
C39	3210 (4)	3764 (2)	7409 (2)	41.0 (8)
C40	2666 (4)	4633 (3)	7533 (2)	39.8 (8)
C41	1914 (4)	5015 (2)	6931 (2)	37.8 (8)
C42	1697 (3)	4526 (2)	6215 (2)	31.3 (7)
C43	80 (3)	2891.3 (19)	4788.4 (18)	25.7 (6)
C44	-930 (3)	3453 (2)	5092 (2)	31.7 (7)

C45	-2242 (3)	3424 (2)	4772 (2)	39.6 (8)
C46	-2572 (3)	2815 (2)	4136 (2)	41.0 (8)
C47	-1588 (4)	2231 (2)	3841 (2)	41.5 (8)
C48	-281 (4)	2262 (2)	4164 (2)	37.0 (7)
C49	2608 (3)	3887.4 (18)	4335.7 (18)	24.3 (6)
C50	1775 (3)	4336.0 (19)	3801.3 (18)	27.0 (6)
C51	2291 (4)	4999 (2)	3326 (2)	36.0 (7)
C52	3653 (4)	5212 (2)	3359 (2)	38.2 (8)
C53	4499 (4)	4762 (2)	3878 (2)	39.7 (8)
C54	3983 (3)	4112 (2)	4366 (2)	32.5 (7)

Table 3 Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for a20180240_JMM199.
The Anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: -
 $2\pi^2[h^2a^2U_{11}+2hka*b*U_{12}+...]$.

Atom	U ₁₁	U ₂₂	U ₃₃	U ₂₃	U ₁₃	U ₁₂
Si1	41.2 (5)	38.5 (5)	34.3 (5)	0.9 (4)	-7.5 (4)	15.9 (4)
Si2	27.2 (4)	28.8 (4)	38.8 (5)	0.6 (4)	-3.3 (3)	3.2 (3)
Si3	19.8 (4)	19.4 (3)	28.9 (4)	1.0 (3)	-1.6 (3)	8.0 (3)
N1	23.7 (13)	22.0 (11)	31.5 (13)	0.7 (10)	-0.3 (10)	5.7 (9)
N2	23.7 (12)	20.4 (11)	28.1 (13)	0.1 (10)	-1.4 (10)	5.2 (9)
C1	22.1 (14)	20.4 (12)	26.9 (15)	1.6 (11)	-1.8 (11)	4.1 (11)
C2	26.3 (15)	21.4 (13)	33.1 (16)	-1.7 (12)	-5.4 (12)	3.8 (11)
C3	34.2 (17)	29.2 (14)	29.9 (16)	3.9 (12)	-2.3 (13)	6.4 (13)
C4	45 (2)	39.2 (17)	37.4 (19)	8.6 (15)	2.2 (15)	10.6 (15)
C5	37.1 (19)	42.2 (18)	36.6 (18)	4.3 (15)	10.8 (14)	11.7 (15)
C6	29.1 (16)	27.1 (14)	36.6 (17)	-0.1 (13)	-1.0 (13)	5.5 (12)
C7	25.7 (15)	23.4 (13)	30.1 (15)	-3.6 (12)	-4.9 (12)	4.3 (11)
C8	20.7 (14)	19.0 (12)	29.9 (15)	-1.9 (11)	-3.6 (11)	2.7 (10)
C9	20.4 (14)	18.0 (12)	32.6 (15)	-0.5 (11)	-4.5 (11)	3.0 (10)
C10	20.2 (14)	24.4 (13)	30.6 (15)	-0.9 (12)	1.0 (11)	5.7 (11)
C11	23.3 (15)	18.0 (12)	33.1 (15)	-1.9 (11)	-3.3 (12)	6.6 (11)
C12	26.2 (15)	22.8 (13)	31.1 (16)	2.5 (12)	-3.2 (12)	5.4 (11)
C13	21.2 (14)	18.9 (12)	30.6 (15)	-1.1 (11)	-5.3 (11)	4.0 (10)
C14	19.7 (13)	18.2 (12)	28.2 (14)	-1.8 (10)	-3.5 (11)	5.0 (11)
C15	37.0 (18)	36.2 (16)	31.5 (16)	4.4 (13)	-0.4 (14)	5.5 (14)
C16	43 (2)	40.6 (18)	37.6 (18)	8.2 (15)	-5.0 (15)	12.2 (15)
C17	54 (3)	70 (3)	38 (2)	-10.6 (19)	0.7 (18)	17 (2)
C18	71 (3)	96 (4)	52 (3)	-1 (3)	17 (2)	6 (3)
C19	41 (5)	72 (7)	72 (6)	-7 (6)	3 (4)	29 (5)
C19B	63 (5)	64 (5)	62 (5)	3 (2)	2.5 (19)	3 (2)
C20	63 (3)	43 (2)	45 (2)	9.7 (17)	-6.7 (19)	10.5 (18)
C21	109 (4)	43 (2)	67 (3)	12 (2)	-33 (3)	10 (2)
C22	84 (4)	66 (3)	56 (3)	9 (2)	-13 (3)	-8 (3)
C23	48 (2)	46.2 (19)	37.0 (19)	-0.6 (16)	-7.7 (16)	15.3 (16)

C24	72 (3)	74 (3)	41 (2)	-6 (2)	9 (2)	19 (2)
C25	80 (3)	55 (2)	55 (3)	-7 (2)	-4 (2)	-3 (2)
C26	31.6 (17)	31.6 (15)	36.3 (17)	-1.0 (13)	3.4 (13)	3.9 (13)
C27	33.2 (18)	33.8 (16)	37.9 (18)	-3.3 (14)	4.0 (14)	6.0 (14)
C28	39 (2)	39.3 (18)	57 (2)	-3.3 (17)	1.5 (17)	-3.7 (15)
C29	65 (3)	67 (3)	85 (4)	22 (3)	13 (3)	-13 (2)
C30	31 (2)	77 (3)	88 (4)	-17 (3)	5 (2)	1 (2)
C31	33.2 (18)	29.1 (16)	59 (2)	3.0 (15)	-12.2 (16)	7.5 (13)
C32	51 (2)	50 (2)	67 (3)	-17 (2)	-8 (2)	2.2 (19)
C33	50 (2)	36.6 (19)	84 (3)	10 (2)	-12 (2)	-8.2 (17)
C34	58 (3)	65 (3)	41 (2)	6.8 (19)	-10.3 (19)	-16 (2)
C35	92 (4)	80 (3)	64 (3)	28 (3)	-43 (3)	-25 (3)
C36	79 (4)	94 (4)	44 (2)	-21 (2)	3 (2)	-21 (3)
C37	22.0 (14)	26.2 (14)	29.2 (15)	-1.2 (12)	0.4 (12)	1.4 (11)
C38	36.5 (18)	29.2 (15)	35.5 (17)	4.9 (13)	-5.6 (14)	3.9 (13)
C39	44 (2)	45.7 (19)	33.5 (18)	5.5 (15)	-9.1 (15)	-1.2 (16)
C40	42 (2)	48.5 (19)	28.3 (16)	-9.2 (15)	-0.1 (14)	-6.3 (16)
C41	34.4 (18)	34.6 (16)	43.1 (19)	-11.2 (15)	0.8 (15)	3.7 (14)
C42	25.4 (16)	31.1 (15)	37.3 (17)	1.7 (13)	-3.1 (13)	5.8 (12)
C43	25.0 (15)	20.0 (13)	32.1 (15)	2.1 (11)	-0.7 (12)	4.6 (11)
C44	26.3 (16)	27.0 (14)	41.2 (18)	-5.2 (13)	-1.7 (13)	3.1 (12)
C45	22.7 (16)	34.6 (16)	61 (2)	-6.4 (16)	0.2 (15)	7.6 (13)
C46	23.2 (17)	41.2 (18)	58 (2)	2.9 (17)	-9.2 (15)	-4.4 (14)
C47	32.9 (19)	42.5 (18)	48 (2)	-9.7 (16)	-7.1 (15)	-5.8 (15)
C48	32.6 (18)	30.6 (15)	47 (2)	-9.0 (14)	1.2 (15)	4.0 (13)
C49	22.5 (14)	20.4 (12)	29.3 (15)	-5.0 (11)	-2.1 (11)	7.5 (11)
C50	25.9 (15)	23.8 (13)	30.9 (15)	-0.1 (12)	-2.5 (12)	6.3 (11)
C51	43 (2)	32.5 (16)	33.1 (17)	6.6 (13)	1.3 (14)	7.7 (14)
C52	45 (2)	32.1 (16)	38.5 (18)	4.6 (14)	4.8 (15)	-4.1 (14)
C53	28.4 (18)	42.7 (18)	48 (2)	2.3 (16)	5.0 (15)	-6.3 (14)
C54	29.0 (16)	31.0 (15)	37.9 (18)	5.7 (13)	-1.1 (13)	4.9 (12)

Table 4 Bond Lengths for a20180240_JMM199.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å	Atom	Atom	Length/Å
Si1	C16	1.842 (3)	C15	C16	1.191 (5)
Si1	C17	1.890 (4)	C17	C18	1.515 (7)
Si1	C20	1.905 (4)	C17	C19	1.565 (7)
Si1	C23	1.875 (4)	C17	C19B	1.536 (9)
Si2	C27	1.841 (3)	C20	C21	1.541 (5)
Si2	C28	1.893 (4)	C20	C22	1.522 (6)
Si2	C31	1.888 (3)	C23	C24	1.525 (6)
Si2	C34	1.890 (4)	C23	C25	1.524 (6)
Si3	C11	1.880 (3)	C26	C27	1.196 (5)

Si3	C37	1.884 (3)	C28	C29	1.521 (6)
Si3	C43	1.873 (3)	C28	C30	1.534 (6)
Si3	C49	1.879 (3)	C31	C32	1.525 (6)
N1	C1	1.337 (4)	C31	C33	1.534 (6)
N1	C2	1.338 (4)	C34	C35	1.522 (7)
N2	C7	1.357 (4)	C34	C36	1.527 (7)
N2	C8	1.314 (4)	C37	C38	1.392 (4)
C1	C8	1.439 (4)	C37	C42	1.397 (4)
C1	C13 ¹	1.452 (4)	C38	C39	1.388 (5)
C2	C3	1.434 (4)	C39	C40	1.386 (5)
C2	C7	1.432 (4)	C40	C41	1.381 (5)
C3	C4	1.380 (5)	C41	C42	1.381 (5)
C3	C15	1.440 (5)	C43	C44	1.386 (4)
C4	C5	1.399 (5)	C43	C48	1.399 (5)
C5	C6	1.388 (5)	C44	C45	1.390 (5)
C6	C7	1.423 (5)	C45	C46	1.388 (5)
C6	C26	1.432 (4)	C46	C47	1.382 (6)
C8	C9	1.468 (4)	C47	C48	1.390 (5)
C9	C10	1.395 (4)	C49	C50	1.391 (4)
C9	C14	1.401 (5)	C49	C54	1.397 (4)
C10	C11	1.398 (4)	C50	C51	1.387 (5)
C11	C12	1.390 (5)	C51	C52	1.380 (5)
C12	C13	1.407 (4)	C52	C53	1.384 (5)
C13	C14	1.413 (4)	C53	C54	1.386 (5)
C14	C14 ¹	1.461 (5)			

¹1-X,-Y,1-Z

Table 5 Bond Angles for a20180240_JMM199.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C16	Si1	C17	108.86 (18)	C9	C14	C13	119.3 (3)
C16	Si1	C20	106.00 (18)	C9	C14	C14 ¹	120.7 (3)
C16	Si1	C23	107.06 (17)	C13	C14	C14 ¹	120.0 (4)
C17	Si1	C20	113.2 (2)	C16	C15	C3	172.2 (4)
C23	Si1	C17	112.69 (19)	C15	C16	Si1	172.7 (3)
C23	Si1	C20	108.61 (18)	C18	C17	Si1	113.0 (3)
C27	Si2	C28	107.96 (17)	C18	C17	C19	102.8 (6)
C27	Si2	C31	107.25 (15)	C18	C17	C19B	121.5 (7)
C27	Si2	C34	106.46 (19)	C19	C17	Si1	113.7 (5)
C31	Si2	C28	112.64 (18)	C19B	C17	Si1	110.0 (7)
C31	Si2	C34	111.69 (19)	C21	C20	Si1	112.8 (3)
C34	Si2	C28	110.53 (19)	C22	C20	Si1	111.7 (3)
C11	Si3	C37	110.26 (13)	C22	C20	C21	110.7 (4)
C43	Si3	C11	110.75 (13)	C24	C23	Si1	112.0 (3)

C43	Si3	C37	113.16 (14)	C25	C23	Si1	113.7 (3)
C43	Si3	C49	107.03 (13)	C25	C23	C24	108.9 (4)
C49	Si3	C11	109.82 (14)	C27	C26	C6	176.7 (4)
C49	Si3	C37	105.62 (13)	C26	C27	Si2	171.5 (3)
C1	N1	C2	117.9 (2)	C29	C28	Si2	113.7 (3)
C8	N2	C7	118.1 (2)	C29	C28	C30	111.3 (4)
N1	C1	C8	120.5 (3)	C30	C28	Si2	112.1 (3)
N1	C1	C13 ¹	119.8 (2)	C32	C31	Si2	112.4 (3)
C8	C1	C13 ¹	119.7 (3)	C32	C31	C33	109.7 (3)
N1	C2	C3	120.0 (3)	C33	C31	Si2	110.9 (3)
N1	C2	C7	121.3 (3)	C35	C34	Si2	111.0 (4)
C7	C2	C3	118.8 (3)	C35	C34	C36	110.2 (4)
C2	C3	C15	121.7 (3)	C36	C34	Si2	112.8 (3)
C4	C3	C2	118.7 (3)	C38	C37	Si3	124.9 (2)
C4	C3	C15	119.6 (3)	C38	C37	C42	116.9 (3)
C3	C4	C5	122.2 (3)	C42	C37	Si3	118.1 (2)
C6	C5	C4	121.0 (3)	C39	C38	C37	121.6 (3)
C5	C6	C7	118.5 (3)	C40	C39	C38	120.0 (3)
C5	C6	C26	121.1 (3)	C41	C40	C39	119.6 (3)
C7	C6	C26	120.3 (3)	C40	C41	C42	119.9 (3)
N2	C7	C2	120.1 (3)	C41	C42	C37	122.1 (3)
N2	C7	C6	119.3 (3)	C44	C43	Si3	123.0 (2)
C6	C7	C2	120.6 (3)	C44	C43	C48	117.3 (3)
N2	C8	C1	121.7 (3)	C48	C43	Si3	118.9 (2)
N2	C8	C9	118.9 (2)	C43	C44	C45	121.9 (3)
C1	C8	C9	119.3 (3)	C46	C45	C44	120.0 (3)
C10	C9	C8	120.2 (3)	C47	C46	C45	119.0 (3)
C10	C9	C14	119.9 (3)	C46	C47	C48	120.6 (3)
C14	C9	C8	119.8 (3)	C47	C48	C43	121.1 (3)
C9	C10	C11	121.5 (3)	C50	C49	Si3	122.1 (2)
C10	C11	Si3	120.3 (2)	C50	C49	C54	117.9 (3)
C12	C11	Si3	121.6 (2)	C54	C49	Si3	119.9 (2)
C12	C11	C10	118.1 (3)	C51	C50	C49	121.0 (3)
C11	C12	C13	121.7 (3)	C52	C51	C50	120.5 (3)
C12	C13	C1 ¹	120.9 (3)	C51	C52	C53	119.2 (3)
C12	C13	C14	119.1 (3)	C52	C53	C54	120.4 (3)
C14	C13	C1 ¹	120.0 (2)	C53	C54	C49	120.9 (3)

¹i-X,-Y,i-Z

Table 6 Torsion Angles for a20180240_JMM199.

A	B	C	D	Angle/°	A	B	C	D	Angle/°
Si3	C11	C12	C13	172.4 (2)	C17	Si1	C23	C25	54.9 (4)
Si3	C37	C38	C39	176.2 (3)	C20	Si1	C17	C18	153.4 (3)

Si3	C37C42C41	-177.0 (3)	C20Si1	C17C19	-89.9 (6)
Si3	C43C44C45	167.2 (3)	C20Si1	C17C19B	-67.1 (6)
Si3	C43C48C47	-167.5 (3)	C20Si1	C23C24	-54.9 (3)
Si3	C49C50C51	174.1 (2)	C20Si1	C23C25	-178.8 (3)
Si3	C49C54C53	-175.4 (3)	C23Si1	C17C18	-82.8 (4)
N1	C1 C8 N2	-5.8 (4)	C23Si1	C17C19	33.9 (6)
N1	C1 C8 C9	171.6 (2)	C23Si1	C17C19B	56.6 (6)
N1	C2 C3 C4	-176.6 (3)	C26C6	C7 N2	6.3 (4)
N1	C2 C3 C15	6.3 (5)	C26C6	C7 C2	-174.4 (3)
N1	C2 C7 N2	-5.9 (4)	C27Si2	C28C29	32.1 (4)
N1	C2 C7 C6	174.8 (3)	C27Si2	C28C30	159.3 (3)
N2	C8 C9 C10	4.6 (4)	C27Si2	C31C32	-67.4 (3)
N2	C8 C9 C14	-178.8 (3)	C27Si2	C31C33	55.8 (3)
C1	N1 C2 C3	-177.0 (3)	C27Si2	C34C35	165.7 (3)
C1	N1 C2 C7	3.3 (4)	C27Si2	C34C36	41.5 (4)
C1	C8 C9 C10	-172.9 (2)	C28Si2	C31C32	51.2 (3)
C1	C8 C9 C14	3.7 (4)	C28Si2	C31C33	174.4 (3)
C1 ¹	C13C14C9	-175.7 (3)	C28Si2	C34C35	48.7 (4)
C1 ¹	C13C14C14 ¹	4.7 (5)	C28Si2	C34C36	-75.5 (4)
C2	N1 C1 C8	2.3 (4)	C31Si2	C28C29	-86.1 (4)
C2	N1 C1 C13 ¹	-178.1 (3)	C31Si2	C28C30	41.1 (4)
C2	C3 C4 C5	0.2 (5)	C31Si2	C34C35	-77.5 (3)
C3	C2 C7 N2	174.3 (3)	C31Si2	C34C36	158.2 (3)
C3	C2 C7 C6	-4.9 (4)	C34Si2	C28C29	148.2 (4)
C3	C4 C5 C6	-1.9 (6)	C34Si2	C28C30	-84.6 (4)
C4	C5 C6 C7	0.1 (5)	C34Si2	C31C32	176.3 (3)
C4	C5 C6 C26	177.8 (3)	C34Si2	C31C33	-60.5 (3)
C5	C6 C7 N2	-176.0 (3)	C37Si3	C11C10	47.4 (3)
C5	C6 C7 C2	3.3 (5)	C37Si3	C11C12	-128.4 (2)
C7	N2 C8 C1	3.1 (4)	C37Si3	C43C44	27.9 (3)
C7	N2 C8 C9	-174.3 (2)	C37Si3	C43C48	-162.6 (2)
C7	C2 C3 C4	3.1 (5)	C37Si3	C49C50	-112.8 (2)
C7	C2 C3 C15	-174.0 (3)	C37Si3	C49C54	62.5 (3)
C8	N2 C7 C2	2.5 (4)	C37C38C39C40		0.7 (6)
C8	N2 C7 C6	-178.3 (3)	C38C37C42C41		-1.0 (5)
C8	C9 C10C11	173.7 (3)	C38C39C40C41		-1.3 (6)
C8	C9 C14C13	-179.5 (2)	C39C40C41C42		0.7 (5)
C8	C9 C14C14 ¹	0.1 (5)	C40C41C42C37		0.4 (5)
C9	C10C11Si3	-170.0 (2)	C42C37C38C39		0.4 (5)
C9	C10C11C12	6.0 (4)	C43Si3	C11C10	-78.6 (3)
C10	C9 C14C13	-2.9 (4)	C43Si3	C11C12	105.5 (3)
C10	C9 C14C14 ¹	176.7 (3)	C43Si3	C37C38	122.6 (3)
C10	C11C12C13	-3.5 (4)	C43Si3	C37C42	-61.7 (3)
C11	Si3 C37C38	-2.0 (3)	C43Si3	C49C50	8.0 (3)
C11	Si3 C37C42	173.6 (2)	C43Si3	C49C54	-176.7 (2)

C11 Si3 C43C44	152.3 (3)	C43C44C45 C46	0.5 (5)
C11 Si3 C43C48	-38.2 (3)	C44C43C48C47	2.6 (5)
C11 Si3 C49C50	128.3 (2)	C44C45 C46C47	1.4 (6)
C11 Si3 C49C54	-56.4 (3)	C45C46C47C48	-1.2 (6)
C11 C12C13C1 ¹	178.9 (3)	C46C47C48C43	-0.8 (6)
C11 C12C13C14	-2.1 (4)	C48C43C44C45	-2.5 (5)
C12 C13C14C9	5.3 (4)	C49Si3 C11C10	163.4 (2)
C12 C13C14C14 ¹	-174.3 (3)	C49Si3 C11C12	-12.5 (3)
C13 ¹ C1 C8 N2	174.6 (3)	C49Si3 C37C38	-120.6 (3)
C13 ¹ C1 C8 C9	-8.0 (4)	C49Si3 C37C42	55.1 (3)
C14 C9 C10C11	-2.9 (4)	C49Si3 C43C44	-88.0 (3)
C15 C3 C4 C5	177.4 (3)	C49Si3 C43C48	81.5 (3)
C16 Si1 C17C18	35.8 (4)	C49C50C51C52	1.6 (5)
C16 Si1 C17C19	152.5 (5)	C50C49C54C53	0.0 (5)
C16 Si1 C17C19B	175.3 (6)	C50C51C52C53	-0.6 (5)
C16 Si1 C23C24	59.2 (3)	C51C52C53C54	-0.7 (5)
C16 Si1 C23C25	-64.8 (4)	C52C53C54C49	1.0 (5)
C17 Si1 C23C24	178.8 (3)	C54C49C50C51	-1.3 (4)

¹I-X,-Y,I-Z

Table 7 Hydrogen Atom Coordinates ($\text{\AA}\times 10^4$) and Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2\times 10^3$) for a20180240_JMM199.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
H4	3169.93	-1597.12	9396.03	48
H5	1375.74	-594.01	9219	46
H10	2136.87	1425.85	5985.29	30
H12	3738.88	2145.76	3918.03	32
H17	8375.3	-3912.22	8036.79	65
H17A	8542.21	-3983.74	8069.56	65
H18A	8079.35	-2494.06	7594.84	109
H18B	9617.81	-2787.19	7459.27	109
H18C	9255.47	-2077.02	8177.12	109
H19A	10458.98	-2956.1	9101.3	93
H19B	10876.15	-3616.8	8360.8	93
H19C	10230.96	-4041.83	9126.62	93
H19D	10487.6	-3431.87	9141.3	94
H19E	10593.12	-4121.98	8376.14	94
H19F	9678.6	-4386.71	9104.23	94
H20	5792.08	-4125.62	9803.4	60
H21A	8372.69	-5012.01	9788.29	110
H21B	7081.73	-5371.64	10240.1	110
H21C	7795.99	-4423.18	10531.94	110
H22A	5484.78	-4606.69	8467.1	103

H22B	5710.48	-5482.59	8992.99	103
H22C	6917.39	-5113.84	8475.18	103
H23	8742.59	-2866.72	10329.59	53
H24A	6194	-1957.85	10408.22	94
H24B	7282.61	-1983.54	11127.3	94
H24C	6531.16	-2908.21	10807.32	94
H25A	9419.79	-1698.78	9506.11	95
H25B	8997.81	-1268.45	10357.4	95
H25C	7984.96	-1207.38	9604.5	95
H28	-3484.54	339.6	7459.25	54
H29A	-2297.51	-108.51	8586.48	107
H29B	-3875.8	-35.89	8768.08	107
H29C	-2856.62	757.79	9096.63	107
H30A	-4422.44	1904.46	8366.08	99
H30B	-5341.64	1045.6	8062.24	99
H30C	-4717.77	1709.47	7432.82	99
H31	-2412.52	3041.68	7860.4	49
H32A	-2680.76	2463.66	9104.26	85
H32B	-1599	3282.69	9210.44	85
H32C	-1102.46	2238.34	9190.1	85
H33A	448.05	2800.4	8070.74	85
H33B	-298.96	3772.89	8113.93	85
H33C	-266.92	3179.98	7288.49	85
H34	-1044.38	1994.16	6326.39	66
H35A	-3774.8	1346.55	6239.76	118
H35B	-3032.08	1832.96	5535.71	118
H35C	-3332.46	2403.28	6348.84	118
H36A	-375.97	447.14	6264.26	110
H36B	-1250.49	665.21	5482.52	110
H36C	-1922.8	121.96	6178.8	110
H38	3343.41	2679.44	6613.32	40
H39	3743.38	3502.7	7816.78	49
H40	2810.52	4963.44	8028.97	48
H41	1546.87	5612.7	7009.19	45
H42	1182.74	4798.56	5804.6	38
H44	-721.58	3869.81	5529.57	38
H45	-2912.16	3821.28	4989.76	47
H46	-3460.58	2800.78	3907.7	49
H47	-1807.45	1803.12	3412.36	50
H48	379.43	1849.84	3957.56	44
H50	839.49	4185.8	3761.52	32
H51	1702.47	5309.18	2974.46	43
H52	4005.96	5662.55	3028.79	46
H53	5439.57	4900.26	3900.81	48
H54	4573.35	3815.28	4725.6	39

Table 8 Atomic Occupancy for a20180240_JMM199.

Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy
H17	0.45	H17A	0.55	C19	0.55
H19A	0.55	H19B	0.55	H19C	0.55
C19B	0.45	H19D	0.45	H19E	0.45
H19F	0.45				

Experimental

Single crystals of C₁₀₈H₁₂₂N₄Si₆ [a20180240_JMM199]. A suitable crystal was selected and mounted on a SuperNova, Single source at offset/far, Atlas diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 150.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the ShelXS [2] structure solution program using Direct Methods and refined with the ShelXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

1. Dolomanov, O.V., Bourhis, L.J., Gildea, R.J., Howard, J.A.K. & Puschmann, H. (2009), J. Appl. Cryst. 42, 339-341.
2. Sheldrick, G.M. (2008). Acta Cryst. A64, 112-122.
3. Sheldrick, G.M. (2015). Acta Cryst. C71, 3-8.

Crystal structure determination of [a20180240_JMM199]

Crystal Data for C₁₀₈H₁₂₂N₄Si₆ (*M* = 1644.63 g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), *a* = 9.8868(7) Å, *b* = 14.5757(6) Å, *c* = 16.8086(13) Å, α = 92.729(5)°, β = 91.415(6)°, γ = 90.226(4)°, *V* = 2418.7(3) Å³, *Z* = 1, *T* = 150.00(10) K, μ (CuK α) = 1.164 mm⁻¹, *D*_{calc} = 1.129 g/cm³, 17000 reflections measured (7.846° ≤ 2 θ ≤ 137.976°), 8946 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0667, *R*_{sigma} = 0.1116) which were used in all calculations. The final *R*₁ was 0.0618 (*I* > 2 σ (*I*)) and *wR*₂ was 0.1544 (all data).

Refinement model description

Number of restraints - 14, number of constraints - unknown.

Details:

1. Fixed Uiso
At 1.2 times of:
All C(H) groups, All C(H,H) groups
At 1.5 times of:
All C(H,H,H) groups
2. Restrained distances
C17-C19B = C19-C17
1.54 with sigma of 0.01
3. Uiso/Uanis restraints and constraints
Uanis(C19B) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002
Uanis(C19) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C19B) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.015 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.03
4. Others
Fixed Sof: H17(0.45) H17A(0.55) C19(0.55) H19A(0.55) H19B(0.55) H19C(0.55)
C19B(0.45) H19D(0.45) H19E(0.45) H19F(0.45)
- 5.a Ternary CH refined with riding coordinates:
C17(H17), C17(H17A), C20(H20), C23(H23), C28(H28), C31(H31), C34(H34)
- 5.b Aromatic/amide H refined with riding coordinates:
C4(H4), C5(H5), C10(H10), C12(H12), C38(H38), C39(H39), C40(H40), C41(H41),
C42(H42), C44(H44), C45(H45), C46(H46), C47(H47), C48(H48), C50(H50),
C51(H51),
C52(H52), C53(H53), C54(H54)
- 5.c Idealised Me refined as rotating group:
C18(H18A,H18B,H18C), C19(H19A,H19B,H19C), C19B(H19D,H19E,H19F),
C21(H21A,H21B),
H21C), C22(H22A,H22B,H22C), C24(H24A,H24B,H24C), C25(H25A,H25B,H25C),
C29(H29A,
H29B,H29C), C30(H30A,H30B,H30C), C32(H32A,H32B,H32C), C33(H33A,H33B,H33C),
C35(H35A,H35B,H35C), C36(H36A,H36B,H36C)

This report has been created with Olex2, compiled on 2018.05.29 svn.r3508 for OlexSys. Please [let us know](#) if there are any errors or if you would like to have additional features.

X-Ray Data Compound 5

SERVICIO GENERAL RAYOS X Unidad de Moléculas y Materiales

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a201801852_jmm182

Comentario:

El usuario envió una muestra del compuesto **JMM182** (prismas amarillos) para determinar su estructura molecular. Se selecciona uno de ellos de tamaño aproximado $0.616 \times 0.226 \times 0.051 \text{ mm}^3$ para realizar la toma de datos.

Se confirma la estructura molecular coincidente con la propuesta por el usuario. La estructura cristalina determinada es centrosimétrica (grupo espacial $P2_1/n$).

Table 1 Crystal data and structure refinement for a201801852_jmm182.

Identification code	a201801852_jmm182
Empirical formula	$C_{151}H_{106}N_4Si_6$
Formula weight	2144.93
Temperature/K	150.00(10)
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/n$
a/Å	18.8903(2)
b/Å	13.9779(2)
c/Å	43.9341(8)
$\alpha/^\circ$	90.0
$\beta/^\circ$	96.0313(15)
$\gamma/^\circ$	90.0
Volume/Å ³	11536.4(3)
Z	4
$\rho_{\text{calc}}/\text{g/cm}^3$	1.235
μ/mm^{-1}	1.120
F(000)	4496.0
Crystal size/mm ³	$0.616 \times 0.226 \times 0.051$
Radiation	$\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54184$)
2 Θ range for data collection/ $^\circ$	6.64 to 137.998
Index ranges	$-22 \leq h \leq 22$, $-12 \leq k \leq 16$, $-53 \leq l \leq 53$
Reflections collected	92397
Independent reflections	21438 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0720$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0501$]
Data/restraints/parameters	21438/361/1625
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.252
Final R indexes [$I \geq 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.1071$, $wR_2 = 0.3057$

Final R indexes [all data] $R_1 = 0.1439$, $wR_2 = 0.3523$

Largest diff. peak/hole / $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$ 2.05/-0.58

[a] Esquema de pesado: $1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2)+(0.2000P)^2]$ donde $P = [\text{Max}(F_o^2,0)+2F_c^2]/3$.

[b] Expresión de extinción secundaria tipo SHELXL: $F_c^* = kF_c[1+0.001F_c^2\lambda^3/\text{sen}(2\theta)]^{-1/4}$

Table 2 Fractional Atomic Coordinates ($\times 10^4$) and Equivalent Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for a201801852_jmm182. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} tensor.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
Si1	989.5 (7)	2627.4 (11)	1589.5 (3)	62.1 (4)
Si2	6640.3 (7)	1723.4 (10)	914.9 (3)	58.9 (3)
Si3	7888.0 (6)	2423.7 (11)	2451.1 (3)	58.3 (3)
Si4	9425.5 (7)	1175.2 (12)	3966.7 (4)	68.1 (4)
Si5	3959.9 (8)	2873.3 (11)	4709.0 (3)	64.4 (4)
Si6	2541.3 (5)	1674.3 (8)	3139.9 (3)	46.8 (3)
N1	5179.8 (18)	2061 (3)	1912.9 (8)	49.7 (8)
N2	6639.2 (19)	1763 (3)	3496.1 (9)	52.2 (8)
N3	5266.6 (19)	1929 (3)	3682.2 (8)	50.8 (8)
N4	3799.7 (17)	2128 (3)	2092.7 (8)	47.2 (7)
C1	3323 (2)	2309 (3)	1566.0 (11)	54.5 (10)
C16	6362 (3)	1945 (4)	4417.2 (11)	63.2 (12)
C28B	2396 (6)	1652 (7)	3775 (2)	68 (3)
C32B	2780 (6)	176 (8)	3589 (3)	74 (3)
C31B	2796 (7)	-234 (9)	3876 (3)	83 (3)
C29B	2430 (6)	1248 (7)	4067 (2)	69 (3)
C15B	3435 (6)	1843 (6)	4816 (3)	70 (3)
C20B	2716 (6)	1926 (9)	4855 (3)	92 (4)
C19B	2345 (6)	1141 (11)	4949 (3)	92 (4)
C18B	2692 (9)	272 (9)	5006 (2)	85 (4)
C17B	3410 (9)	189 (6)	4968 (3)	100 (4)
C16B	3782 (7)	974 (7)	4873 (3)	92 (4)
C2	3447 (3)	2349 (4)	1263.1 (12)	66.0 (13)
C3	4133 (3)	2285 (4)	1175.2 (12)	69.3 (13)
C4	4718 (3)	2181 (4)	1385.7 (11)	60.1 (11)
C04A	8308 (6)	-272 (8)	2124 (3)	90 (3)
C5	4612 (2)	2136 (3)	1702.6 (10)	50.0 (9)
C6	5069 (2)	2033 (3)	2205.9 (10)	44.9 (8)
C6CA	7817 (6)	3073 (9)	2091 (2)	57 (3)
C78B	8237 (7)	2846 (10)	1860 (2)	79 (4)
C77B	8281 (8)	3474 (11)	1617 (2)	96 (5)
C76B	7904 (8)	4329 (11)	1605 (2)	72 (4)
C75B	7483 (7)	4556 (9)	1836 (3)	95 (5)
C74B	7439 (6)	3928 (10)	2079 (3)	85 (4)
C7	5688 (2)	2026 (3)	2438.7 (10)	46.7 (9)
C8	6377 (2)	2128 (4)	2354.5 (10)	53.0 (10)
C9	6967 (2)	2164 (3)	2570.3 (10)	53.3 (10)

C10	6855 (2)	2034 (3)	2878.1 (10)	52.1 (10)
C11	6177 (2)	1919 (3)	2969.0 (10)	48.2 (9)
C12	6073 (2)	1839 (3)	3294.2 (10)	49.2 (9)
C13	6539 (2)	1777 (3)	3798.1 (10)	52.5 (10)
C14	7138 (2)	1714 (4)	4019.5 (11)	59.2 (11)
C15	7037 (3)	1795 (4)	4324.0 (12)	64.8 (12)
C17	5772 (3)	2017 (4)	4209.3 (11)	58.0 (11)
C18	5843 (2)	1909 (3)	3889.8 (10)	52.6 (10)
C19	5373 (2)	1868 (3)	3387.3 (10)	48.7 (9)
C20	4759 (2)	1859 (3)	3156.1 (10)	45.7 (9)
C21	4070 (2)	1789 (3)	3242.2 (10)	48.7 (9)
C22	3472 (2)	1780 (3)	3023.8 (10)	47.3 (9)
C23	3582 (2)	1859 (3)	2715.9 (10)	47.5 (9)
C24	4261 (2)	1935 (3)	2621.9 (9)	44.0 (8)
C25	4363 (2)	2032 (3)	2296.3 (10)	45.4 (8)
C26	3909 (2)	2202 (3)	1795.7 (10)	48.9 (9)
C27	5582 (2)	1946 (3)	2749.4 (10)	44.2 (8)
C28	4862 (2)	1910 (3)	2843.8 (10)	43.9 (8)
C29	2597 (2)	2385 (4)	1633.5 (11)	58.4 (11)
C30	1962 (3)	2455 (4)	1636.7 (13)	67.8 (13)
C31	5413 (3)	2104 (4)	1285.8 (12)	66.6 (13)
C32	5946 (3)	2026 (5)	1160.2 (11)	69.2 (13)
C33	7846 (3)	1577 (4)	3939.9 (11)	63.4 (12)
C34	8465 (3)	1443 (4)	3917.3 (13)	67.0 (12)
C35	5112 (3)	2255 (4)	4324.2 (11)	60.5 (11)
C36	4631 (3)	2482 (4)	4463.2 (12)	68.5 (13)
C37	740 (3)	3325 (4)	1925.2 (15)	74.1 (14)
C38	1214 (3)	3563 (4)	2162.8 (14)	75.6 (14)
C39	1016 (5)	4087 (5)	2414.3 (18)	103 (2)
C40	342 (5)	4376 (6)	2417.2 (18)	105 (3)
C41	-160 (4)	4233 (7)	2164 (2)	110 (3)
C42	39 (4)	3726 (7)	1920 (2)	109 (3)
C43	544 (3)	1423 (4)	1544.1 (11)	62.6 (12)
C44	-208 (3)	1387 (5)	1498.3 (17)	82.4 (17)
C45	-562 (4)	522 (5)	1454 (2)	95 (2)
C046	7975 (5)	565 (7)	2194 (2)	76 (3)
C46	-184 (4)	-311 (5)	1450.1 (16)	91.5 (19)
C47	542 (4)	-291 (6)	1493.0 (18)	100 (2)
C48	897 (3)	577 (5)	1542.5 (17)	85.6 (18)
C49	733 (3)	3328 (4)	1232.1 (13)	65.2 (12)
C50	609 (5)	4299 (6)	1233.5 (19)	111 (3)
C51	426 (6)	4809 (6)	970 (2)	124 (3)
C52	355 (4)	4350 (6)	695.4 (18)	97 (2)
C53	479 (3)	3382 (5)	680.5 (15)	83.5 (17)
C54	666 (3)	2873 (4)	947.6 (13)	69.5 (13)

C55	6159 (3)	1527 (4)	525.1 (12)	66.4 (12)
C56	5460 (3)	1246 (4)	483.8 (13)	69.8 (13)
C57	5099 (3)	1105 (5)	192.5 (15)	83.2 (17)
C58	5467 (4)	1256 (6)	-60.8 (15)	94 (2)
C59	6165 (4)	1509 (6)	-21.3 (15)	94 (2)
C60	6514 (3)	1660 (5)	265.0 (13)	81.3 (16)
C61	7079 (3)	599 (5)	1073.9 (16)	78.0 (15)
C62	7526 (4)	86 (5)	914.4 (18)	96 (2)
C63	7864 (5)	-750 (6)	1036 (2)	108 (2)
C64	7699 (5)	-1014 (7)	1311 (2)	118 (3)
C65	7287 (6)	-524 (8)	1480 (3)	133 (3)
C66	6952 (5)	272 (7)	1354 (2)	112 (2)
C67	7310 (3)	2680 (4)	886.9 (11)	62.1 (12)
C68	8043 (3)	2489 (5)	908.3 (15)	75.2 (14)
C69	8527 (3)	3205 (5)	855.9 (17)	86.5 (18)
C70	8288 (3)	4123 (5)	789.3 (15)	80.1 (16)
C71	7579 (3)	4314 (4)	771.5 (15)	76.3 (15)
C72	7096 (3)	3608 (4)	816.8 (12)	68.8 (13)
C73B	7750 (4)	3321 (6)	2113.3 (13)	52 (2)
C78	8108 (4)	3146 (7)	1858.4 (15)	55 (3)
C77	8069 (5)	3803 (7)	1619.9 (13)	65 (3)
C76	7672 (6)	4635 (7)	1636.3 (15)	65 (3)
C75	7314 (5)	4810 (6)	1891.2 (19)	74 (3)
C74	7352 (4)	4153 (6)	2129.7 (16)	69 (3)
C79	8339 (2)	1286 (3)	2364.8 (11)	67.3 (13)
C80B	7987 (4)	415 (4)	2375 (3)	101 (6)
C81B	8321 (5)	-424 (4)	2299 (4)	137 (9)
C82	9008 (4)	-392 (4)	2212.2 (17)	102 (2)
C83	9360 (4)	479 (5)	2202 (3)	108 (7)
C84	9025 (4)	1318 (4)	2278 (3)	103 (6)
C83B	9339 (8)	182 (10)	2401 (4)	107 (4)
C84B	9024 (7)	1051 (9)	2483 (3)	95 (3)
C85	8440 (3)	3090 (4)	2765.2 (12)	63.3 (12)
C86	8556 (3)	4080 (4)	2746.7 (14)	72.2 (14)
C87	8960 (3)	4574 (5)	2974.3 (17)	86.5 (17)
C88	9259 (4)	4070 (6)	3227.0 (19)	101 (2)
C89	9162 (5)	3109 (6)	3245.6 (19)	115 (3)
C90	8743 (4)	2621 (5)	3021.2 (16)	86.8 (18)
C91	9690 (3)	574 (4)	3619.6 (15)	74.2 (15)
C92	9282 (4)	-179 (6)	3495.6 (19)	97 (2)
C93	9455 (4)	-676 (6)	3242 (2)	110 (3)
C94	9939 (9)	-436 (11)	3063 (4)	77 (4)
C94B	10195 (8)	-446 (9)	3167 (4)	80 (4)
C95	10318 (9)	345 (12)	3170 (4)	86 (5)
C95B	10612 (11)	147 (13)	3311 (5)	113 (5)

C96	10163 (8)	869 (10)	3428 (4)	71 (4)
C96B	10413 (10)	675 (11)	3557 (4)	100 (5)
C97	9901 (3)	2334 (5)	4045.3 (13)	72.1 (14)
C98	10641 (3)	2364 (5)	4108.5 (15)	81.2 (16)
C99	10990 (4)	3216 (6)	4142.7 (16)	92 (2)
C100	10611 (4)	4074 (6)	4119.4 (16)	91.1 (19)
C101	9899 (4)	4046 (5)	4066.1 (16)	88.2 (18)
C102	9544 (3)	3215 (5)	4030.9 (14)	78.5 (15)
C103	9538 (3)	314 (5)	4292.2 (15)	77.9 (16)
C104	9868 (3)	-563 (5)	4267.9 (18)	88.0 (18)
C105	9879 (4)	-1219 (6)	4501 (2)	102 (2)
C106	9578 (4)	-1049 (6)	4754 (2)	99 (2)
C107	9241 (4)	-169 (7)	4791.6 (18)	105 (3)
C108	9215 (3)	508 (6)	4558.4 (15)	88.3 (18)
C109	4431 (3)	3474 (4)	5054.5 (12)	67.3 (12)
C110	5130 (3)	3787 (4)	5069.4 (14)	74.2 (14)
C111	5451 (3)	4247 (5)	5326.5 (17)	84.7 (17)
C112	5074 (4)	4402 (5)	5574.7 (16)	88.5 (18)
C113	4401 (4)	4124 (6)	5566.2 (15)	103 (2)
C114	4066 (4)	3650 (6)	5306.5 (15)	93 (2)
C115	3544 (6)	1713 (7)	4852 (3)	55 (4)
C120	2820 (5)	1677 (9)	4882 (2)	55 (4)
C119	2516 (6)	834 (11)	4975 (2)	64 (4)
C118	2936 (9)	28 (9)	5038 (3)	67 (4)
C117	3661 (9)	64 (7)	5008 (3)	78 (5)
C116	3965 (6)	907 (7)	4915 (3)	74 (4)
C121	3338 (3)	3704 (4)	4480.1 (13)	67.4 (12)
C122	2866 (3)	4296 (5)	4612.8 (17)	86.5 (18)
C123	2422 (3)	4935 (5)	4438 (2)	99 (2)
C124	2436 (4)	4982 (5)	4132 (2)	100 (2)
C125	2883 (4)	4388 (6)	3992.3 (19)	102 (2)
C126	3335 (3)	3771 (5)	4165.9 (15)	81.5 (16)
C127	2546 (2)	1111 (3)	3530.6 (8)	52.9 (10)
C128	2807 (5)	1650 (3)	3783.9 (11)	63 (3)
C129	2800 (5)	1276 (5)	4076.7 (9)	84 (4)
C130	2533 (4)	363 (5)	4116.2 (9)	97 (2)
C131	2272 (5)	-176 (4)	3863.0 (13)	112 (6)
C132	2279 (5)	198 (4)	3570.2 (11)	83 (4)
C133	2162 (2)	2909 (3)	3171.5 (10)	53.5 (10)
C4B	2523 (3)	3679 (4)	3061 (2)	71 (4)
C5B	2282 (5)	4606 (3)	3098 (2)	75 (3)
C6B	1679 (6)	4764 (4)	3247.5 (19)	81 (4)
C7B	1317 (6)	3994 (6)	3358 (2)	86 (3)
C8B	1558 (4)	3067 (5)	3320 (2)	67 (3)
C134	2494 (6)	3766 (8)	3125 (4)	41 (3)

C135	2111 (9)	4680 (9)	3163 (4)	57 (4)
C136	1450 (11)	4621 (12)	3239 (4)	66 (4)
C137	1102 (9)	3803 (11)	3258 (4)	67 (4)
C138	1426 (7)	2958 (9)	3210 (4)	55 (3)
C139	2013 (2)	954 (3)	2838.0 (10)	53.7 (10)
C140	2101 (3)	-32 (4)	2815.3 (15)	78.6 (15)
C141	1714 (4)	-571 (5)	2596.4 (16)	86.9 (17)
C142	1256 (3)	-122 (5)	2379.8 (15)	86.3 (18)
C143	1165 (5)	845 (6)	2389.4 (17)	108 (3)
C144	1543 (4)	1365 (5)	2620.2 (15)	86.2 (18)
C1E	8063 (5)	3011 (6)	4957.4 (18)	99 (2)
C2D	8441 (4)	2354 (6)	5138.8 (19)	96 (2)
C3D	8150 (5)	1888 (6)	5374.0 (19)	102 (2)
C4D	7458 (4)	2069 (6)	5426 (2)	103 (2)
C5D	7084 (5)	2717 (6)	5242 (2)	105 (2)
C6D	7377 (5)	3192 (6)	5015 (2)	101 (2)
C7D	8378 (5)	3513 (8)	4707 (2)	127 (3)

Table 3 Anisotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$) for a201801852_jmm182. The Anisotropic displacement factor exponent takes the form: - $2\pi^2[h^2a^2U_{11}+2hka*b*U_{12}+\dots]$.

Atom	U ₁₁	U ₂₂	U ₃₃	U ₂₃	U ₁₃	U ₁₂
Si1	39.5 (6)	91.4 (9)	55.3 (7)	-3.5 (6)	4.5 (5)	0.7 (6)
Si2	48.0 (6)	78.2 (8)	51.9 (7)	0.1 (6)	12.3 (5)	-0.1 (5)
Si3	37.7 (6)	90.6 (9)	47.9 (6)	3.9 (6)	10.5 (5)	-4.5 (5)
Si4	47.1 (7)	84.5 (9)	73.1 (9)	13.8 (7)	7.7 (6)	-1.0 (6)
Si5	60.2 (8)	83.4 (9)	52.4 (7)	-1.0 (6)	19.9 (6)	2.5 (6)
Si6	35.1 (5)	59.6 (6)	47.7 (6)	2.5 (5)	13.6 (4)	0.4 (4)
N1	37.7 (17)	68 (2)	44.7 (18)	1.6 (16)	10.2 (14)	-0.5 (15)
N2	42.8 (18)	69 (2)	46.8 (19)	-1.6 (16)	11.3 (15)	-0.9 (15)
N3	45.2 (18)	62 (2)	46.7 (19)	-0.3 (15)	11.3 (15)	0.5 (15)
N4	34.7 (16)	62 (2)	46.4 (18)	2.0 (15)	8.9 (14)	0.7 (14)
C1	45 (2)	68 (3)	51 (2)	5 (2)	7.9 (18)	-4.7 (19)
C16	67 (3)	79 (3)	45 (2)	-3 (2)	9 (2)	4 (2)
C28B	69 (3)	68 (3)	67 (3)	0.2 (10)	7.7 (10)	0.8 (10)
C32B	74 (3)	74 (3)	73 (3)	0.1 (10)	8.1 (11)	1.0 (10)
C31B	83 (3)	83 (3)	83 (3)	0.7 (10)	9.1 (11)	0.8 (10)
C29B	70 (3)	70 (3)	68 (3)	-0.2 (10)	7.7 (10)	1.1 (10)
C15B	70 (3)	71 (3)	69 (3)	0.3 (10)	8.5 (11)	0.5 (10)
C20B	92 (4)	92 (4)	92 (4)	0.5 (10)	10.6 (11)	0.2 (10)
C19B	92 (4)	92 (4)	92 (4)	0.1 (10)	10.5 (11)	0.1 (10)
C18B	85 (4)	85 (4)	84 (4)	0.6 (10)	9.7 (11)	0.0 (10)
C17B	100 (4)	100 (4)	100 (4)	0.0 (10)	10.5 (11)	0.1 (10)
C16B	91 (4)	92 (4)	91 (4)	0.5 (10)	10.2 (11)	-0.4 (10)

C2	47 (2)	97 (4)	54 (3)	5 (2)	5 (2)	-5 (2)
C3	52 (3)	108 (4)	50 (3)	3 (3)	14 (2)	-5 (3)
C4	48 (2)	85 (3)	48 (2)	1 (2)	12.2 (19)	-5 (2)
C04A	90 (3)	89 (3)	90 (3)	0.0 (10)	10.5 (11)	-0.4 (10)
C5	38 (2)	66 (3)	47 (2)	0.6 (18)	8.8 (17)	-2.0 (17)
C6	33.7 (18)	55 (2)	47 (2)	2.3 (17)	9.1 (16)	-1.8 (15)
C6CA	56 (3)	57 (3)	57 (3)	-0.1 (10)	6.3 (11)	-0.6 (10)
C78B	79 (4)	80 (4)	79 (4)	0.4 (10)	9.1 (11)	0.1 (10)
C77B	96 (5)	96 (5)	95 (5)	0.5 (10)	10.3 (11)	0.0 (10)
C76B	73 (4)	72 (4)	73 (4)	0.5 (10)	7.8 (11)	0.1 (10)
C75B	95 (5)	95 (5)	95 (5)	0.0 (10)	9.8 (11)	0.1 (10)
C74B	85 (4)	85 (4)	85 (4)	0.3 (10)	8.9 (11)	0.2 (10)
C7	35.6 (19)	61 (2)	45 (2)	0.1 (17)	8.9 (16)	-0.6 (16)
C8	37 (2)	78 (3)	45 (2)	2.8 (19)	11.9 (17)	-1.6 (18)
C9	37 (2)	77 (3)	46 (2)	1 (2)	10.9 (17)	0.0 (18)
C10	34.8 (19)	75 (3)	48 (2)	-1 (2)	8.1 (16)	-0.9 (18)
C11	37.3 (19)	61 (2)	48 (2)	-0.5 (18)	10.0 (16)	-3.7 (16)
C12	39 (2)	59 (2)	50 (2)	-4.1 (18)	10.0 (17)	-1.3 (16)
C13	47 (2)	63 (3)	48 (2)	-5.4 (19)	8.6 (18)	-0.4 (18)
C14	48 (2)	80 (3)	50 (2)	0 (2)	5.0 (19)	-2 (2)
C15	56 (3)	88 (3)	50 (3)	-2 (2)	2 (2)	4 (2)
C17	53 (2)	70 (3)	53 (2)	-2 (2)	16 (2)	2 (2)
C18	46 (2)	64 (3)	49 (2)	-1.6 (19)	11.7 (18)	-1.1 (18)
C19	43 (2)	58 (2)	46 (2)	0.8 (17)	10.7 (17)	0.5 (17)
C20	38.2 (19)	54 (2)	47 (2)	-0.5 (17)	11.5 (16)	-0.8 (15)
C21	41 (2)	64 (2)	43 (2)	1.0 (18)	13.3 (16)	0.3 (17)
C22	36.2 (19)	61 (2)	47 (2)	0.0 (17)	13.2 (16)	-0.7 (16)
C23	37.3 (19)	57 (2)	50 (2)	0.0 (17)	11.2 (16)	-0.9 (16)
C24	33.9 (18)	54 (2)	46 (2)	-0.2 (16)	12.5 (16)	-1.1 (15)
C25	36.9 (19)	54 (2)	47 (2)	-4.2 (17)	8.8 (16)	-4.0 (15)
C26	41 (2)	56 (2)	51 (2)	6.1 (18)	11.3 (17)	-1.2 (16)
C27	33.1 (18)	54 (2)	47 (2)	-1.0 (17)	13.0 (16)	-1.1 (15)
C28	32.8 (18)	52 (2)	49 (2)	0.4 (16)	12.6 (16)	-2.6 (14)
C29	42 (2)	78 (3)	55 (2)	12 (2)	2.8 (18)	-4 (2)
C30	44 (2)	98 (4)	62 (3)	9 (3)	7 (2)	5 (2)
C31	52 (3)	101 (4)	48 (2)	-2 (2)	9 (2)	-2 (2)
C32	54 (3)	109 (4)	46 (2)	0 (2)	12 (2)	-3 (3)
C33	52 (3)	88 (3)	50 (2)	0 (2)	2 (2)	-2 (2)
C34	49 (3)	91 (4)	62 (3)	-1 (3)	7 (2)	1 (2)
C35	64 (3)	73 (3)	47 (2)	2 (2)	16 (2)	0 (2)
C36	70 (3)	87 (3)	52 (3)	5 (2)	19 (2)	10 (3)
C37	57 (3)	89 (4)	77 (4)	-12 (3)	14 (3)	-17 (3)
C38	73 (3)	75 (3)	76 (4)	-11 (3)	-4 (3)	1 (3)
C39	121 (6)	86 (4)	94 (5)	-27 (4)	-27 (4)	18 (4)
C40	132 (7)	102 (5)	89 (5)	-27 (4)	51 (5)	-26 (5)

C41	76 (4)	138 (7)	120 (6)	-43 (5)	31 (4)	-1 (4)
C42	64 (4)	152 (7)	111 (6)	-47 (5)	9 (4)	2 (4)
C43	50 (2)	87 (3)	51 (2)	1 (2)	8 (2)	2 (2)
C44	56 (3)	85 (4)	107 (5)	11 (3)	13 (3)	-2 (3)
C45	66 (4)	95 (5)	126 (6)	12 (4)	15 (4)	-8 (3)
C046	75 (3)	76 (3)	77 (3)	0.0 (10)	8.8 (10)	-0.2 (10)
C46	105 (5)	87 (4)	81 (4)	-6 (3)	6 (4)	-11 (4)
C47	102 (5)	101 (5)	96 (5)	-8 (4)	10 (4)	27 (4)
C48	63 (3)	98 (4)	95 (5)	-24 (4)	2 (3)	10 (3)
C49	46 (2)	83 (3)	65 (3)	-5 (2)	-1 (2)	9 (2)
C50	139 (7)	95 (5)	92 (5)	-11 (4)	-20 (5)	39 (5)
C51	162 (8)	95 (5)	108 (6)	2 (5)	-12 (6)	53 (5)
C52	90 (5)	118 (6)	84 (4)	24 (4)	8 (4)	18 (4)
C53	79 (4)	103 (5)	69 (4)	16 (3)	12 (3)	3 (3)
C54	66 (3)	79 (3)	64 (3)	3 (3)	12 (2)	0 (2)
C55	60 (3)	81 (3)	60 (3)	-3 (2)	13 (2)	-1 (2)
C56	67 (3)	78 (3)	65 (3)	-3 (3)	11 (2)	0 (2)
C57	67 (3)	102 (4)	80 (4)	-18 (3)	5 (3)	-9 (3)
C58	90 (4)	123 (5)	65 (4)	-19 (4)	-4 (3)	-5 (4)
C59	83 (4)	142 (6)	60 (3)	-11 (4)	19 (3)	-9 (4)
C60	67 (3)	121 (5)	57 (3)	-7 (3)	15 (3)	-4 (3)
C61	60 (3)	87 (4)	85 (4)	1 (3)	1 (3)	-3 (3)
C62	101 (5)	93 (4)	90 (5)	-14 (4)	-4 (4)	16 (4)
C63	109 (2)	108 (2)	108 (2)	-1.4 (10)	10.3 (10)	0.4 (10)
C64	118 (3)	117 (3)	118 (3)	0.3 (10)	12.9 (11)	0.8 (10)
C65	133 (3)	133 (3)	133 (3)	0.9 (10)	14.2 (11)	1.4 (10)
C66	113 (3)	112 (3)	112 (3)	1.7 (10)	12.6 (10)	1.4 (10)
C67	52 (2)	84 (3)	52 (3)	-4 (2)	14 (2)	1 (2)
C68	56 (3)	86 (4)	84 (4)	7 (3)	11 (3)	1 (3)
C69	57 (3)	108 (5)	98 (5)	14 (4)	21 (3)	-8 (3)
C70	79 (4)	88 (4)	76 (4)	3 (3)	18 (3)	-15 (3)
C71	80 (4)	73 (3)	76 (4)	2 (3)	14 (3)	0 (3)
C72	62 (3)	84 (3)	61 (3)	-3 (3)	10 (2)	4 (2)
C73B	52 (3)	52 (3)	52 (3)	-0.5 (10)	6.2 (10)	-0.6 (10)
C78	55 (3)	56 (3)	55 (3)	1.3 (10)	7.3 (10)	-0.5 (10)
C77	65 (3)	65 (3)	65 (3)	0.1 (10)	7.5 (11)	0.6 (10)
C76	65 (3)	65 (3)	65 (3)	0.1 (10)	6.8 (10)	-0.3 (10)
C75	74 (3)	74 (3)	74 (3)	0.0 (10)	7.2 (11)	-0.1 (10)
C74	69 (3)	70 (3)	69 (3)	0.2 (10)	7.1 (11)	0.1 (10)
C79	48 (2)	100 (4)	56 (3)	1 (3)	18 (2)	5 (2)
C80B	101 (6)	101 (6)	101 (6)	-0.2 (10)	10.4 (12)	0.1 (10)
C81B	137 (9)	137 (9)	137 (9)	-0.1 (10)	14.3 (14)	0.2 (10)
C82	106 (5)	113 (5)	93 (5)	0 (4)	31 (4)	31 (4)
C83	108 (7)	108 (7)	108 (7)	0.0 (10)	11.4 (12)	0.4 (10)
C84	103 (6)	103 (6)	103 (6)	0.2 (10)	11.0 (12)	0.2 (10)

C83B	107 (4)	107 (4)	108 (4)	-0.3 (10)	11.6 (11)	0.9 (10)
C84B	95 (4)	96 (4)	96 (4)	-0.8 (10)	10.1 (11)	1.1 (10)
C85	45 (2)	86 (3)	58 (3)	7 (2)	5 (2)	-2 (2)
C86	56 (3)	90 (4)	71 (3)	5 (3)	8 (2)	-10 (3)
C87	67 (3)	91 (4)	102 (5)	0 (4)	10 (3)	-14 (3)
C88	99 (5)	100 (5)	95 (5)	-4 (4)	-24 (4)	-15 (4)
C89	143 (7)	99 (5)	91 (5)	4 (4)	-46 (5)	-12 (5)
C90	94 (4)	82 (4)	80 (4)	6 (3)	-14 (3)	-6 (3)
C91	62 (3)	73 (3)	90 (4)	15 (3)	20 (3)	4 (2)
C92	66 (4)	123 (6)	106 (5)	-2 (4)	27 (4)	9 (4)
C93	92 (5)	100 (5)	146 (8)	-26 (5)	43 (5)	4 (4)
C94	77 (4)	77 (4)	77 (4)	-0.2 (10)	8.5 (11)	-0.1 (10)
C94B	79 (4)	80 (4)	79 (4)	-0.4 (10)	8.9 (11)	0.6 (10)
C95	86 (5)	86 (5)	86 (5)	0.3 (10)	9.8 (11)	-0.1 (10)
C95B	112 (5)	113 (5)	113 (5)	0.1 (10)	12.4 (12)	-0.2 (10)
C96	70 (4)	71 (4)	71 (4)	0.3 (10)	8.3 (11)	-0.5 (10)
C96B	100 (5)	101 (5)	100 (5)	0.2 (10)	11.0 (11)	-0.4 (10)
C97	58 (3)	94 (4)	65 (3)	10 (3)	7 (2)	-8 (3)
C98	67 (3)	105 (4)	72 (4)	7 (3)	5 (3)	-5 (3)
C99	74 (4)	128 (6)	75 (4)	-5 (4)	10 (3)	-30 (4)
C100	97 (5)	99 (5)	78 (4)	-11 (3)	14 (4)	-18 (4)
C101	99 (5)	86 (4)	78 (4)	-8 (3)	2 (3)	-6 (3)
C102	72 (3)	95 (4)	69 (3)	3 (3)	7 (3)	-3 (3)
C103	54 (3)	95 (4)	82 (4)	20 (3)	-1 (3)	-12 (3)
C104	64 (3)	103 (5)	94 (5)	21 (4)	-6 (3)	-1 (3)
C105	84 (4)	109 (5)	107 (6)	36 (4)	-13 (4)	-6 (4)
C106	89 (5)	101 (5)	100 (5)	35 (4)	-19 (4)	-20 (4)
C107	85 (4)	149 (7)	78 (4)	21 (4)	0 (3)	-35 (5)
C108	67 (3)	120 (5)	76 (4)	18 (4)	0 (3)	-15 (3)
C109	64 (3)	85 (3)	55 (3)	4 (2)	13 (2)	0 (2)
C110	63 (3)	84 (4)	76 (4)	9 (3)	9 (3)	1 (3)
C111	64 (3)	86 (4)	102 (5)	6 (3)	-3 (3)	-4 (3)
C112	90 (4)	97 (4)	75 (4)	-1 (3)	-4 (3)	-11 (3)
C113	102 (5)	152 (7)	58 (3)	-20 (4)	19 (3)	-30 (5)
C114	91 (4)	130 (6)	61 (3)	-20 (4)	21 (3)	-24 (4)
C115	55 (4)	56 (4)	54 (4)	0.0 (10)	6.9 (11)	0.3 (10)
C120	55 (4)	55 (4)	55 (4)	0.5 (10)	6.8 (11)	0.2 (10)
C119	64 (4)	65 (4)	64 (4)	0.5 (10)	7.6 (11)	0.4 (10)
C118	67 (4)	67 (4)	67 (4)	0.5 (10)	7.6 (11)	-0.4 (10)
C117	78 (5)	78 (5)	78 (5)	0.3 (10)	8.3 (11)	0.2 (10)
C116	73 (4)	74 (4)	73 (4)	0.7 (10)	8.1 (11)	-0.2 (10)
C121	58 (3)	76 (3)	69 (3)	-10 (3)	10 (2)	-7 (2)
C122	64 (3)	103 (4)	90 (4)	-28 (4)	1 (3)	11 (3)
C123	65 (4)	96 (5)	130 (7)	-40 (4)	-10 (4)	9 (3)
C124	81 (4)	88 (4)	126 (7)	9 (4)	-15 (4)	3 (3)

C125	88 (5)	125 (6)	92 (5)	29 (4)	10 (4)	6 (4)
C126	81 (4)	91 (4)	75 (4)	15 (3)	19 (3)	9 (3)
C127	46 (2)	61 (2)	54 (2)	2.1 (19)	14.6 (18)	5.2 (18)
C128	63 (3)	64 (3)	63 (3)	0.0 (10)	6.5 (11)	-0.9 (10)
C129	84 (4)	84 (4)	83 (4)	0.0 (10)	8.8 (11)	-0.6 (10)
C130	124 (6)	114 (5)	53 (3)	14 (3)	13 (3)	1 (4)
C131	113 (6)	112 (6)	112 (6)	0.6 (10)	11.6 (12)	-0.7 (10)
C132	83 (4)	82 (4)	82 (4)	0.2 (10)	8.4 (11)	-0.5 (10)
C133	47 (2)	60 (2)	54 (2)	2.3 (19)	9.0 (19)	9.8 (18)
C4B	71 (4)	71 (4)	71 (4)	-0.3 (10)	7.4 (11)	-0.5 (10)
C5B	74 (3)	75 (3)	75 (3)	0.0 (10)	8.0 (11)	-0.1 (10)
C6B	81 (4)	81 (4)	82 (4)	-0.1 (10)	7.6 (11)	0.6 (10)
C7B	85 (3)	86 (3)	86 (3)	-1.2 (10)	9.2 (11)	1.1 (10)
C8B	67 (3)	68 (3)	67 (3)	-0.2 (10)	8.1 (11)	0.8 (10)
C134	41 (3)	41 (3)	41 (3)	-0.5 (10)	4.4 (11)	-0.3 (10)
C135	57 (4)	57 (4)	57 (4)	-0.2 (10)	6.2 (11)	-0.4 (10)
C136	66 (4)	66 (4)	67 (4)	-0.4 (10)	6.7 (11)	0.9 (10)
C137	67 (4)	68 (4)	68 (4)	-0.8 (10)	7.5 (11)	0.8 (10)
C138	54 (4)	55 (4)	55 (4)	-0.7 (10)	6.2 (11)	0.3 (10)
C139	43 (2)	70 (3)	50 (2)	-1 (2)	15.8 (18)	-4.5 (18)
C140	86 (4)	71 (3)	75 (4)	-13 (3)	-6 (3)	13 (3)
C141	97 (4)	80 (4)	84 (4)	-19 (3)	7 (4)	0 (3)
C142	75 (4)	109 (5)	73 (4)	-21 (3)	3 (3)	-3 (3)
C143	127 (6)	111 (6)	77 (4)	-4 (4)	-35 (4)	11 (5)
C144	102 (5)	73 (3)	77 (4)	5 (3)	-20 (3)	-3 (3)
C1E	103 (5)	102 (5)	86 (5)	-13 (4)	-19 (4)	-9 (4)
C2D	80 (4)	106 (5)	98 (5)	-1 (4)	-4 (4)	4 (4)
C3D	101 (5)	111 (5)	90 (5)	6 (4)	-14 (4)	-1 (4)
C4D	90 (5)	119 (6)	97 (5)	-6 (4)	0 (4)	-12 (4)
C5D	96 (5)	110 (6)	106 (6)	-32 (5)	-1 (5)	7 (4)
C6D	105 (6)	99 (5)	93 (5)	-16 (4)	-20 (4)	11 (4)
C7D	130 (7)	145 (8)	99 (6)	16 (6)	-23 (5)	-24 (6)

Table 4 Bond Lengths for a201801852_jmm182.

Atom	Atom	Length/Å	Atom	Atom	Length/Å
Si1	C30	1.843 (5)	C53	C54	1.386 (9)
Si1	C37	1.869 (6)	C55	C56	1.371 (8)
Si1	C43	1.883 (6)	C55	C60	1.398 (8)
Si1	C49	1.871 (6)	C56	C57	1.400 (9)
Si2	C32	1.833 (5)	C57	C58	1.389 (10)
Si2	C55	1.873 (6)	C58	C59	1.359 (10)
Si2	C61	1.877 (6)	C59	C60	1.373 (9)
Si2	C67	1.854 (5)	C61	C62	1.357 (9)

Si3	C6CA	1.818 (7)	C61	C66	1.358 (11)
Si3	C9	1.904 (4)	C62	C63	1.410 (11)
Si3	C73B	1.939 (5)	C63	C64	1.333 (12)
Si3	C79	1.861 (4)	C64	C65	1.320 (13)
Si3	C85	1.886 (5)	C65	C66	1.367 (13)
Si4	C34	1.843 (5)	C67	C68	1.404 (7)
Si4	C91	1.855 (7)	C67	C72	1.383 (8)
Si4	C97	1.867 (6)	C68	C69	1.392 (8)
Si4	C103	1.864 (6)	C69	C70	1.381 (9)
Si5	C15B	1.839 (6)	C70	C71	1.360 (9)
Si5	C36	1.833 (5)	C71	C72	1.372 (8)
Si5	C109	1.876 (6)	C73B	C78	1.3900
Si5	C115	1.935 (7)	C73B	C74	1.3900
Si5	C121	1.869 (6)	C78	C77	1.3900
Si6	C22	1.887 (4)	C77	C76	1.3900
Si6	C127	1.888 (3)	C76	C75	1.3900
Si6	C133	1.880 (4)	C75	C74	1.3900
Si6	C139	1.869 (5)	C79	C80B	1.3900
N1	C5	1.344 (6)	C79	C84	1.3900
N1	C6	1.327 (5)	C79	C84B	1.382 (13)
N2	C12	1.320 (6)	C80B	C81B	1.3900
N2	C13	1.360 (6)	C81B	C82	1.3900
N3	C18	1.346 (6)	C82	C83	1.3900
N3	C19	1.334 (6)	C82	C83B	1.269 (15)
N4	C25	1.323 (6)	C83	C84	1.3900
N4	C26	1.346 (6)	C83B	C84B	1.417 (18)
C1	C2	1.376 (7)	C85	C86	1.405 (8)
C1	C26	1.425 (6)	C85	C90	1.373 (8)
C1	C29	1.438 (6)	C86	C87	1.378 (9)
C16	C15	1.395 (7)	C87	C88	1.384 (10)
C16	C17	1.370 (7)	C88	C89	1.359 (11)
C28B	C29B	1.397 (14)	C89	C90	1.378 (10)
C28B	C127	1.367 (11)	C91	C92	1.383 (10)
C32B	C31B	1.383 (16)	C91	C96	1.356 (14)
C32B	C127	1.394 (11)	C91	C96B	1.428 (17)
C31B	C130	1.472 (13)	C92	C93	1.381 (11)
C29B	C130	1.268 (12)	C93	C94	1.312 (16)
C15B	C20B	1.3900	C93	C94B	1.503 (16)
C15B	C16B	1.3900	C94	C95	1.36 (2)
C20B	C19B	1.3900	C94B	C95B	1.26 (2)
C19B	C18B	1.3900	C95	C96	1.41 (2)
C18B	C17B	1.3900	C95B	C96B	1.39 (2)
C17B	C16B	1.3900	C97	C98	1.397 (8)
C2	C3	1.394 (7)	C97	C102	1.402 (9)
C3	C4	1.371 (7)	C98	C99	1.363 (10)

C4	C5	1.428 (6)	C99	C100	1.394 (11)
C4	C31	1.431 (7)	C100	C101	1.342 (10)
C04A	C046	1.379 (15)	C101	C102	1.343 (9)
C04A	C82	1.348 (14)	C103	C104	1.385 (10)
C5	C26	1.433 (6)	C103	C108	1.401 (10)
C6	C7	1.470 (6)	C104	C105	1.373 (10)
C6	C25	1.431 (5)	C105	C106	1.321 (12)
C6CA	C78B	1.3900	C106	C107	1.403 (12)
C6CA	C74B	1.3900	C107	C108	1.392 (10)
C78B	C77B	1.3900	C109	C110	1.384 (8)
C77B	C76B	1.3900	C109	C114	1.387 (8)
C76B	C75B	1.3900	C110	C111	1.383 (9)
C75B	C74B	1.3900	C111	C112	1.380 (10)
C7	C8	1.399 (5)	C112	C113	1.328 (10)
C7	C27	1.405 (6)	C113	C114	1.410 (9)
C8	C9	1.385 (6)	C115	C120	1.3900
C9	C10	1.402 (6)	C115	C116	1.3900
C10	C11	1.391 (6)	C120	C119	1.3900
C11	C12	1.467 (6)	C119	C118	1.3900
C11	C27	1.403 (6)	C118	C117	1.3900
C12	C19	1.426 (6)	C117	C116	1.3900
C13	C14	1.416 (7)	C121	C122	1.389 (8)
C13	C18	1.426 (6)	C121	C126	1.383 (8)
C14	C15	1.376 (7)	C122	C123	1.399 (11)
C14	C33	1.430 (7)	C123	C124	1.350 (12)
C17	C18	1.432 (6)	C124	C125	1.374 (11)
C17	C35	1.431 (7)	C125	C126	1.384 (10)
C19	C20	1.460 (6)	C127	C128	1.3900
C20	C21	1.396 (5)	C127	C132	1.3900
C20	C28	1.408 (6)	C128	C129	1.3900
C21	C22	1.403 (6)	C129	C130	1.3900
C22	C23	1.395 (6)	C130	C131	1.3900
C23	C24	1.392 (5)	C131	C132	1.3900
C24	C25	1.470 (6)	C133	C4B	1.3900
C24	C28	1.417 (6)	C133	C8B	1.3900
C27	C28	1.464 (5)	C133	C134	1.377 (13)
C29	C30	1.205 (7)	C133	C138	1.419 (14)
C31	C32	1.203 (7)	C4B	C5B	1.3900
C33	C34	1.199 (7)	C5B	C6B	1.3900
C35	C36	1.190 (7)	C6B	C7B	1.3900
C37	C38	1.343 (8)	C7B	C8B	1.3900
C37	C42	1.436 (9)	C134	C135	1.49 (2)
C38	C39	1.409 (10)	C135	C136	1.33 (2)
C39	C40	1.336 (11)	C136	C137	1.33 (2)
C40	C41	1.398 (12)	C137	C138	1.357 (19)

C41	C42	1.371 (10)	C139	C140	1.394 (8)
C43	C44	1.416 (7)	C139	C144	1.362 (8)
C43	C48	1.357 (8)	C140	C141	1.371 (9)
C44	C45	1.385 (9)	C141	C142	1.369 (10)
C45	C46	1.367 (10)	C142	C143	1.364 (11)
C046	C79	1.395 (11)	C143	C144	1.384 (10)
C46	C47	1.364 (11)	C1E	C2D	1.367 (11)
C47	C48	1.393 (11)	C1E	C6D	1.371 (12)
C49	C50	1.378 (9)	C1E	C7D	1.482 (12)
C49	C54	1.396 (8)	C2D	C3D	1.384 (11)
C50	C51	1.372 (11)	C3D	C4D	1.373 (12)
C51	C52	1.361 (11)	C4D	C5D	1.361 (12)
C52	C53	1.376 (10)	C5D	C6D	1.363 (12)

Table 5 Bond Angles for a201801852_jmm182.

Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°	Atom	Atom	Atom	Angle/°
C30	Si1	C37	108.1 (3)	C50	C49	Si1	122.7 (5)
C30	Si1	C43	108.9 (3)	C50	C49	C54	116.9 (6)
C30	Si1	C49	109.3 (2)	C54	C49	Si1	120.3 (4)
C37	Si1	C43	113.8 (2)	C51	C50	C49	122.4 (7)
C37	Si1	C49	109.0 (3)	C52	C51	C50	119.7 (7)
C49	Si1	C43	107.8 (2)	C51	C52	C53	120.3 (7)
C32	Si2	C55	105.2 (2)	C52	C53	C54	119.6 (7)
C32	Si2	C61	106.8 (3)	C53	C54	C49	121.1 (6)
C32	Si2	C67	114.1 (3)	C56	C55	Si2	122.1 (4)
C55	Si2	C61	111.8 (3)	C56	C55	C60	117.9 (5)
C67	Si2	C55	108.3 (2)	C60	C55	Si2	119.9 (4)
C67	Si2	C61	110.6 (3)	C55	C56	C57	122.1 (5)
C6CA	Si3	C9	110.4 (4)	C58	C57	C56	118.3 (6)
C6CA	Si3	C79	104.0 (5)	C59	C58	C57	119.9 (6)
C6CA	Si3	C85	112.1 (4)	C58	C59	C60	121.5 (6)
C9	Si3	C73B	106.3 (3)	C59	C60	C55	120.2 (6)
C79	Si3	C9	110.1 (2)	C62	C61	Si2	121.6 (6)
C79	Si3	C73B	115.1 (3)	C62	C61	C66	117.9 (7)
C79	Si3	C85	109.9 (2)	C66	C61	Si2	120.4 (6)
C85	Si3	C9	110.1 (2)	C61	C62	C63	121.6 (8)
C85	Si3	C73B	105.1 (3)	C64	C63	C62	115.7 (9)
C34	Si4	C91	110.0 (3)	C65	C64	C63	125.0 (11)
C34	Si4	C97	107.1 (3)	C64	C65	C66	118.1 (11)
C34	Si4	C103	104.7 (3)	C61	C66	C65	121.5 (9)
C91	Si4	C97	112.3 (3)	C68	C67	Si2	122.2 (4)
C91	Si4	C103	108.6 (3)	C72	C67	Si2	120.4 (4)
C103	Si4	C97	113.8 (3)	C72	C67	C68	117.1 (5)

C15B	Si5	C109	111.5(4)	C69	C68	C67	120.8(6)
C15B	Si5	C121	107.4(5)	C70	C69	C68	119.8(6)
C36	Si5	C15B	110.0(4)	C71	C70	C69	119.6(6)
C36	Si5	C109	108.2(3)	C70	C71	C72	121.0(6)
C36	Si5	C115	105.7(4)	C71	C72	C67	121.7(5)
C36	Si5	C121	107.6(2)	C78	C73B	Si3	117.7(4)
C109	Si5	C115	106.7(4)	C78	C73B	C74	120.0
C121	Si5	C109	112.0(3)	C74	C73B	Si3	122.1(4)
C121	Si5	C115	116.2(4)	C77	C78	C73B	120.0
C22	Si6	C127	111.26(19)	C76	C77	C78	120.0
C133	Si6	C22	108.76(19)	C75	C76	C77	120.0
C133	Si6	C127	106.33(19)	C74	C75	C76	120.0
C139	Si6	C22	107.10(19)	C75	C74	C73B	120.0
C139	Si6	C127	111.8(2)	C046	C79	Si3	121.2(5)
C139	Si6	C133	111.6(2)	C80B	C79	Si3	120.7(3)
C6	N1	C5	118.3(3)	C80B	C79	C84	120.0
C12	N2	C13	117.9(4)	C84	C79	Si3	119.2(3)
C19	N3	C18	117.6(4)	C84B	C79	Si3	123.9(6)
C25	N4	C26	117.9(3)	C84B	C79	C046	114.7(7)
C2	C1	C26	119.4(4)	C81B	C80B	C79	120.0
C2	C1	C29	117.3(4)	C80B	C81B	C82	120.0
C26	C1	C29	123.2(4)	C83	C82	C81B	120.0
C17	C16	C15	121.4(4)	C83B	C82	C04A	120.7(9)
C127	C28B	C29B	120.3(9)	C82	C83	C84	120.0
C31B	C32B	C127	122.1(10)	C83	C84	C79	120.0
C32B	C31B	C130	116.3(10)	C82	C83B	C84B	121.0(13)
C130	C29B	C28B	122.8(9)	C79	C84B	C83B	120.8(11)
C20B	C15B	Si5	121.7(5)	C86	C85	Si3	121.4(4)
C20B	C15B	C16B	120.0	C90	C85	Si3	121.0(5)
C16B	C15B	Si5	118.3(5)	C90	C85	C86	117.6(5)
C19B	C20B	C15B	120.0	C87	C86	C85	121.9(6)
C20B	C19B	C18B	120.0	C86	C87	C88	118.4(7)
C19B	C18B	C17B	120.0	C89	C88	C87	120.3(7)
C16B	C17B	C18B	120.0	C88	C89	C90	121.1(7)
C17B	C16B	C15B	120.0	C85	C90	C89	120.5(7)
C1	C2	C3	121.5(5)	C92	C91	Si4	118.8(5)
C4	C3	C2	121.8(5)	C92	C91	C96B	120.3(8)
C3	C4	C5	118.5(4)	C96	C91	Si4	128.8(7)
C3	C4	C31	120.0(4)	C96	C91	C92	111.3(8)
C5	C4	C31	121.5(4)	C96B	C91	Si4	117.3(8)
C82	C04A	C046	119.8(10)	C93	C92	C91	122.1(7)
N1	C5	C4	119.3(4)	C92	C93	C94B	111.8(9)
N1	C5	C26	120.3(4)	C94	C93	C92	126.5(10)
C4	C5	C26	120.3(4)	C93	C94	C95	111.9(14)
N1	C6	C7	118.7(3)	C95B	C94B	C93	125.2(14)

N1	C6	C25	121.1(4)	C94	C95	C96	123.4(15)
C25	C6	C7	120.2(4)	C94B	C95B	C96B	121.9(17)
C78B	C6CA	Si3	121.7(5)	C91	C96	C95	123.3(12)
C78B	C6CA	C74B	120.0	C95B	C96B	C91	116.0(14)
C74B	C6CA	Si3	116.9(6)	C98	C97	Si4	121.0(5)
C77B	C78B	C6CA	120.0	C98	C97	C102	116.7(6)
C78B	C77B	C76B	120.0	C102	C97	Si4	122.3(4)
C75B	C76B	C77B	120.0	C99	C98	C97	120.8(7)
C76B	C75B	C74B	120.0	C98	C99	C100	120.3(7)
C75B	C74B	C6CA	120.0	C101	C100	C99	119.1(7)
C8	C7	C6	120.7(4)	C100	C101	C102	121.6(7)
C8	C7	C27	119.8(4)	C101	C102	C97	121.5(6)
C27	C7	C6	119.5(3)	C104	C103	Si4	121.9(5)
C9	C8	C7	121.8(4)	C104	C103	C108	118.3(6)
C8	C9	Si3	120.7(3)	C108	C103	Si4	119.4(5)
C8	C9	C10	117.6(4)	C105	C104	C103	120.3(8)
C10	C9	Si3	121.6(3)	C106	C105	C104	122.3(8)
C11	C10	C9	121.9(4)	C105	C106	C107	119.8(7)
C10	C11	C12	120.7(4)	C108	C107	C106	119.4(8)
C10	C11	C27	119.7(4)	C107	C108	C103	119.9(8)
C27	C11	C12	119.5(4)	C110	C109	Si5	123.3(4)
N2	C12	C11	118.6(4)	C110	C109	C114	117.2(6)
N2	C12	C19	121.3(4)	C114	C109	Si5	119.5(5)
C19	C12	C11	120.0(4)	C111	C110	C109	121.3(6)
N2	C13	C14	119.1(4)	C112	C111	C110	120.0(6)
N2	C13	C18	120.3(4)	C113	C112	C111	120.3(7)
C14	C13	C18	120.5(4)	C112	C113	C114	120.4(7)
C13	C14	C33	122.8(4)	C109	C114	C113	120.7(6)
C15	C14	C13	118.7(4)	C120	C115	Si5	119.9(5)
C15	C14	C33	118.5(4)	C120	C115	C116	120.0
C14	C15	C16	121.5(5)	C116	C115	Si5	120.1(5)
C16	C17	C18	119.4(4)	C115	C120	C119	120.0
C16	C17	C35	117.4(4)	C118	C119	C120	120.0
C35	C17	C18	123.1(5)	C119	C118	C117	120.0
N3	C18	C13	121.0(4)	C116	C117	C118	120.0
N3	C18	C17	120.6(4)	C117	C116	C115	120.0
C13	C18	C17	118.4(4)	C122	C121	Si5	122.6(5)
N3	C19	C12	121.3(4)	C126	C121	Si5	121.1(4)
N3	C19	C20	119.1(4)	C126	C121	C122	116.3(6)
C12	C19	C20	119.6(4)	C121	C122	C123	121.6(7)
C21	C20	C19	120.5(4)	C124	C123	C122	120.4(7)
C21	C20	C28	119.8(4)	C123	C124	C125	119.4(7)
C28	C20	C19	119.7(3)	C124	C125	C126	120.2(8)
C20	C21	C22	121.4(4)	C121	C126	C125	122.0(6)
C21	C22	Si6	121.5(3)	C28B	C127	Si6	120.1(5)

C23	C22	Si6	120.4 (3)	C28B C127 C32B	117.5 (7)
C23	C22	C21	118.1 (3)	C32B C127 Si6	121.9 (5)
C24	C23	C22	122.0 (4)	C128 C127 Si6	118.0 (3)
C23	C24	C25	121.0 (4)	C128 C127 C132	120.0
C23	C24	C28	119.3 (4)	C132 C127 Si6	122.0 (3)
C28	C24	C25	119.7 (3)	C129 C128 C127	120.0
N4	C25	C6	121.3 (4)	C130 C129 C128	120.0
N4	C25	C24	119.3 (3)	C29B C130 C31B	119.2 (7)
C6	C25	C24	119.4 (4)	C131 C130 C129	120.0
N4	C26	C1	120.5 (4)	C130 C131 C132	120.0
N4	C26	C5	120.9 (4)	C131 C132 C127	120.0
C1	C26	C5	118.6 (4)	C4B C133 Si6	118.6 (3)
C7	C27	C28	120.6 (4)	C4B C133 C8B	120.0
C11	C27	C7	119.0 (3)	C8B C133 Si6	121.2 (3)
C11	C27	C28	120.4 (4)	C134 C133 Si6	127.2 (6)
C20	C28	C24	119.3 (3)	C134 C133 C138	116.3 (8)
C20	C28	C27	120.4 (4)	C138 C133 Si6	116.1 (6)
C24	C28	C27	120.3 (4)	C5B C4B C133	120.0
C30	C29	C1	168.8 (5)	C4B C5B C6B	120.0
C29	C30	Si1	172.3 (5)	C7B C6B C5B	120.0
C32	C31	C4	170.6 (6)	C8B C7B C6B	120.0
C31	C32	Si2	167.4 (5)	C7B C8B C133	120.0
C34	C33	C14	170.6 (5)	C133 C134 C135	119.7 (11)
C33	C34	Si4	168.2 (5)	C136 C135 C134	117.1 (12)
C36	C35	C17	169.3 (6)	C137 C136 C135	123.8 (14)
C35	C36	Si5	174.0 (6)	C136 C137 C138	120.3 (14)
C38	C37	Si1	122.7 (5)	C137 C138 C133	121.6 (12)
C38	C37	C42	116.9 (6)	C140 C139 Si6	121.7 (4)
C42	C37	Si1	120.0 (5)	C144 C139 Si6	122.1 (4)
C37	C38	C39	121.9 (6)	C144 C139 C140	116.2 (5)
C40	C39	C38	119.8 (7)	C141 C140 C139	122.3 (6)
C39	C40	C41	121.1 (7)	C142 C141 C140	119.2 (6)
C42	C41	C40	118.5 (7)	C143 C142 C141	120.4 (6)
C41	C42	C37	121.2 (7)	C142 C143 C144	119.1 (7)
C44	C43	Si1	118.5 (4)	C139 C144 C143	122.7 (6)
C48	C43	Si1	124.4 (4)	C2D C1E C6D	117.5 (8)
C48	C43	C44	117.0 (6)	C2D C1E C7D	121.7 (9)
C45	C44	C43	120.9 (6)	C6D C1E C7D	120.7 (8)
C46	C45	C44	120.0 (6)	C1E C2D C3D	121.8 (8)
C04A	C046	C79	121.6 (9)	C4D C3D C2D	119.9 (8)
C47	C46	C45	119.9 (7)	C5D C4D C3D	117.8 (9)
C46	C47	C48	120.0 (7)	C4D C5D C6D	122.3 (8)
C43	C48	C47	122.1 (6)	C5D C6D C1E	120.6 (8)

Table 6 Torsion Angles for a201801852_jmm182.

A	B	C	D	Angle/°	A	B	C	D	Angle/°
Si1	C37	C38	C39	-179.9 (6)	C37	Si1	C43	C44	60.7 (5)
Si1	C37	C42	C41	179.4 (7)	C37	Si1	C43	C48	-121.6 (5)
Si1	C43	C44	C45	178.0 (6)	C37	Si1	C49	C50	19.5 (7)
Si1	C43	C48	C47	-176.8 (6)	C37	Si1	C49	C54	-161.3 (4)
Si1	C49	C50	C51	179.5 (8)	C37	C38	C39	C40	-1.3 (12)
Si1	C49	C54	C53	-179.7 (5)	C38	C37	C42	C41	-7.6 (13)
Si2	C55	C56	C57	179.5 (5)	C38	C39	C40	C41	-5.0 (13)
Si2	C55	C60	C59	179.4 (6)	C39	C40	C41	C42	4.7 (14)
Si2	C61	C62	C63	179.0 (6)	C40	C41	C42	C37	1.8 (15)
Si2	C61	C66	C65	-177.4 (7)	C42	C37	C38	C39	7.3 (11)
Si2	C67	C68	C69	173.5 (5)	C43	Si1	C37	C38	116.1 (5)
Si2	C67	C72	C71	-174.9 (5)	C43	Si1	C37	C42	-71.3 (7)
Si3	C6CA	C78B	C77B	-166.2 (8)	C43	Si1	C49	C50	143.4 (6)
Si3	C6CA	C74B	C75B	166.9 (8)	C43	Si1	C49	C54	-37.4 (5)
Si3	C9	C10	C11	174.9 (4)	C43	C44	C45	C46	-0.9 (12)
Si3	C73B	C78	C77	-175.2 (5)	C44	C43	C48	C47	1.1 (10)
Si3	C73B	C74	C75	175.0 (6)	C44	C45	C46	C47	0.7 (12)
Si3	C79	C80B	C81B	177.6 (4)	C45	C46	C47	C48	0.4 (12)
Si3	C79	C84	C83	-177.6 (4)	C046	C04A	C82	C83B	11.5 (16)
Si3	C79	C84B	C83B	-178.3 (9)	C046	C79	C84B	C83B	7.0 (14)
Si3	C85	C86	C87	-179.8 (5)	C46	C47	C48	C43	-1.3 (12)
Si3	C85	C90	C89	178.3 (7)	C48	C43	C44	C45	0.0 (10)
Si4	C91	C92	C93	-178.4 (7)	C49	Si1	C37	C38	-123.6 (6)
Si4	C91	C96	C95	-179.9 (11)	C49	Si1	C37	C42	49.0 (7)
Si4	C91	C96B	C95B	174.5 (12)	C49	Si1	C43	C44	-60.3 (5)
Si4	C97	C98	C99	175.0 (5)	C49	Si1	C43	C48	117.5 (5)
Si4	C97	C102	C101	-175.1 (5)	C49	C50	C51	C52	0.6 (16)
Si4	C103	C104	C105	-173.5 (5)	C50	C49	C54	C53	-0.5 (9)
Si4	C103	C108	C107	174.2 (5)	C50	C51	C52	C53	-1.2 (15)
Si5	C15B	C20B	C19B	-177.1 (8)	C51	C52	C53	C54	1.1 (12)
Si5	C15B	C16B	C17B	177.2 (8)	C52	C53	C54	C49	-0.2 (10)
Si5	C109	C110	C111	178.5 (5)	C54	C49	C50	C51	0.3 (13)
Si5	C109	C114	C113	-178.2 (7)	C55	Si2	C32	C31	34 (3)
Si5	C115	C120	C119	177.9 (8)	C55	Si2	C61	C62	53.0 (6)
Si5	C115	C116	C117	-177.9 (8)	C55	Si2	C61	C66	-126.5 (6)
Si5	C121	C122	C123	177.9 (5)	C55	Si2	C67	C68	-107.9 (5)
Si5	C121	C126	C125	-179.5 (6)	C55	Si2	C67	C72	66.4 (5)
Si6	C22	C23	C24	-179.8 (3)	C55	C56	C57	C58	0.1 (10)
Si6	C127	C128	C129	178.0 (3)	C56	C55	C60	C59	-0.2 (10)
Si6	C127	C132	C131	-177.9 (3)	C56	C57	C58	C59	1.7 (11)
Si6	C133	C4B	C5B	-175.8 (4)	C57	C58	C59	C60	-2.8 (13)
Si6	C133	C8B	C7B	175.7 (4)	C58	C59	C60	C55	2.1 (12)
Si6	C133	C134	C135	-179.4 (8)	C60	C55	C56	C57	-0.9 (9)

Si6	C133	C138	C137	175.0 (11)	C61	Si2	C32	C31	-85 (3)
Si6	C139	C140	C141	179.6 (5)	C61	Si2	C55	C56	89.6 (5)
Si6	C139	C144	C143	177.8 (7)	C61	Si2	C55	C60	-90.0 (6)
N1	C5	C26	N4	-4.2 (7)	C61	Si2	C67	C68	14.9 (6)
N1	C5	C26	C1	178.2 (4)	C61	Si2	C67	C72	-170.8 (4)
N1	C6	C7	C8	5.4 (6)	C61	C62	C63	C64	1.9 (12)
N1	C6	C7	C27	-176.6 (4)	C62	C61	C66	C65	3.1 (13)
N1	C6	C25	N4	-4.9 (6)	C62	C63	C64	C65	-4.2 (15)
N1	C6	C25	C24	175.9 (4)	C63	C64	C65	C66	5.9 (17)
N2	C12	C19	N3	7.8 (7)	C64	C65	C66	C61	-5.1 (15)
N2	C12	C19	C20	-174.1 (4)	C66	C61	C62	C63	-1.4 (11)
N2	C13	C14	C15	175.6 (5)	C67	Si2	C32	C31	153 (2)
N2	C13	C14	C33	-3.9 (8)	C67	Si2	C55	C56	-148.4 (5)
N2	C13	C18	N3	6.5 (7)	C67	Si2	C55	C60	32.0 (6)
N2	C13	C18	C17	-173.7 (4)	C67	Si2	C61	C62	-67.7 (6)
N3	C19	C20	C21	-8.3 (6)	C67	Si2	C61	C66	112.7 (6)
N3	C19	C20	C28	172.5 (4)	C67	C68	C69	C70	1.6 (11)
C1	C2	C3	C4	-0.1 (9)	C68	C67	C72	C71	-0.4 (8)
C16	C17	C18	N3	176.7 (5)	C68	C69	C70	C71	-0.9 (11)
C16	C17	C18	C13	-3.1 (7)	C69	C70	C71	C72	-0.4 (10)
C16	C17	C35	C36	10 (3)	C70	C71	C72	C67	1.1 (9)
C28B	C29B	C130	C31B	15.1 (14)	C72	C67	C68	C69	-1.0 (9)
C32B	C31B	C130	C29B	-12.4 (14)	C73B	Si3	C79	C046	-76.3 (7)
C31B	C32B	C127	Si6	178.9 (8)	C73B	Si3	C79	C84B	109.4 (8)
C31B	C32B	C127	C28B	6.4 (13)	C73B	Si3	C85	C86	11.4 (5)
C29B	C28B	C127	Si6	-177.2 (7)	C73B	Si3	C85	C90	-168.8 (6)
C29B	C28B	C127	C32B	-4.5 (12)	C73B	C78	C77	C76	0.0
C15B	Si5	C109	C110	137.3 (6)	C78	C73B	C74	C75	0.0
C15B	Si5	C109	C114	-45.0 (7)	C78	C77	C76	C75	0.0
C15B	Si5	C121	C122	76.3 (6)	C77	C76	C75	C74	0.0
C15B	Si5	C121	C126	-104.8 (6)	C76	C75	C74	C73B	0.0
C15B	C20B	C19B	C18B	0.0	C74	C73B	C78	C77	0.0
C20B	C15B	C16B	C17B	0.0	C79	Si3	C6CA	C78B	-18.9 (7)
C20B	C19B	C18B	C17B	0.0	C79	Si3	C6CA	C74B	174.5 (5)
C19B	C18B	C17B	C16B	0.0	C79	Si3	C85	C86	135.8 (4)
C18B	C17B	C16B	C15B	0.0	C79	Si3	C85	C90	-44.4 (6)
C16B	C15B	C20B	C19B	0.0	C79	C80B	C81B	C82	0.0
C2	C1	C26	N4	-177.7 (5)	C80B	C79	C84	C83	0.0
C2	C1	C26	C5	-0.1 (7)	C80B	C81B	C82	C83	0.0
C2	C1	C29	C30	2 (3)	C81B	C82	C83	C84	0.0
C2	C3	C4	C5	0.1 (9)	C82	C04A	C046	C79	-2.4 (16)
C2	C3	C4	C31	179.1 (6)	C82	C83	C84	C79	0.0
C3	C4	C5	N1	-178.2 (5)	C82	C83B	C84B	C79	1.5 (19)
C3	C4	C5	C26	-0.1 (8)	C84	C79	C80B	C81B	0.0
C4	C5	C26	N4	177.7 (4)	C85	Si3	C6CA	C78B	99.8 (7)

C4	C5	C26	C1	0.1 (7)	C85	Si3	C6CA	C74B	-66.8 (6)
C04A	C046	C79	Si3	178.8 (8)	C85	Si3	C79	C046	165.3 (6)
C04A	C046	C79	C84B	-6.5 (13)	C85	Si3	C79	C80B	125.0 (7)
C04A	C82	C83B	C84B	-11.0 (18)	C85	Si3	C79	C84	-57.4 (7)
C5	N1	C6	C7	-175.3 (4)	C85	Si3	C79	C84B	-9.0 (8)
C5	N1	C6	C25	3.3 (6)	C85	C86	C87	C88	0.0 (10)
C6	N1	C5	C4	179.1 (4)	C86	C85	C90	C89	-1.9 (11)
C6	N1	C5	C26	1.0 (6)	C86	C87	C88	C89	1.1 (13)
C6	C7	C8	C9	177.3 (4)	C87	C88	C89	C90	-2.6 (15)
C6	C7	C27	C11	178.6 (4)	C88	C89	C90	C85	3.1 (15)
C6	C7	C27	C28	-2.6 (6)	C90	C85	C86	C87	0.4 (9)
C6CA	Si3	C79	C80B	-114.8 (8)	C91	Si4	C34	C33	143 (3)
C6CA	Si3	C79	C84	62.8 (8)	C91	Si4	C97	C98	-62.3 (6)
C6CA	Si3	C85	C86	20.6 (6)	C91	Si4	C97	C102	114.8 (5)
C6CA	Si3	C85	C90	-159.5 (6)	C91	Si4	C103	C104	8.5 (6)
C6CA	C78B	C77B	C76B	0.0	C91	Si4	C103	C108	-164.5 (5)
C78B	C6CA	C74B	C75B	0.0	C91	C92	C93	C94	-10.6 (18)
C78B	C77B	C76B	C75B	0.0	C91	C92	C93	C94B	12.4 (13)
C77B	C76B	C75B	C74B	0.0	C92	C91	C96	C95	-12.6 (18)
C76B	C75B	C74B	C6CA	0.0	C92	C91	C96B	C95B	16.1 (19)
C74B	C6CA	C78B	C77B	0.0	C92	C93	C94	C95	6 (2)
C7	C6	C25	N4	173.6 (4)	C92	C93	C94B	C95B	-2 (2)
C7	C6	C25	C24	-5.6 (6)	C93	C94	C95	C96	-5 (2)
C7	C8	C9	Si3	-174.1 (4)	C93	C94B	C95B	C96B	-1 (3)
C7	C8	C9	C10	3.9 (7)	C94	C95	C96	C91	10 (3)
C7	C27	C28	C20	-178.0 (4)	C94B	C95B	C96B	C91	-6 (3)
C7	C27	C28	C24	1.3 (6)	C96	C91	C92	C93	12.9 (13)
C8	C7	C27	C11	-3.3 (6)	C96B	C91	C92	C93	-20.3 (15)
C8	C7	C27	C28	175.4 (4)	C97	Si4	C34	C33	-95 (3)
C8	C9	C10	C11	-3.1 (7)	C97	Si4	C91	C92	-166.5 (5)
C9	Si3	C6CA	C78B	-137.0 (6)	C97	Si4	C91	C96	-0.1 (11)
C9	Si3	C6CA	C74B	56.3 (6)	C97	Si4	C91	C96B	34.7 (10)
C9	Si3	C79	C046	43.8 (6)	C97	Si4	C103	C104	-117.4 (5)
C9	Si3	C79	C80B	3.5 (8)	C97	Si4	C103	C108	69.6 (5)
C9	Si3	C79	C84	-178.9 (7)	C97	C98	C99	C100	0.9 (10)
C9	Si3	C79	C84B	-130.5 (7)	C98	C97	C102	C101	2.1 (9)
C9	Si3	C85	C86	-102.7 (5)	C98	C99	C100	C101	0.7 (11)
C9	Si3	C85	C90	77.2 (6)	C99	C100	C101	C102	-0.9 (11)
C9	C10	C11	C12	-176.4 (4)	C100	C101	C102	C97	-0.6 (11)
C9	C10	C11	C27	-0.9 (7)	C102	C97	C98	C99	-2.3 (9)
C10	C11	C12	N2	-8.1 (7)	C103	Si4	C34	C33	26 (3)
C10	C11	C12	C19	170.5 (4)	C103	Si4	C91	C92	66.7 (6)
C10	C11	C27	C7	4.1 (6)	C103	Si4	C91	C96	-126.9 (10)
C10	C11	C27	C28	-174.7 (4)	C103	Si4	C91	C96B	-92.1 (9)
C11	C12	C19	N3	-170.7 (4)	C103	Si4	C97	C98	61.7 (6)

C11	C12	C19	C20	7.3 (6)	C103 Si4	C97	C102	-121.3 (5)
C11	C27	C28	C20	0.8 (6)	C103 C104	C105	C106	0.4 (11)
C11	C27	C28	C24	-179.9 (4)	C104 C103	C108	C107	0.9 (9)
C12	N2	C13	C14	-178.8 (4)	C104 C105	C106	C107	-0.8 (11)
C12	N2	C13	C18	-2.4 (7)	C105 C106	C107	C108	1.4 (11)
C12	C11	C27	C7	179.7 (4)	C106 C107	C108	C103	-1.4 (10)
C12	C11	C27	C28	0.9 (6)	C108 C103	C104	C105	-0.4 (9)
C12	C19	C20	C21	173.5 (4)	C109 Si5	C15B	C20B	94.3 (7)
C12	C19	C20	C28	-5.7 (6)	C109 Si5	C15B	C16B	-82.8 (6)
C13	N2	C12	C11	174.2 (4)	C109 Si5	C121	C122	-46.5 (6)
C13	N2	C12	C19	-4.4 (6)	C109 Si5	C121	C126	132.4 (5)
C13	C14	C15	C16	-0.6 (8)	C109 C110	C111	C112	0.0 (10)
C14	C13	C18	N3	-177.1 (4)	C110 C109	C114	C113	-0.3 (11)
C14	C13	C18	C17	2.7 (7)	C110 C111	C112	C113	-1.0 (11)
C15	C16	C17	C18	1.8 (8)	C111 C112	C113	C114	1.3 (13)
C15	C16	C17	C35	-174.6 (5)	C112 C113	C114	C109	-0.7 (13)
C17	C16	C15	C14	0.1 (9)	C114 C109	C110	C111	0.7 (9)
C18	N3	C19	C12	-3.6 (6)	C115 Si5	C109	C110	129.5 (6)
C18	N3	C19	C20	178.3 (4)	C115 Si5	C109	C114	-52.8 (7)
C18	C13	C14	C15	-0.8 (8)	C115 Si5	C121	C122	76.5 (6)
C18	C13	C14	C33	179.7 (5)	C115 Si5	C121	C126	-104.6 (6)
C18	C17	C35	C36	-166 (3)	C115 C120	C119	C118	0.0
C19	N3	C18	C13	-3.2 (6)	C120 C115	C116	C117	0.0
C19	N3	C18	C17	177.0 (4)	C120 C119	C118	C117	0.0
C19	C20	C21	C22	180.0 (4)	C119 C118	C117	C116	0.0
C19	C20	C28	C24	-177.8 (4)	C118 C117	C116	C115	0.0
C19	C20	C28	C27	1.6 (6)	C116 C115	C120	C119	0.0
C20	C21	C22	Si6	179.5 (3)	C121 Si5	C15B	C20B	-28.8 (7)
C20	C21	C22	C23	-1.0 (7)	C121 Si5	C15B	C16B	154.0 (5)
C21	C20	C28	C24	3.1 (6)	C121 Si5	C109	C110	-102.3 (5)
C21	C20	C28	C27	-177.6 (4)	C121 Si5	C109	C114	75.5 (6)
C21	C22	C23	C24	0.6 (6)	C121 C122	C123	C124	0.9 (11)
C22	Si6	C127	C28B	109.0 (6)	C122 C121	C126	C125	-0.5 (10)
C22	Si6	C127	C32B	-63.3 (6)	C122 C123	C124	C125	0.8 (12)
C22	Si6	C127	C128	71.7 (5)	C123 C124	C125	C126	-2.4 (12)
C22	Si6	C127	C132	-110.3 (5)	C124 C125	C126	C121	2.2 (12)
C22	Si6	C133	C4B	11.0 (5)	C126 C121	C122	C123	-1.1 (9)
C22	Si6	C133	C8B	-164.7 (5)	C127 Si6	C22	C21	-22.6 (4)
C22	Si6	C133	C134	-1.0 (9)	C127 Si6	C22	C23	157.9 (3)
C22	Si6	C133	C138	170.4 (8)	C127 Si6	C133	C4B	130.9 (4)
C22	Si6	C139	C140	74.5 (5)	C127 Si6	C133	C8B	-44.8 (6)
C22	Si6	C139	C144	-102.7 (5)	C127 Si6	C133	C134	118.9 (9)
C22	C23	C24	C25	-179.0 (4)	C127 Si6	C133	C138	-69.7 (8)
C22	C23	C24	C28	1.6 (6)	C127 Si6	C139	C140	-47.7 (5)
C23	C24	C25	N4	5.7 (6)	C127 Si6	C139	C144	135.2 (5)

C23	C24	C25	C6	-175.1 (4)	C127	C28B	C29B	C130	-6.7 (15)
C23	C24	C28	C20	-3.4 (6)	C127	C32B	C31B	C130	1.6 (15)
C23	C24	C28	C27	177.2 (4)	C127	C128	C129	C130	0.0
C25	N4	C26	C1	-179.8 (4)	C128	C127	C132	C131	0.0
C25	N4	C26	C5	2.7 (6)	C128	C129	C130	C131	0.0
C25	C6	C7	C8	-173.2 (4)	C129	C130	C131	C132	0.0
C25	C6	C7	C27	4.8 (6)	C130	C131	C132	C127	0.0
C25	C24	C28	C20	177.2 (4)	C132	C127	C128	C129	0.0
C25	C24	C28	C27	-2.1 (6)	C133	Si6	C22	C21	94.2 (4)
C26	N4	C25	C6	1.7 (6)	C133	Si6	C22	C23	-85.3 (4)
C26	N4	C25	C24	-179.1 (4)	C133	Si6	C127	C28B	-9.2 (6)
C26	C1	C2	C3	0.1 (8)	C133	Si6	C127	C32B	178.4 (6)
C26	C1	C29	C30	-178 (3)	C133	Si6	C127	C128	-46.5 (5)
C27	C7	C8	C9	-0.8 (7)	C133	Si6	C127	C132	131.4 (5)
C27	C11	C12	N2	176.4 (4)	C133	Si6	C139	C140	-166.6 (4)
C27	C11	C12	C19	-5.0 (6)	C133	Si6	C139	C144	16.2 (5)
C28	C20	C21	C22	-0.8 (6)	C133	C4B	C5B	C6B	0.0
C28	C24	C25	N4	-175.0 (4)	C133	C134	C135	C136	-1 (2)
C28	C24	C25	C6	4.3 (6)	C4B	C133	C8B	C7B	0.0
C29	C1	C2	C3	179.8 (5)	C4B	C5B	C6B	C7B	0.0
C29	C1	C26	N4	2.6 (7)	C5B	C6B	C7B	C8B	0.0
C29	C1	C26	C5	-179.8 (4)	C6B	C7B	C8B	C133	0.0
C30	Si1	C37	C38	-4.9 (6)	C8B	C133	C4B	C5B	0.0
C30	Si1	C37	C42	167.7 (6)	C134	C133	C138	C137	-12.6 (18)
C30	Si1	C43	C44	-178.8 (5)	C134	C135	C136	C137	-5 (2)
C30	Si1	C43	C48	-1.0 (6)	C135	C136	C137	C138	2 (3)
C30	Si1	C49	C50	-98.5 (6)	C136	C137	C138	C133	7 (2)
C30	Si1	C49	C54	80.8 (5)	C138	C133	C134	C135	9.2 (16)
C31	C4	C5	N1	2.8 (8)	C139	Si6	C22	C21	-145.1 (4)
C31	C4	C5	C26	-179.1 (5)	C139	Si6	C22	C23	35.4 (4)
C32	Si2	C55	C56	-26.0 (6)	C139	Si6	C127	C28B	-131.2 (6)
C32	Si2	C55	C60	154.4 (5)	C139	Si6	C127	C32B	56.4 (6)
C32	Si2	C61	C62	167.6 (6)	C139	Si6	C127	C128	-168.5 (5)
C32	Si2	C61	C66	-11.9 (7)	C139	Si6	C127	C132	9.4 (5)
C32	Si2	C67	C68	135.3 (5)	C139	Si6	C133	C4B	-106.9 (4)
C32	Si2	C67	C72	-50.4 (5)	C139	Si6	C133	C8B	77.3 (5)
C33	C14	C15	C16	178.9 (5)	C139	Si6	C133	C134	-118.9 (9)
C34	Si4	C91	C92	-47.4 (6)	C139	Si6	C133	C138	52.5 (9)
C34	Si4	C91	C96	119.0 (10)	C139	C140	C141	C142	4.2 (11)
C34	Si4	C91	C96B	153.9 (9)	C140	C139	C144	C143	0.5 (10)
C34	Si4	C97	C98	176.8 (5)	C140	C141	C142	C143	-2.7 (11)
C34	Si4	C97	C102	-6.1 (6)	C141	C142	C143	C144	0.2 (13)
C34	Si4	C103	C104	126.0 (5)	C142	C143	C144	C139	0.9 (13)
C34	Si4	C103	C108	-47.0 (5)	C144	C139	C140	C141	-3.1 (9)
C35	C17	C18	N3	-7.1 (7)	C1E	C2D	C3D	C4D	1.2 (12)

C35	C17	C18	C13	173.1 (5)	C2D	C1E	C6D	C5D	-1.2 (11)
C36	Si5	C15B	C20B	-145.7 (5)	C2D	C3D	C4D	C5D	-0.5 (12)
C36	Si5	C15B	C16B	37.1 (6)	C3D	C4D	C5D	C6D	-1.0 (12)
C36	Si5	C109	C110	16.2 (6)	C4D	C5D	C6D	C1E	2.0 (12)
C36	Si5	C109	C114	-166.1 (6)	C6D	C1E	C2D	C3D	-0.4 (12)
C36	Si5	C121	C122	-165.3 (5)	C7D	C1E	C2D	C3D	179.6 (8)
C36	Si5	C121	C126	13.7 (6)	C7D	C1E	C6D	C5D	178.8 (8)

Table 7 Hydrogen Atom Coordinates ($\text{\AA}\times 10^4$) and Isotropic Displacement Parameters ($\text{\AA}^2\times 10^3$) for a201801852_jmm182.

Atom	x	y	z	U(eq)
H16	6311.57	1998.91	4629.32	76
H28B	2268.27	2305.25	3746.1	82
H32B	2934.42	-190.4	3426.04	88
H31B	2966.58	-865.22	3915.65	99
H29B	2373.34	1654.4	4236.08	83
H20B	2479.07	2520.2	4815.87	110
H19B	1853.51	1198.49	4975.49	111
H18B	2437.6	-264.12	5070.9	102
H17B	3647.27	-405.03	5006.67	120
H16B	4272.85	916.66	4847.04	110
H2	3055.58	2422.6	1110.4	79
H3	4198	2314.33	963.88	83
H04A	8045.31	-763.9	2013.56	107
H78B	8495.3	2261.2	1867.59	95
H77B	8568.56	3318.45	1459.14	115
H76B	7933.42	4758.26	1439.52	87
H75B	7225.02	5140.83	1828.36	114
H74B	7151.75	4083.59	2236.82	102
H8	6443.6	2174.56	2143.65	64
H10	7254.61	2023.28	3028.84	63
H15	7436.01	1746.91	4474.24	78
H21	4004.76	1746.77	3453.3	58
H23	3181.66	1859.78	2565.72	57
H38	1695.86	3372.11	2161.28	91
H39	1359.57	4234.68	2581.22	124
H40	202.55	4684.63	2594.14	126
H41	-628.52	4481.13	2161.6	132
H42	-292.7	3638.52	1744.28	131
H44	-474.16	1963.76	1497.85	99
H45	-1067.39	507.6	1426.29	114
H046	7486.39	652.69	2123.74	91
H46	-426.34	-903.84	1417.5	110
H47	804.79	-869.2	1489.11	120

H48	1402.2	577.5	1576.12	103
H50	653.06	4627.9	1423.81	133
H51	349.26	5479.31	979.62	148
H52	218.73	4699.76	513.15	117
H53	437.32	3064.42	488.25	100
H54	750.28	2204.77	936.92	83
H56	5213.03	1143.26	658.5	84
H57	4613.78	912.14	168.58	100
H58	5231.05	1182.3	-261.25	112
H59	6418.12	1582.12	-195.67	113
H60	6998.22	1857.03	286.18	98
H62	7612.38	295.45	715.98	115
H63	8187.8	-1103.03	928.18	130
H64	7893.5	-1597.98	1392.89	141
H65	7224.64	-718.72	1682.37	160
H66	6623.35	603.22	1465.22	135
H68	8210.72	1862.05	959.2	90
H69	9021.02	3063.62	865.91	104
H70	8616	4617.05	756.12	96
H71	7414.93	4946.77	727.11	92
H72	6603.69	3759.5	799.48	83
H78	8379.6	2577.33	1847.22	66
H77	8314.55	3684.11	1445.65	78
H76	7645.91	5084.81	1473.23	78
H75	7042.3	5378.74	1902.37	89
H74	7107.33	4271.97	2303.95	83
H80B	7517.86	393.66	2434.58	121
H81B	8081.06	-1018.97	2306.11	164
H82	9255.42	-911.48	2132.68	123
H82A	9236.49	-965.46	2160.05	123
H83	9828.72	500.68	2142.47	129
H84	9265.53	1913.32	2270.94	123
H83B	9806.83	26.04	2487.7	129
H84B	9285.59	1476.88	2620.45	114
H86	8348.96	4419.51	2572.17	87
H87	9032.99	5243.41	2958.04	104
H88	9532.6	4397.22	3388.32	121
H89	9385.83	2768.48	3416.34	138
H90	8663.85	1955.11	3043.63	104
H92	8869.52	-360.7	3587.73	117
H93	9198.35	-1249.57	3192.4	132
H93A	9144.39	-1111.52	3128.27	132
H94	10016.48	-766.48	2880.09	92
H94B	10362.63	-772.36	2999.46	96
H95	10706.68	546.12	3064.54	103

H95B	11074.02	235.46	3248.27	135
H96	10402.64	1459.71	3469.56	85
H96B	10738.97	1078.2	3676.23	120
H98	10903.56	1783.87	4127.84	97
H99	11494.52	3226.52	4182.68	111
H100	10854.21	4668.95	4140.92	109
H101	9639.82	4629.92	4052.97	106
H102	9039.1	3223.73	3995.33	94
H104	10088.4	-712.02	4089.06	106
H105	10111.35	-1814.2	4480.13	122
H106	9590.05	-1521.96	4909.94	118
H107	9032.16	-36.17	4974.54	126
H108	8978.84	1100	4579.59	106
H110	5393.17	3683.36	4899.76	89
H111	5930.82	4455.48	5332.27	102
H112	5298.31	4709.23	5752.25	106
H113	4141.89	4245.98	5736.24	124
H114	3585.34	3448.56	5304.2	112
H120	2531.92	2227.92	4839.32	66
H119	2020.44	809.83	4995.91	77
H118	2728.8	-547.59	5101.56	80
H117	3948.65	-486.93	5050.62	94
H116	4460.14	931.15	4894.03	88
H122	2844.18	4266.33	4827.65	104
H123	2108.98	5337.92	4535.06	119
H124	2138.16	5422.22	4013.43	120
H125	2882.56	4400.16	3776.1	122
H126	3652.47	3382.57	4066.2	98
H128	2989.46	2273.69	3756.82	76
H129	2977.98	1643.75	4249.74	101
H13A	2527.88	106.89	4316.34	116
H130	2440.87	87.3	4305.85	116
H131	2089.27	-800.03	3890.02	135
H132	2100.75	-170.1	3397.09	99
H4B	2935.75	3571.08	2958.73	85
H5B	2529.27	5132.24	3022.63	89
H6B	1513.78	5397.81	3273.4	97
H7B	904.76	4102.23	3460.27	103
H8B	1311.22	2541.06	3396.36	81
H134	2965.55	3772.56	3068.21	49
H135	2329.85	5281.13	3134.89	68
H136	1213.65	5197.57	3281.54	80
H137	623.13	3808.75	3306.58	81
H138	1153.66	2385.96	3201.09	65
H140	2441.03	-342.3	2956.63	94

H141	1762.98	-1247.53	2594.99	104
H142	1000.84	-486.57	2222	104
H143	846	1156.75	2239.63	130
H144	1471.07	2037.21	2627.07	103
H2D	8916.99	2213.19	5102.33	115
H3D	8427.64	1443.54	5499.18	123
H4D	7247.74	1751.81	5585.49	123
H5D	6602.72	2841.98	5273.12	126
H6D	7102.47	3653.64	4895.87	121
H7DA	8481.46	4177.74	4766.77	191
H7DB	8040.42	3501.76	4521.31	191
H7DC	8819.4	3191.93	4666.14	191

Table 8 Atomic Occupancy for a201801852_jmm182.

Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy	Atom	Occupancy
C28B	0.556 (11)	H28B	0.556 (11)	C32B	0.556 (11)
H32B	0.556 (11)	C31B	0.556 (11)	H31B	0.556 (11)
C29B	0.556 (11)	H29B	0.556 (11)	C15B	0.58 (3)
C20B	0.58 (3)	H20B	0.58 (3)	C19B	0.58 (3)
H19B	0.58 (3)	C18B	0.58 (3)	H18B	0.58 (3)
C17B	0.58 (3)	H17B	0.58 (3)	C16B	0.58 (3)
H16B	0.58 (3)	C04A	0.631 (12)	H04A	0.631 (12)
C6CA	0.46 (2)	C78B	0.46 (2)	H78B	0.46 (2)
C77B	0.46 (2)	H77B	0.46 (2)	C76B	0.46 (2)
H76B	0.46 (2)	C75B	0.46 (2)	H75B	0.46 (2)
C74B	0.46 (2)	H74B	0.46 (2)	C046	0.631 (12)
H046	0.631 (12)	C73B	0.54 (2)	C78	0.54 (2)
H78	0.54 (2)	C77	0.54 (2)	H77	0.54 (2)
C76	0.54 (2)	H76	0.54 (2)	C75	0.54 (2)
H75	0.54 (2)	C74	0.54 (2)	H74	0.54 (2)
C80B	0.369 (12)	H80B	0.369 (12)	C81B	0.369 (12)
H81B	0.369 (12)	H82	0.631 (12)	H82A	0.369 (12)
C83	0.369 (12)	H83	0.369 (12)	C84	0.369 (12)
H84	0.369 (12)	C83B	0.631 (12)	H83B	0.631 (12)
C84B	0.631 (12)	H84B	0.631 (12)	H93	0.45 (2)
H93A	0.55 (2)	C94	0.45 (2)	H94	0.45 (2)
C94B	0.55 (2)	H94B	0.55 (2)	C95	0.45 (2)
H95	0.45 (2)	C95B	0.55 (2)	H95B	0.55 (2)
C96	0.45 (2)	H96	0.45 (2)	C96B	0.55 (2)
H96B	0.55 (2)	C115	0.42 (3)	C120	0.42 (3)
H120	0.42 (3)	C119	0.42 (3)	H119	0.42 (3)
C118	0.42 (3)	H118	0.42 (3)	C117	0.42 (3)
H117	0.42 (3)	C116	0.42 (3)	H116	0.42 (3)

C128	0.444 (11)	H128	0.444 (11)	C129	0.444 (11)
H129	0.444 (11)	H13A	0.444 (11)	H130	0.556 (11)
C131	0.444 (11)	H131	0.444 (11)	C132	0.444 (11)
H132	0.444 (11)	C4B	0.61 (2)	H4B	0.61 (2)
C5B	0.61 (2)	H5B	0.61 (2)	C6B	0.61 (2)
H6B	0.61 (2)	C7B	0.61 (2)	H7B	0.61 (2)
C8B	0.61 (2)	H8B	0.61 (2)	C134	0.39 (2)
H134	0.39 (2)	C135	0.39 (2)	H135	0.39 (2)
C136	0.39 (2)	H136	0.39 (2)	C137	0.39 (2)
H137	0.39 (2)	C138	0.39 (2)	H138	0.39 (2)

Experimental

Single crystals of C₁₅₁H₁₀₆N₄Si₆ [a201801852_jmm182]. A suitable crystal was selected and mounted on a SuperNova, Single source at offset/far, Atlas diffractometer. The crystal was kept at 150.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the ShelXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the ShelXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

1. Dolomanov, O.V., Bourhis, L.J., Gildea, R.J., Howard, J.A.K. & Puschmann, H. (2009), *J. Appl. Cryst.* 42, 339-341.
2. Sheldrick, G.M. (2015). *Acta Cryst.* A71, 3-8.
3. Sheldrick, G.M. (2015). *Acta Cryst.* C71, 3-8.

Crystal structure determination of [a201801852_jmm182]

Crystal Data for C₁₅₁H₁₀₆N₄Si₆ (*M* = 2144.93 g/mol): monoclinic, space group P2₁/n (no. 14), *a* = 18.8903(2) Å, *b* = 13.9779(2) Å, *c* = 43.9341(8) Å, β = 96.0313(15)°, *V* = 11536.4(3) Å³, *Z* = 4, *T* = 150.00(10) K, μ (CuK α) = 1.120 mm⁻¹, *D*_{calc} = 1.235 g/cm³, 92397 reflections measured (6.64° ≤ 2 θ ≤ 137.998°), 21438 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0720, *R*_{sigma} = 0.0501) which were used in all calculations. The final *R*₁ was 0.1071 (*I* > 2 σ (*I*)) and *wR*₂ was 0.3523 (all data).

Refinement model description

Number of restraints - 361, number of constraints - unknown.

Details:

1. Fixed Uiso
At 1.2 times of:
All C(H) groups, All C(H,H) groups
At 1.5 times of:
All C(H,H,H) groups
2. Restrained distances
Si5-C15B
1.87 with sigma of 0.01
3. Uiso/Uanis restraints and constraints
Uanis(C84B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C83B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C83) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C04A) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C81B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C80B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C046) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C84) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002
Uanis(C96B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C95B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C96) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C94B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C94) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002
Uanis(C129) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C128) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C31B) ≈ Ueq,
Uanis(C131) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C32B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C132) ≈ Ueq,
Uanis(C29B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C28B) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002
Uanis(C8B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C7B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C137) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C138) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C95) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002
Uanis(C136) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C6B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C135) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C5B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C4B) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C134) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002
Uanis(C66) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C65) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C64) ≈ Ueq, Uanis(C63) ≈ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C6CA) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C73B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C74B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C74)
 $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C75) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C75B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C76) $\approx$ Ueq,
Uanis(C76B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C77) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C77B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C78)
 $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C78B) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma of 0.001 and sigma for terminal
atoms of 0.002

Uanis(C20B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C120) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C19B) $\approx$ Ueq,
Uanis(C119) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C18B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C118) $\approx$ Ueq,
Uanis(C117) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C17B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C116) $\approx$ Ueq,
Uanis(C16B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C15B) $\approx$ Ueq, Uanis(C115) $\approx$ Ueq: with sigma
of 0.001 and sigma for terminal atoms of 0.002

4. Others

Sof(C128)=Sof(H128)=Sof(C129)=Sof(H129)=Sof(H13A)=Sof(C131)=Sof(H131)=
Sof(C132)=Sof(H132)=1-FVAR(1)
Sof(C28B)=Sof(H28B)=Sof(C32B)=Sof(H32B)=Sof(C31B)=Sof(H31B)=Sof(C29B)=
Sof(H29B)=Sof(H130)=FVAR(1)
Sof(C134)=Sof(H134)=Sof(C135)=Sof(H135)=Sof(C136)=Sof(H136)=Sof(C137)=
Sof(H137)=Sof(C138)=Sof(H138)=1-FVAR(2)
Sof(C4B)=Sof(H4B)=Sof(C5B)=Sof(H5B)=Sof(C6B)=Sof(H6B)=Sof(C7B)=Sof(H7B)=
Sof(C8B)=Sof(H8B)=FVAR(2)
Sof(H93A)=Sof(C94B)=Sof(H94B)=Sof(C95B)=Sof(H95B)=Sof(C96B)=Sof(H96B)=1-
FVAR(3)
Sof(H93)=Sof(C94)=Sof(H94)=Sof(C95)=Sof(H95)=Sof(C96)=Sof(H96)=FVAR(3)
Sof(C80B)=Sof(H80B)=Sof(C81B)=Sof(H81B)=Sof(H82A)=Sof(C83)=Sof(H83)=Sof(C84)=
Sof(H84)=1-FVAR(4)
Sof(C04A)=Sof(H04A)=Sof(C046)=Sof(H046)=Sof(H82)=Sof(C83B)=Sof(H83B)=
Sof(C84B)=Sof(H84B)=FVAR(4)
Sof(C115)=Sof(C120)=Sof(H120)=Sof(C119)=Sof(H119)=Sof(C118)=Sof(H118)=
Sof(C117)=Sof(H117)=Sof(C116)=Sof(H116)=1-FVAR(5)
Sof(C15B)=Sof(C20B)=Sof(H20B)=Sof(C19B)=Sof(H19B)=Sof(C18B)=Sof(H18B)=
Sof(C17B)=Sof(H17B)=Sof(C16B)=Sof(H16B)=FVAR(5)
Sof(C6CA)=Sof(C78B)=Sof(H78B)=Sof(C77B)=Sof(H77B)=Sof(C76B)=Sof(H76B)=
Sof(C75B)=Sof(H75B)=Sof(C74B)=Sof(H74B)=1-FVAR(6)
Sof(C73B)=Sof(C78)=Sof(H78)=Sof(C77)=Sof(H77)=Sof(C76)=Sof(H76)=Sof(C75)=
Sof(H75)=Sof(C74)=Sof(H74)=FVAR(6)

5.a Aromatic/amide H refined with riding coordinates:

C16(H16), C28B(H28B), C32B(H32B), C31B(H31B), C29B(H29B), C20B(H20B),
C19B(H19B), C18B(H18B), C17B(H17B), C16B(H16B), C2(H2), C3(H3), C04A(H04A),
C78B(H78B), C77B(H77B), C76B(H76B), C75B(H75B), C74B(H74B), C8(H8), C10(H10),
C15(H15), C21(H21), C23(H23), C38(H38), C39(H39), C40(H40), C41(H41),
C42(H42),
C44(H44), C45(H45), C046(H046), C46(H46), C47(H47), C48(H48), C50(H50),
C51(H51), C52(H52), C53(H53), C54(H54), C56(H56), C57(H57), C58(H58),
C59(H59),
C60(H60), C62(H62), C63(H63), C64(H64), C65(H65), C66(H66), C68(H68),
C69(H69), C70(H70), C71(H71), C72(H72), C78(H78), C77(H77), C76(H76),
C75(H75),
C74(H74), C80B(H80B), C81B(H81B), C82(H82), C82(H82A), C83(H83), C84(H84),
C83B(H83B), C84B(H84B), C86(H86), C87(H87), C88(H88), C89(H89), C90(H90),
C92(H92), C93(H93), C93(H93A), C94(H94), C94B(H94B), C95(H95), C95B(H95B),
C96(H96), C96B(H96B), C98(H98), C99(H99), C100(H100), C101(H101), C102(H102),
C104(H104), C105(H105), C106(H106), C107(H107), C108(H108), C110(H110),
C111(H111), C112(H112), C113(H113), C114(H114), C120(H120), C119(H119),
C118(H118), C117(H117), C116(H116), C122(H122), C123(H123), C124(H124),
C125(H125), C126(H126), C128(H128), C129(H129), C130(H13A), C130(H130),
C131(H131), C132(H132), C4B(H4B), C5B(H5B), C6B(H6B), C7B(H7B), C8B(H8B),
C134(H134), C135(H135), C136(H136), C137(H137), C138(H138), C140(H140),
C141(H141), C142(H142), C143(H143), C144(H144), C2D(H2D), C3D(H3D), C4D(H4D),
C5D(H5D), C6D(H6D)

5.b Fitted hexagon refined as free rotating group:

C15B(C20B,C19B,C18B,C17B,C16B), C6CA(C78B,C77B,C76B,C75B,C74B), C73B(C78,C77,
C76,C75,C74), C79(C80B,C81B,C82,C83,C84), C115(C120,C119,C118,C117,C116),
C127(C128,C129,C130,C131,C132), C133(C4B,C5B,C6B,C7B,C8B)

5.c Idealised Me refined as rotating group:

C7D(H7DA,H7DB,H7DC)

References

- [35] A. M. Brouwer, *Pure. Appl. Chem.* **2011**, *83*, 2213-2228.